

Before the Common Era

Author's unfiltered and unordered research notes for posterity, written as entertainment.

Complete analytical refutation of Christianity: logical, linguistic, historical, Rabbinical, and permutational. Establishes distinction between Hebraism and Judaism.

Fractal permutational word splitting can be demonstrated highly nonrandom via entropic information measure.

Unfinished line by line permutational analysis, resting at Psalm 37, NASB 1977 ordering.

Pater, pattern

(Chronicles of Amber: Pattern vs Logrus ... Logus (Word) ... Log in the Courts of Chaos ... Cao)

ellipse, elapse (time counted)

Odin ... dino (bird)

apple, apparel

serpent, usurp

matrix, dominatrix

talia, retaliate

perish, parish

dolphin, Delphi, dauphin (Fr)

Ergotise, ergo (therefore, logic), Argo

Salt מֶלַח

Tyre (purple ... snail blood), tyrant, Tyrannosaurus Rex

Vampire, pyre

Coven, covenant

cat (pussy), cattle (cow), category theory (N chronicler), catastrophe (Solomon corruption), catabolism

mars, marshal (properly Ko)

Cao, chaos, cow

Ko, kowtow, Koran, Koren Tanakh, Kosher, Hong Kong, James Bible

Lot, lottery, plotting, lotus, lotus-eater, harlot

Cathay, Catholic, Cathy, cat (pussy), Catiline (conspiracy), Cato, cattle (cow), Cay, Kane (sugarcane,

soda, sod, Sodom, carbonation yeasty, murder brother), Canton, Cantonese

multipliCATION, fornicATION

Cow, coward, cowering, chowder (Boston ... Irish Catholic)

Bee, bet, beetle, Beta (bitch ass), masturbator (Master beta), betrayed, beat (zero sum vs helping, to

hit, drums), bitter, beast, Bethesda, beg, been, buttery, beard

Purim ("lots", Esther, ether "telepathy", Easter, East, ... jester)

Spill, spoil (G), spool, pill, ill

Cassius, Cass Tech, Cassidy Yates of DS9, casing, Casino

cruel, Reuel, rue

Hebrew ... the brew ... Coffee

Paris (Lancelot), parasite (Travis),

fleurdelis (Flis)

pillar, pill, ill

Sarah, seraph (Ishmael)

MIT, smith (Mithrandir), smite

skew (odds), skewer (impale, imp)

K, kill, skill

Dinah, denature

Guinevere, GUINEA pig

whore, horror, hordes, abhorrent

serpent (snake a toilet), usurp

Seti (death), settle

David, divide (multiplicative inverse)

Laps, Laplander (Finn, "fins and scales")

Prince, principled, principal, prime

Octave (music), Octavio, octopus (pussy) ... [vices]

Bach (lush X-tian), Bacchanal

Khazarian (K, Manchurian)

Apollo, apple, appall

Oklahoma (horses, X-tian commune), ... hokey, Kay, Oakland (James, Jae, J)

Kendall Square (soulless), Kenneth (South Park)

Cao Cao, Coca Cola, Macao

Pole, polygamy, pig, pollen, pollute, pillar, stake

cedar, Sedar, seed, Cid, acid

Athenian, atheist

Mormonism, moron
 Dogma, dog
 Salamander, mandarine
 virginity, Virginia
 Yaz, Yasmine, Yah's mine
 The Name, Nam (Chan Ho)
 Odin...dino
 assemble (congregation), assembly (language, fundamental)
 Hormah, Hor, horcrux, whore
 serpent, Sir, Servant
 cedar (logger), Seder (Passover)
 Zur (Cosby the daughter of), Zurich
 hat, hate
 Moses, mosaic (pattern, no idols)
 Mattanah, Manhattan (Project ... explode atom and Hebrew faith, projects, tenements, Harlem, Hurley),
 Matty (porn*), Mat (Cauthon, ... Cat)
 Halo (radioactive glow), halogenated (K)
 Poli, politics, police, polite, poll
 Base, alkaline (antithesis of acidic), Caligula
 parasite, Paris
 drag, Dragon (Vlad Tepes), Dagon
 Lyre, lyricist
 Puppy, puppet
 Odo, odometer, odour, ode (music)
 belly (snake), Belle, Baal
 Gotham (NYC, N), Goth (Cain)
 Meta, Metatron, metaphor, metastasis, McDonald's (M)
 apple, appalls, applause (custom reversal), Apollo, application
 Gauss (boob averages, studying curvature, primal numbers)
 Friedrich, Frieda, Freya
 Joseph, Joe, Job, "cup of Joe" (coffee, Yahweh), "get a job" (hardwork)
 Diary, dairy (plot), homogenised milk sugar from Dairy Queen
 alkaline (base) opposite of acidic
 whore, horror, hordes

E: Cain (sneaky), Dinah (allegedly raped), Mary Magdalene, Catherine the Great, Hypatia Neoplatonist,
 Earhart Amelia, Standhart Erica
 F: Behemoth, Moses, Faisal Siddiqui, Mephibosheth, Crowfoot
 G: Lilith, Snake, Rachel (period ... Dot Dorothy), Confucius, Nefertiti, Cosbi the daughter of Zur,
 Scheherazade, Esther, Galileo Galilee
 H: Paris of Troy, Lancelot
 J: Noah, Jonah, Job, Jeremiah, Leah, Deborah, Zerubbabel, Delilah, Sheba, Pilate, Euler, Fermat, Anne
 Frank, Jehoshaphat, Amenhotep
 K: James Hin Ting Ko ... Hin (gallon), hunting, anointing, cHINA
 Cherub of Eden, Lot (...lotus, to gamble/bet), Judah (sold Joseph), Aaron (golden calf, grandson of
 Kohath, later Korah rebellion), Elijah, Adonai-bezek, Hamilcar, Mithridates, Archimedes, Einstein,
 Riemann, Cao Cao (Coca Cola), Thutmose, Hiram of Tyre (ferryman), Octavio, Constantine,
 Niccolo Machiavelli ('Ol Nick), Nebuzaradan, Mordecai, Remus
 L: Abraham, Joseph, Enoch, Nimrod, Sargon, Pericles (Parthenon), Cyrus (rebuild temple), Solomon (temple
 bricklayer), Aristotle, Jason, Perseus, Hiawatha, Vladimir Tepes (Transylvania ... Michael), Arthur,
 Rama, Nebuchadnezzar, Master Sun, Lao Tzu, Saladin (Aladdin), Balaam son of Beor, Caesar, Marcus
 Aurelius, Ahasuerus, Romulus
 M: Satan, Sita, Miriam, Murasaki, Morgause, Ruth, Ramanujan, Hamedatha, Maimonides
 N: Leviathan (Lochness monster Nessy), Abel?, Isaac, Nathan, Themistocles, Cato, Diocletian?, Mordred,
 Leonardo da Vinci, Isaac Newton, Lenin, Grothendieck/Schapiro (category theory, chronicler), Paul of
 Tarsus of Cilicia, Socrates?, Haman
 R: Benjamin, Simmons (China)
 T: Trump Donald J. or Tesla?
 V: Vasilios, Cicero
 Y (next to X): Yasmine [Jasmine ... James]/Virginia Devi-Chou [Virgil Devil Cao], Ishmael, Gilgamesh,
 Richard Phillips Feynman (Richard of SOT Fine-man)("confinement" Genesis 40:3, "budding" Genesis 40:10),
 Potiphar's wife (Egyptian, ... gypsy), Aspasia of Athens, Yasodhara (Buddha's wife), Anastasia Romanovna,
 Hysicratia (Mithridates' concubine)

...
 Alexander Oleg Daniv: Israel
 (deep interest in genetics)
 Arjun Jaganathan Satyamoorthy: Arjuna
 Anna Flys: Michael, Achilles, Abimelech ... Amalekite
 Caleb from Brighton: Caleb
 Colin Clarke: Jules Henri Poincare

Edward Ku Cho: Zechariah, Doeg the Edomite, Diogenes (famously w. Alexander), Jack Kerouac, Archduke
Franz Ferdinand, Oedipus Laiades
Elina Pradhan: Hellen Keller (Killer)
Gideon from Brighton: Gideon
Jared Hudson (GTO gift): Jared
Jeffrey Thomas DeSano (Dr.): Demosthenes
Joel Nosanchuk: Laban, Joel the son of Pethuel
Jonathan Wagoner: Esau, Jeroboam
Joseph Martin Escobar (Felix, Sulla): Saul?
Josh White: Joshua
Marko M.G. Slusarczyk: Napoleon, Democritus
Odey Meroueh: Odysseus
Sarah Grey: Sarah
Shiuan Wei Lai: good thief, Lao Tzu's friend, Karl Weierstrass
Vasilios: Cicero (compared w. Demosthenes in Plutarch)
Yuyin Chen: Chenaniah (1 Chronicles 15:22,27), Telemachus, John Harvard

...
Marshall Mathers: David
David DeAngelo (Eben Pagan): Daniel
Elon Musk: Flaming Sword of Eden, Adolf Hitler, (Lucifer: Uriel)

Challengers:
Leviathan (N), Octopus (K), Succubus (E), Parasite (G), Hermaphrodite (Achilles)

Alexander relatives:
Hilbert, Kelvin, Banach, Schrodinger

David, Aaron, Saul, Felix, Pharaoh, Atreus, Jezebel, Rurik, Nevsky, Genghis Khan, Hideyoshi, Richard the
Lionhearted, Louis, Marie Antoinette, Thurn and Taxis, Aragorn, Van Dam, Ferdinand

Marshal "horse master", metaphorically women, because typically women control men.

Death the Diabolo does not have a license to do anything to take a soul; God has laws, it is personal.

War of the Genders.
After patriarchal excess, matriarchal revenge.
Human species mildly patriarchal, demonstrated by size difference between males and females.
Most abuse oblique because of heavy prison sentences, not physical but emotional violence.
Skewed scales that men have approximately 10x testosterone of women and held to equal standard. Why
women get everything in divorce, men are pinatas.
Exemplar is Travis vs Flis.

"Catholicism is matriarchal":
militaristic marshal/cacao/chaos

Essence of Polygamy:
Behaviorally men compete and women socialise. Men are more alone, women more in groups.
Consorts acceptable with permission, blessed if necessary.

...
Dominant women are the norm in China (Cathay), Italy, Ukraine.
Dominant men are the norm in Japan (Nihon), Arabia, Russia.

...
Catholicism like Cathay is based on dominant women, why Alexander loathes it.

Worm (Rounders 1998)
Kay just like Cane his namesake betrayed and murdered his brother. He needs to justify it so he creates
problems then pretends to solve them, just like a telemarketing identity theft scammer. Tokugawa: become
friends with your enemies so you know how to destroy them.

...
What's China doing to the West?
It cozies up, then bleeds it dry.

...
Joseph and Judah
Master Sun and Cao Cao
Caesar and Agosto
Aurelius and Constantine
Taiko and Tokugawa
Gauss and Riemann

Pattern of moral and physical corruption, until only soul remains.

Biblical promises targeted by Leviathan and Co. (Similar Hebrew characters for Kaf and Nun)
David promised a lamp, so destroy his religion, turn his kin into pariahs (Jews, Russians). Job promised a signet ring, alienate her, then inbreed her flesh to handicap.

Kali's thugs ... Cretins.

"Truth is in the mind of God.":
definition thought

Sugar is lethal.

"Law is digital, clemency subjective.":
ecclesiastical judgement

Relativity is selective application.

Samson lets his hair be cut by "The Philistines are upon you" Delilah.

...
Solomon:
"All is vanity",
"And rejoice in the wife of your youth" (Proverbs 5:18)
700 wives and 300 consorts shouts and records interference beyond incoherent testimony.

...
Judas and Jesus echoes Abraham and Isaac. Starts a fire from smouldering embers of Judaism, propagating good with bad. Could have stoned Jesus for blasphemy quietly, LORD arranges crucifixion symbolizing K (Judah), followed by religious thermonuclear blast.

Darwinian human male behavior beta or suboptimal long term, humans require nurturing.
Evolutionary fallacy: how does adaptation change the number of chromosomes?

[Dragon is dragooning, no permission hence wrongdoing!]

"Wife Jordan Consort Georgia Consort Virginia":
RETROGRESSION rancidification/incoordination/fornication/conviction/*DRAGOONING*/*WRONGDOING*/Darwinian/
gorgonian
DIVERSIFICATION congregations/*NEWTONIAN*
DRAGOONING REVERIFICATION

"Alexander Shapiro Grothendieck":
HADAD PALEOCORTEX SHRINKING
Hadad peregrination Sherlocke

...
prekindergarden ethical
PEREGRINATION HEXAHEDRAL/Sherlocke/axeheads/Heraclis
NATANIEL choreographer
Nataniel exorcise Godhead
DANDELION SCAPEGOATER
scapegoater hexahedron/Rhineland

...
Kleenex * [list of crimes]
Kleenex historiographer [4K years]
Kleenex coordinated Hagar
Kleenex choreograph tsarina
Kleenex addiction pharaoh
Kleenex diagnose Richard
Kleenex Hadad cooperating
Kleenex Schrodinger pariah
Kleenex rape (2221) originator/Siddhartha
Kleenex parasite Dacron/dragon
Kleenex operations Richard
Kleenex Aphro (4844) cantharidised
Kleenex tardigrade harpoons/scorpion
Kleenex tradership arachnoid
Kleenex patriarchies dragon
Kleenex Cain priesthood/Siddhartha/tardigrade/tradership/Aphrodite/posterior/hardship/shithead/Pharaoh
Kleenex Siddhartha coroner
Kleenex arachnoid adopter/pothead
Kleenex pothead signora Richard

...
Einstein hexahedral Ko

Cowardice is submission to fear. Abuse conditions fear, in my case of academics and women, the beat down of Catholic Amazons.

Distinguish between a cowardly soul and conditioned terror.

Distinguish between a moment of cowardice and a habit of cowardice.

The deepest scars are unseen.

Easiest to mold children, most profoundly evil to miseducate. Christianity creates drones by child abuse and smoking weed in youth.

If you have problems, society prefers to attribute them to you rather than collective error; they are responsibility and rebuke resistant.

People take jealous pleasure in seeing your potential handicapped, out of the relative fallacy that shining your light dims theirs.

...

Never give up. You feel something wrong in your soul, likely wrong, correct it. Trust LORD over self.

Intelligence is malleable not a precise number. People have genetic proclivities, natural gifts. Our lives are measured by results which stem from persistence and positive attitude beyond intellect.

Character is destiny, and character is developed and refined.

You miss 100% of the shots you don't take.

You don't know until you try.

Failure is an incident not a syndrome, it can be corrected.

Miseducation and spiritual corruption necessitate self aware introspection.

Don't let anyone tell you you can't do something. You can do anything you set your mind to. Almost.

The point is you don't know where your mental limits are, if any.

We constrain ourselves through false beliefs, becoming prisoners of our own minds. Intelligent people learn too quickly, accept failure too readily, and attribute it to their capability versus their attempt, attitude, and effort.

The truth will set you free.

You want your skin on the line.

God's law vs man's. Silence is complicity in sins against the LORD and will bring God's wrath on everyone. War suspends law not humanity.

Preference for maintaining faith via blood, but Judaism is not mystically passed on maternally, a free ticket and idolatrous fetish of the womb.

E.g. Manasseh, Ephraim, Jesse, etc.

Circumcision covenant with LORD, not the Jewish people.

Blood is blood, and faith is faith.

Karaite Judaism is patriarchal with Biblical adherence, rabbis are scholars not prophets.

Philosophy 101 underlies wars.

The sincerest flattery is imitation.

Universalisation and proselytizing are carcinogens.

e.g.'s: Defending democracy in my backyard, Russia is far too small.

[Guinness ... Guan Yin, Ginni

Gauss lives across street]

"world historical record for torture":

HARCOURT DETROIT FREDRIC SORROW

...

circulariser foretold horror

circulariser whore drool

"Carl Friedrich Gauss":

circulariser gash [... ring a bell?]

"Arjun Jaganathan Satyamoorthy":

nonstatutory [RAPE] maharajah

Maharashtra [Mumbai] annatto

tyrannosaur Mahayana/Gotham/(math agony)

annotator hamstrung/maharajah/anagrams/Mahayana/Ramayana/Gautama/Saturn

GUANTANAMO [Guanyin G, Bay ... Bayesian] sanatory/Thanatos

[death; "Death I am become, destroyer of worlds" (Gita 11:32)]

GASTRONOMY ARJUNA

Manhattan Argonaut

orangutan [Kong] maharajah/Thanatos/ashtray/Aaron/Roman

...

SATAN RAMANUJAN /MARYANNA

NATHAN ARTHROSTOMY [surgical opening into joint ... WEED] /gnathostoma [parasitic worm]

Nathan Utahan gyrator/orgasm [spirit sabotaging Alexander]

Gautama Jason John

Gautama (Torah)^2 Nanny/Jay
Gautama Torah tyranny

People reflect what you project.
Chaos is a ladder.

Game of Thrones (GOT):

Leaf creates Night King
[Eve and Apple]
Octavia Alexandru (Season 4)
Kae Alexander (Season 6)

[NATHANIEL, "wake the dragon"]
"Viserys Targaryen":
VISE ARRANGES
SERVANT GRAYS
gayness irate
gay vainest
Artin greaser/serves

"Viserys Targaryen Dragon":
EASTER ARRANGING
retrogressing Rand
Natan aggressive/adviser/advisory

"Joffrey Baratheon":
BETRAYER JOHN
FATHER OBERON
beta honorary

"Ramsay Bolton":
ABSALOM
Salomon Rab

"Daenerys Targaryen":
Easterner angry [Esther, G]
tyranny eagerer

"Eddard Stark": trader dad [LORD]

"Brandon Stark":
DAKOTAN
Satan Bond
Ko bastard/brand

...
Hodor "Hold the Door", Odor

[and Shae J, face axed monster]

"Tyrion Lannister":
ARISTOTLE
Trinity ensnarl/Roseann

[Snaked disobedience, Reek ... Erik]

"Theon Greyjoy":
Joey hornet/theory/throne/Tyreon/ergot/honey/horny/hero
Nero Goth

[Bastard means LORD's younger]
"Jon Snow Aegon Targaryen":
George sanatory/sayonara/Rosanna/Trojans/wanton
wrong oestrogen/estrogen/negator/Roseanna/Tennyson/eastern/regent/Agosto
AGOSTO AARON (88) Gwenny
Gwynne/Genny/Jewry/Jenny
Agosto orange/wagerer/wronger/renown
REGENT AARON/GANJA
gangrene Rosanna
Newton gorgon
Ann Jay newsagent
Wagoner Jay negator/treason

[Kingslayer, Tyrion's brother]
"Jamie Lannister":
Jamesian litre
James Latiner

"Night King": HIN TING

[Red Witch]
"Melisandre":
Emeralds
AENEID MRS [XY]

[Retard stinks, reek ... Erica]
"Erica is like a fungus":
(sugarcane filius)/(cleanses augur)

Pardon a fool.

Self-immolation puts a fire under your ass. (Job motivation)

"Even those who have occasion for a lamp supply it with oil." (Plutarch: Pericles)

Dandelions exacerbate cracks.

[Erica Standhart, Seven of Nine,
Attempted erotic assimilation.
Georgia Travis, Geordi La Forge,
Attempted erotic vising ... visor.]

"America is the Borg":
MATRIARCHIES
marriage bitch
Creator Isiah/Sheba/Shae
armchair beet/Bose/bees/bets/set
Beta heroic/Homeric
research atom/goat
Cao British/eight
Moishe arbitrage/Arabic

Adam compelled overreach apple, disobedience. Result is G automatic demotion, Adam limbo. Apple J rotting; must obey and eat.

...
Snake envenomed since Adam and Eve, the Lilly of the valley.

The Las Vegas Needle
Dependence on emotion is addiction.
Masculine examples include exhilarating challenges e.g. fighting, hunting, pressure, gambling.
(Cocaine, Adrenalin, Heroin ... heroism)
Feminine examples include sensuality, orgasm, love, drama, music, suckling, pointless charity.
(Serotonin, endorphins, bass)

A half truth is a whole lie.
E.g. "New Testament", Koran

Strength is self control, wisdom is knowing when. E g. Mercy from the vengeful or justice from the timid.

Heaven and hell are on earth.

Big men small things.

Jack Kevorkian the prophet, people have a right to die.
<https://www.bidoun.org/articles/a-very-still-life>

Artwork:
1. Man in cracked rainbow egg praying, puppeteered by bunny rabbits with crosses to have a halo.
2. Achilles possessing a man to self-decapitate, has apple in mouth.
3. Santa stopping baby Jesus.
4. Blond Buddha decapitated by Lenin, motive force behind WWI, WWII, and Jesus ben Joseph, who frames him.

LORD curses those he despises with madness. LORD blesses those he loves with prophesy.

[Oy Vey!]

Hebrew faith becomes second temple Judaism in Ezra, Nehemiah.
Harder, ALL foreigners excluded, ALL mixed marriages forbidden.
Ironically, modern Jewish is Hebrew mixed with Eastern European.

[Catholic, pussy cat]

"Christianity is feminisation":
antichrist insanities

[Discovered at precisely 3:33 PM in the bathroom]

"God is like a shadow in the back of the mind":
denicotinise shithead (333) Oklahoma/lambda

[Bird's eye]

LORD likes listening to prayers, He records them in the Bible. He also records conversations from a bird's eye perspective.

Circumcision circumscribes people, rings are symbolic of a covenant, and there is no foreskin rejuvenation therapy.
(Lebedovych is working on that.)

[Job's rebellion]

Job, Biblically Japanese, has a strong sense of duty, honor, and pride, stunted sense of humor.
LORD and Satan busted on Job, so he swore eternal vengeance.

Freewill is limited. The LORD causes things to be.

Satan the Adversary, Diabolo the Slanderer. Ancient Greek διαβάλλω (diabállō, "to slander", literally "to throw across"). M and K.

"Satan the Adversary, Diabolo the Slanderer":
levelheadedness arbitrator/birthday
restorativeness hardheartedly/dethroned

"American Christian Diabolists":

decriminalisation archaist/catharsis
CHARACTERISATION ALBINISM
discrimination caesarist/Hebraist/Alastair
NONMATERIALISTIC ISIAIAH
remilitarisation Cain/China/Diana/Dinah
SENSATIONALISTIC ARMCHAIR
incarceration dismissal/hasidism/lambda
mercantilistic Obadiah
mineralisation archaistic/catharsis/diarist/Triassic
radicalisation cretinism/criminals
scandalisation arbiter/Hebraist
TRINITARIANISM ABOLISHES
...
ADAMANTINE SCHOLASTIC/CHARBROILS/CLASSICIST/HISTORICAL
charlatan misdirection/dominatrices/missionaries/romanticised

Humor a retard.

[LUNACY]

Paradoxical that the greatest enemies of the God of Israel had their greatest success as Hebrews.

G ... Jesus,

J ... Anne Frank yearning for Job,

K ... Einstein,

N ... Grothendieck,

Y ... Feynman

[Anti-Marcus]

Groundhog day, women sense the realization of best you. Soul senses potential, should feel discontent at settling in life. People sense their mistakes, but lie to themselves to buffer self esteem.
Intuition points to success, whereas logic is blind.

Logic impedes intuition.

Renaissance is rebirth, metaphor for return of antiquity.

Youth is insolent.

(E.g. J ... Japan is young, N ... Richardson, USA ... Demo-baby)

Humanities study human patterns, science studies divine patterns.

Assuming integrity of Tanakh, cluster of miracles around Elijah parallel those alleged of Jesus.

Universalisation is nonsense.

Most people do not want an agreement with the LORD, who will destroy you for disobedience.

[American Idol]

American democracy primed for close elections. If one party were substantially larger, they could kamikaze the other in primaries. Structure pushes popularity toward being neck to neck. Eliminating general primary prevents this possible strategic bias and focuses on opinion poll. Structure discourages consensus, promotes polarization, adversity.

[IDOLATRY]

Point of interest: consider the recent case of 30 North Koreans executed for smuggling K-dramas. Seems tyrannical by Western standards, a violation of liberty, yet the Biblical punishment for idolatry is death. Possession vs worship?

Biblically destruction is appropriate, execution for worship only.

Legally smugglers deserve death.

Idols: Alexander received 20 years for MIT, misbranded for Georgia.

Occident (West) vs Orient (East). Cradle of civilization is Mesopotamia near Mediterranean, West unmatched in depth.

Seen in reincarnation frequency, and in choice of Canaan Israel.

Adam and Eve, LORD said He would create strife between men and women, echoed in BCE vs CE. Torah is penned by Behemoth, Phaeton Testament by Leviathan.

Book of Enoch about spiritual sabotage, then corruption of mankind, then Noah's ark.

Pattern of spiritual sabotage:

1. Adam and Eve (G)
2. Abraham and Hagar (N)
3. Samson and Delilah (N)
4. David and Bathsheba (Michael)
5. Solomon and 700 women (N)
6. Jesus the false Messiah (N)
7. Vladimir impaling (Michael)

Pattern of murder:

1. Julius Caesar (N)
2. Marcus Aurelius (N)

A word to the wise suffices.

Euthanasia is acceptable.

Masculinity and femininity are earned. They are disjoint, though an individual can have elements of both.

Seeding psychological technique. Children should consume quality.

E.g. video games

FF7 - MIT (Emerald Weapon is Leviathan, Chronicler course #'s), FF8 - Caltech

Rankings can be skewed.

For example MIT and Harvard are highly mis-ranked to entrap Alexander, whereas Caltech and Oxford rule.

"Massachusetts Institute of Technology":

Themistocles Cato astonishes

Themistocles Augustness Octant/China/Hanoi

UNENTHUSIASTICAL ECOSYSTEM

"California Institute of Technology":

Lenin Catholicisation forego/forget

Lenin Christianity flatfoot/cattle/cutoff

"Oxford University": rounder visit

The "New Testament", in particular "Revelation", is a sanctioned snare.

Good thoughts, words, deeds. LORD rewards faith itself, wholeheartedly.

Fear is an instinct inhibiting action meant to protect value: life, safety.

In practice it is the most insidious and powerful weapon of mind control because of its primality.

Need courage and honesty to overcome, e.g. be true to soul in work and love, fear of success and mating. The most common obstacle is the dog training of man, a prison for your mind, not God's Commandments which save.

Why child abuse is the one crime deserving a life sentence.

Nathaniel's hit list includes Samson and Solomon (Israel), Caesar and Aurelius (Rome), and the Romanovs (Russia). Anti-Alexander, Catholic (Cathay or China), Communist, Athenian in that order. The ruin of nations and war is no obstacle. And were I to bring world peace, he would still want my soul. Next target is the USA via the degradation of law in Trump, potentially to imprison Alexander.

Women are more metaphorical, men are more literal.

Psychological tragedy. Of course Yahweh annoyed, of course universal disdain for a Servant. Fault lies with people not God.

Condensation: set a rate.

Meeting quota vs allowing tasks or sleep to expand.

Inclination is like handedness.

The path of the loser is paved with excuses and self pity.

Jacob Israel wrestling with angel analogous to Israel nation wrestling with its neighbors with its faith.

Tanakh has one coherent narrator throughout. Why four fragmented versions: Matthew, Mark, Luke, John? Because it is a fraud.

Digitality creates structure.

Relativity creates chaos.

K, Lord of Cao, death the destroyer.

Supreme Court ruled presidents be treated as divinity; Biden should round them up to kowtow.

Honor from the dishonorable has no value, like the cheering of a crowd at WrestleMania.

Same sex union not marriage is condoned by David and Jonathan, echoed by musicality. There are human gender norms, adoption should respect them.

You could be raised by Amazons like Alexander.

[CONSORTS]

Consorts for the wrong reasons reflect greed. Women should not be a burden, but they are raised to squabble to emasculate men, pushing for ideal equivalence.

Monogamy won't cure rottenness, and polygamy won't corrupt virtue. Imagine someone saved from abandonment creating chaos in a family in gratitude, e.g. Leah.

The Torah honors not condemns Israel and Leah, Judah and Tamar, and Ruth and Boaz.

Moral relativity favors relatives.

The LORD is omniscient; thus He values righteousness in people whereas people idolise intelligence in themselves.

Challengers' overall strategy is to humanise Alexander which is debasement. Alexander overall strategy is to elevate humanity though righteous instruction.

Caste elevation is more difficult than debasement, and you cannot change someone's soul. Inter-marriage destroys families.

Pleasures of the flesh are base.

Alkaline is the antithesis of acidic.

Christianity is the antithesis of Hebraism, nullifying its central tenants out of collective jealousy, beating good people down.

Why not follow a good example, why try to rewrite the Book? Pride.

Women already carry guns. Biblical Queen Esther is a good example.

The world is laced with divine humor. The LORD verifies His covenant by exalting Israel.

Israel owes its existence to the Torah, its allegiance to the LORD, all its problems arising from Biblical disobedience.

A secular identity is anathema; conquered minorities who are not slain become labor with the opportunity to convert.

Corollary is that in a secular country, state sponsorship of religion is forbidden, including the Ten Commandments.

No lapping blood: bloodthirst is forbidden.

[ORIENTAL WEEDS]

Duty and respect alone are insidious Oriental idols. Manufactured obligations and moderation toward anathema.

A duty to respect the lives and dignity of weeds in your garden.

Unobtrusiveness is cowardliness, in essence mutual enablement of vices. Silence is consent of rape.

Georgia is horny as a rabbit, devilish, a siren vices, squirt is a discharge.

A succubus Erica also vices.

Rebellious souls become demons.

[GOVERNANCE - bottom up]

LORD favors rule of law preserving rights of individuals, permits robust diversity of governance structures.

LORD favors self appointed judges and officers.

Individual rule singularly vulnerable, yet potential to do tremendous good. Best to preserve capacity, empower as needed in proportion to competence.

Military, moral, philosophical needs and competence hard to recognize, also problems hard to correct by resisting a majority, evidence that the LORD elevates individuals.

Recognize need by spotting cracks, i.e. contradictions and injustices.

Recognize competence by success.

Brainwashing, emotionalism, trained dependence, and ideals are psychological vices misemployed by all forms of government.

Trust childhood intuition and common sense rooted in the soul, as even logic can mislead.

The best defenses are virtue: truth, integrity, education, humanity.

History illustrates that beating is beta and creating alpha.

Limited logical capacity to innovate in government. Ideas are more powerful than people.

Nathaniel intense irrational hatred of Torah.

[Secular logic]

People have a right to their bodies and lives thus none to others'.

Both parents have custodial rights to unborn fetuses.

Lot offers his daughters to be gang raped, so they in turn rape him, producing Moab and Benammi, enemies of Israel.

In rape and incest, children are not accountable for parents' sin, but they inherit their troubles.

Evil is easy.

Insanity is defined by unhealthy mental deviation from the average.

Genius is defined by mentally exceeding the average.

Not necessarily correlated.

[IGNORAMUSES]

Roman dictators were elected for a period when survival of the state was in jeopardy, e.g. Civil War.

The American euphemism is martial law, the weaker version executive order. (E.g. Trump is unfit, circumstance inappropriate.)

War suspends law not ethics.

Birds are dinosaurs.

Levi's blue jeans have tassels.

Beards give majesty.

In work and life, trusting your soul leads to greatness. Yet competence and appreciation can be developed in any sphere by patient persistence toward a goal.

[IDOLS]

All men are not created equal, equal, or brothers, but deserve equal justice and opportunity in most spheres.

Preserving individual liberty is fundamental, the corollary national. Yet liberty alone becomes vice. Idols are double edged swords, both powerful encouraging ideals and sacred pillars, people turn violent if you touch them.

Shepherds are for sheep, taking the guise of idols.

Education empowers, enabling innovation and growth, fundamentally beginning with truth in the mind. Yet without religion and ethics it is a soulless machine.

Favor lighthouse over lash, respecting choice and its spirit.

The world is asymmetric, imperfectly perfect.

Worshipping life is idolatry, respecting life is religious duty.

...

There is no liberty from the LORD or His laws, desiring such is folly.

One man's innocent blood carries an eternal curse, David and Uriah.

David educates on equality. Absalom educates on democracy,

Solomon and Nathan on autocracy.

David and Goliath is an example to inspire, not limited to archangels.

Biblical law highly values female virginity because of attachment. Disincentive for copulation, incentive toward earlier marriage in prime childbearing years.

Strong incentive for men to mature young; the early bird gets the worm.

Women naturally manipulate, why the LORD put men in charge.

See Adam and Eve.

Genitalia resemble snakes and octopi.

Obedience over sacrifice. All things are the LORD'S, and He causes things to be. The most you can give is the choice allotted you.

Saul instructs that is often easier to give up your life than your pride.

Can tradition be possessed? (Nathan says yes.) The living are caretakers.

Can the collective change divine law and judgement? No, see Moses and Aaron, Absalom and David.

Salamanders inhabit palaces, thus teaching empathy, humility, and service are key. Cold blooded warm hearted is best.

Unearned and unchecked power easily becomes vice, beauty exemplary in women.

One penis cannot simultaneously inhabit two vaginas. Rational purpose for polygamy is necessity or love; greed, vanity, and pleasure are vices.

Marriage is a sacred contract, not ROMANTic mutual unbreakable possession.

Culturally neither education nor the military are esteemed in the United States, rather industrial moneymaking.

CHRISTIANITY

Christianity is feminisation and homogenisation, an attempt at repealing the Torah using ideals.

It annuls: the Law ... hence women's rights and antislavery ethos, beards, hats, hygiene of hand washing and bathing, kosher food, circumcision, plurality, rational education, and proportional sentencing ... hence the death penalty in lieu of lifetime confinement.

Why the heros lived in antiquity, followed by the dark ages. Why heavily Christianized men act gay, failing to satisfy Christian women.

THE GENDER WARS

Different physical standards for men and women. Value of a man measured more by competition women by childbearing. Women are attracted to dominant men, but not vice versa. Also women are more likely to be bisexual, men polarized either straight or gay.

Why mild plurality is no insult to the dignity of a woman, yet for a man it is a complete disgrace.

No male beauty contests in Israel.

Profeminists hate asymmetry hence unborn children.

The patriarchs and David were righteous, Solomon excessive.

Biblical Judaism does not need revision, it has become legally matriarchal, how insidious !

Bitter women preemptively emasculate innocent men as if the genders were at war, domineering in a misguided attempt at dominance.

Masculinity is characterized by emotional stability and rationality, not machismo or pollination.

Dating is like locusts crawling.
Sex carries a toll.

Responsibility for the Holocaust lies with Lenin, echoed in the kibbutz. Weeds penetrate crevices and dull the mind.

Promise of creating a nation Israel necessitates reproduction. Model of one man thirteen children is nonstandard, consorts handicap in most circumstances. Similar to Islamic acute shortage of men due to war.

Surface attraction common, search for deeper connection. Corollary is fear to speak to someone is absurd.

Royals and aristocrats are behaviorally and genetically filtered over millennia. People who have managed to subdue an entire population are nontrivial, even chosen by the LORD as David. Antithetical to athenianism and coarsely handled by its system both by structure and intent. Yet nurture is even more powerful than nature, so there is hope for all.

American athenianism (... atheism) is financially shear masses while maintaining illusion of choice hence complacency. Genius mind control. When facing ruin, why must elections be adversarial? Why not a no contest joint ticket? Effective plutocracy where Nathaniel runs the show. Ruled by blind hatred, he would do anything to hurt Alexander, even betray his democratic ideals via Chinese Catholic allegiance.

No surer way to handicap someone than by miseducation in youth. Truth liberates.

Sarah should have born the consequences of her decision and cooperated with consort Hagar, children are a profound blessing not garbage for the wilderness. Discarding offspring is no solution, does not discharge responsibility or consequences. Look at Israel now, needlessly at war with Arabs. Ishmael has been loyal and righteous.

Law on Marriage:
One man one wife.
Inheritance primacy with wife.
Consorts not ideal, limit two with wife's consent.

...
Biblically, best offspring are from monogamous true love. Polygamy splinters families, in excess becomes vice, gluttony and vanity.
Yet motive for consorts can be physical need, e.g. children and companionship, or more rarely love, peace, and righteousness.
Consorts: splinter families, constrain men physically and legally, power dynamic shifts toward women and children, potential child support and alimony, usually unattractive logistically, endanger emotional intimacy, highly stigmatic with prejudice against intent, alternative to divorce severance. In practice modern examples of consorts are mistresses and the "ex ... X", the ex being only acceptable post marital, whereas "consort" is retrograded and more general.

...
X ideals create gender X and marital exes. Exes as if the relationship and responsibility is dead which it is often not.
Consider Abraham and Ishmael.

...
Consorts may be a Godsend in places with declining populations like Japan and Korea, as gender norms are asymmetric and the physical labor involved in childbearing is heavier for women.
Useful when shortage of men.
Mormonism produces offspring.

Chinese love gambling. Macao, lucky eight.

Light and dark define each other. Plebeian vs Aristocrat.
Jesus serves a deep purpose.

Rushing ahead you do not get far. Tortoise and the hare.

Trump's ethics are poor, but factually he is innocent of insurrection by a sliver, guilty of inciting to riot and tax fraud.
Politics is no cause for prejudice on bond lending or legal defense; however, BIDEN has my vote.

[INCITING RIOT,
just short of insurrection]

TRUMP'S SPEECH

Right and wrong versus establishment of guilt versus severity of crime.

Right and wrong are digital, a vote by a standard measures guilt.
Can a state singlehandedly keep president off ballot? Severity.

If you rape one person you are a rapist, does not matter the others who consented. You murder one person you are a murderer. You betray one state you are a traitor. Yes, but not necessarily to the nation. Notably betrayal ranks less than murder, also less definite as dealing with abstractions.

...
You commit one felony you are a felon and can be excluded from the ballot for moral turpitude.

Trump assembled crowd hence is their leader, wrongly incited to riot.
Leaders bear some responsibility for followers' actions.
Freedom of speech does not apply for elected officials as they represent others hence are responsible to them. Cannot lie or mislead, betraying public trust.

Value integrity over skill in top positions, because principles establish foundations whereas skill fades. Tortoise and the hare.
Consider Solomon.

Music in excess is a vice, though inspiring in small doses. Likewise with sexuality.

Trade based on principles, should align with patterns and probability.

"Adam Enoch Abraham Joseph":
Ahab comprehends

Strategy to kill God: bleed virtue while teaching vice.
Character progression incongruity:
Adam, Enoch, Abraham, Joseph all exemplary. Then Samson, Solomon, Judas fools. Vices bind.

Tactic to destroy Alexander:
layered probability.
1. Ignore Bible
2. Idolize marriage and trinity
3. Emasculation
4. Abusive ignorance
5. Depressive climate
6. Sabotage family
7. Poison Hebrew faith
8. Isolation and torture

TRUST YOUR INTUITION. If you sense something is wrong, it is wrong. Not difficult to make major life decisions correctly, in fact very easy, agonizing leads to error.

Ideal life can be become an idol: rather, it is a blessing to realise and correct your mistakes.

Inflection "turning" points in life: religion, education, marriage.
Alexander got 25 years for two wrong turns, prom and college.

Equal work merits equal pay, yet on average expect women to make less money because of innate gender differences, men providing and women nurturing.

Fit in work and marriage should be natural, you should gravitate toward, not struggle against the current. Commitment and consistency creating success, "hard work" should become daily joy.
Beware addiction to struggle or pain as a false proxy of progress, life should become smooth.

In our souls we sense our mistakes, confirmation is not necessary. Redemption begins by recognizing and admitting mistakes.
Most people identify with their thinking, defending falsehood. Most people want to see you fail, it cheers them with respect to their own mediocre lives. Most people get convinced they are stupid. Losers drag others down, winners help people up.

...
Interestingly declining Ko's challenge is worse than cowering before Caltech and J because there is no excuse.

Challenging the strong has substance, challenging the weak is worse than nothing, for by hiding you self limit, becoming as your associates. Helping the poor is noble, picking on the defenseless despicable.

Like James Ko plotting child abuse and family betrayal.

The architect of Xtianity is not Ko but rather Nathan and Georgia. Nathan is the nemesis by design, Georgia betrayed the man to whom she owes everything, like Absalom.

COVENANT

All men are equal as lives, they do not equally keep the covenant.
Is not the ethnic hurdle deliberate to test men as Abraham was tested?
Is not the persecution Israel striving with the nations, exemplified?
You reap what you sow, easy come easy go.

Observe how yeast multiplies (x, .), negated by division (/), line).
Observe how Catholicism was historically banned in Cathay its point of origin, observe how China exports junk.
Learn virtue by studying vice, inching toward the source by truth.
Religion is divine instruction in virtue, imitation falls short.
Virtue speaks for itself.
Force necessary when reason collapses, as advertisements are necessary when products are poor.

If the LORD saves the righteous, why do Xtian saints die hideously? Halo thermonuclear glow.

ON WOMEN - HONESTY

Healthy to feel uncomfortable approaching strangers with dubious intent, called having a conscience.
Discomfort disappears with honesty and positive intent: stick to entertainment mindset to develop social skills. People radiate intent.
At worst hire a prostitute and save time and complications, like drama, disease, abortion, and bastards.
James Bond lives on screen... mentality "I could but I won't."
Sexuality is sacred, cheapened in modern world, pollination idolised by both men and women.
Pollination and gambling exalt skill as opposed to substance.
People are not interchangeable parts on an assembly line, souls are special and irreplaceable.
Rejection akin to physical pain, fear of it cowardice, yet regret is a nail in your coffin.
Cowards die every day looking in the mirror, the brave once.
If women treat you with discourtesy and disrespect, it reflects on them.
Onus and responsibility is on men, why women are renamed.
Woman's physical attraction proportional to her esteem of you, status for women and beauty for men being equally superficial.
Pornography is junk food.

TRIBALNESS

Humans are tribal, no excuses, no apologies. Inter-marriage weighs genetics against culture, the latter typically dominating. Why Ruth is special.

...
Xtianity has been trying for two millennia to demonise and destroy the Hebrew tribes to create its own.

PSYCHOLOGY OF EDUCATION

Worst disservice is lying to people.
e.g. telling children they are special when their results are mediocre, leading to entitled college degrees for everyone versus trade school, or convincing geniuses they are stupid by jealous sabotage or incorrect feedback, e.g. learning too quickly through failure versus persisting.
The brutal feedback of securities trading kindly prevents languishing, likewise Caltech is supposed to mercifully weed out nonacademics not cater to published averages. Poor results are not permanent, measurements do not perfectly gauge your intellect or ability, but also reflect your effort, attitude, and circumstances.

You cannot do anything you set your mind to, but you can TRY, and you do not know where your mental limits are, or if they even exist, or to what extent the mind can master the flesh, like in Buddhism.
Best to bravely jump in deep end or ring, necessitating focus on goal, forcibly shifting attention away from petty psychology. Analogously true in business, focusing on goals versus securities pays dividends, e.g. Musk, Buffett.

Trying and failing is preferable to regret, for why not try again? Persistence leads to excellence, persistence is attractive.

Michael Jordan: "Miss 100% of unattempted shots."
Key is to give 100% in each attempt.

Success is never permanent, failure not fatal, persistence wins. The righteous man falls and gets up over and over again. Israel had his wages changed ten times! You are only a failure if you accept failure, you are only a fool if you give up.

X-Tianity

Good in bad is dirty, looking for the silver lining in an atomic blast, like mass distributed Bibles no one bothers to actually read carefully because critical thought was not encouraged in the Dark Ages. Easier to destroy than to create.

ISRAEL

Hebrew faith is of the Creator, with precedence to write holy law, hence it is real. Primal. Neither intended for nor beholden to mass market, only to LORD. Literally God's people, with an open door.

...

The real lesson of Jacob Israel is persistence after love. After twenty one years of labor, having wages changed ten times, he finally got what he wanted. Similar lesson of the promised land of Canaan Israel.

US Immigration - Federal Overreach

Freedom of movement of legals once within border, therefore immigration administration federal. However illegals do not have right to freedom of movement, therefore border security need not be federal. Asylum is federal, burden necessarily distributed evenly throughout states by possibly restricting movement (to Martha's vineyard). If burden not distributed, federal asylum invalid by inequity. Practically immigration is a local problem (TX, Southwest), majority unaffected initially. Individual need not bow to mob, States should not be handicapped (Abbott metaphor) by Congress, for then what benefit in Statehood?

The LORD despised the generation of Sinai, so He led them in circles in the desert for forty years and spoon fed them manna and quail.

Xtianity borrows the notion of trained dependence through the yeasty Eucharist, likewise through the "penalty" of Excommunication.

Empowering rivals spurs excellence, consider Abraham Lincoln, considered the finest. Having a nemesis corrects errors.

Smiles bury grief.

Attribute guilt precisely, recognising emotions are coarse, unlike Simeon and Levi in Genesis. Every man's sin is his own; countries inherit the fallout of those of sovereigns and governments, but not guilt. No communal guilt without communal action. [Hamis militants deserve death, Hamas voters deserve misery not death, which I find appalling.]

In my case I suspect the LORD wants my skin on the line, similarly to Nebuchadnezzar humbled. Likewise I suspect He promotes a battle arena to foster excellence, recognizing the good in bad.

Joseph Stalin's artificial famines prompting the Holocaust.

We see consorts in Genesis, especially of Israel, the hidden point being to multiply into a nation.

"A good enemy is your best friend."

Interesting, Nathaniel of all the archangels honors me most highly by constantly trying to destroy me while others spit and gaslight. I suppose he is doing his job.

Algebraic Ideals ... K-Theory
(unholy trinity, HQ in NYC)
Freedom - in excess New Jersey
Love - in excess Meatloafian
Democracy - unchecked is the Mob

To be able to cheat someone is not possible, actions sum to worth, because the LORD is the judge.

BURNING MAN psychedelic festival in NEVADA's Black Rock desert.

On Mercy

"Sticks and stones can break my bones but words can never hurt me." Nonsense, directly contrary to Biblical narrative, curses feared and blessings regarded. Divine model instructing human behavior toward good thoughts, words, and deeds.

Injury heals but pride does not, as forgiveness requires effort and nobility of soul, yet interestingly not understanding.

If people had understanding, or at least recognized their ignorance, they would be quicker to forgive. The wise know they know nothing.

Mercy with understanding is equally virtuous but less laudable than without, analogous to why the struggle of humanity elevates.

"God is merciful" reflects the LORD'S omniscience and holiness.

Most hatred flows from ignorance, revenge the hobby of the small, properly belonging to the LORD.

We see in the Book of Job the real test is not of Job but of the LORD, who's plan is to elevate poor Job, the counterplot to dethrone God.

Perhaps afterward Job became vassal of Antichrist Nathan, making further appearances as Jonah defying the LORD, Delilah slaying Samson, Sheba diluting Israel, Pilate washing his hands, and Anne Frank the lovable victimised heretic.

...
"People don't change," at least according to M, the smartest angel.

Consider K and L.

Lot instigates against Abraham, Abraham later sparing Lot's life in Sodom and rescuing him and his family. Judah tosses brother Joseph into a pit and sells him into slavery, Joseph later saving Judah and family from starvation.

Consider the CATiline conspiracy against Caesar where Octavio's allies assassinate Caesar, Caesar willing his fortune to Octavio and the Roman people.

Presently Alexander is a "monster" for surviving a lifetime of indirect persecution by James, including instigating Oct.8, Alexander's reward for having helped China, followed by sparing James's life.

...
Travis tortures Alexander to world historical record, Alexander spares her pathetic life at NYC. Travis instigates the brand, Israel complicit, Alexander helps Israel avoid implosion by suicide and enslavement by Georgia. Americans torture Alexander to death, Alexander spares NYC, headquarters of nemesis N, who thanks him by sabotaging surgery.

Lesson of David is warfare does not annul being good to others.

***Believe in Yourself.

"Faith in probability is the death of God.":
indefeasibility footpath/highroad/Horatio/OBADIAH/Pharaoh

...
And so not taking a "bet" reflects fear of probability and lack of faith in Oneself, a self annulment.

The shortcut to human greatness is the Bible; it's all been done.

Alexander History

Immaculate Conception Ukrainian Catholic Grade School.

Baba "Anna Flys": slay Ann F

"Alexander Luka Flis": Aeneid Ursula

Principal "Doris Jurek": Sire Ko

Fat bitch looks like Octopus Ursula from The Little Mermaid, purpose is to child abuse me into becoming a worm, too scared to even speak to Jordan, scared to learn, ashamed of reflection in mirror.

Octavian responsible.

"Georgia Nathan Achilles Ko":

Ashikaga challenger

[Practices exclusion, preaches universalism.]

[ON ROME]

Hannibal and Maharbal.

According to Livy, Maharbal strongly urged an immediate march on the city of Rome. Hannibal responded by saying "I commend your zeal, but I need time to weigh the plan which you propose." Maharbal then replied, "Assuredly, no one man has been blessed with all God's gifts. You, Hannibal, know how to gain a victory; you do not know how to use it." Latin: "Vincere scis, Hannibal; victoria uti nescis."

Was this not rather clemency, or even the LORD? Hannibal was not stupid, having done a lot of killing he would recognize a deathblow, life followed closely by Caesar.

Alexander had a chance to obliterate NYC, and despite strong distaste found it wrong, see Abraham and Sodom.

That the LORD was going to obliterate NYC does not mean he wanted it so, see Nineveh.

In war, weigh their lives and Isaiah versus potential World War III?

Alexander should have obeyed and not trimmed his beard, see Saul.

Prayer, unwitting disobedience.

Yet earning a crown implies prayer considered, for accidents merit no honor as manslaughter merit no death. Also subsequent opportunity for expiation.

[... Beto vs AO Cortez,
grass crown of Sulla,
tragically not worth Creator soul.]

Likewise consider, Caesar was known for celerity and clemency. Master Sun, "I have heard that in war haste can be folly, but have never seen delay that was wise."

[Cato=emotion+idealism+relativity]

ANTICATO

Caesar was right circumstantially:

there was no presidency, no elliptic oval office, rather squabbling and civil war.

Caesar was wrong legally: the Rubicon is not to be crossed, a parallel to Christian moral relativity.

Yet God's law is above man's, never to be broken.

Cato was wrong circumstantially:

recognizing the need for a military dictator in civil war and individual leadership in government, his personal hatred spurred him to not only legitimately support Pompey but also move to disenfranchise

Caesar and his legions, legally inciting civil war.

Cato was right legally but wrong ethically; no soldier, also no Roman, he weaponised the law to ensnare like a woman.

He was also motivated by illogical idealism, wishing for a less capable leader to mitigate structural damage, when a more capable leader is more enlightened.

Ideals must yield to survival, and empowering a fool solves nothing.

Naturally he disguised his actions as preservation, when in fact he preserved a state of civil war.

Rome did not benefit from Cato's Catiline conspiracy. There was a year of blight, a decade of civil war, every traitor's dagger was avenged, and Caesar was deified and burned on a pyre, even before the populace learned he willed a large fraction of his fortune to ordinary Roman citizens.

Cato has doubled down on evil.

Caesar was known for his clemency toward enemies and even Cato, who plotted misguided vengeance for his own needless suicide.

Caesar surrendered the dictatorship after eleven days, his later folly being that lifetime dictator was an egoistic ploy for assassination.

There is a different law for war and peace, but ethics remain the same.

Unrighteous judgement never endures for the LORD is real.

ANTICATHOLIC

Unspoken duty is idolatry.

Unannullable marriage is tyranny. Relative morality is criminal.

Universal religion is communist.

...

Faith without reason is blind.

Hope without action is lame.

Love without discipline is dumb.

Virtue in excess can become vice, e.g. the meatloafian love of Jesus.

Also virtue disobedient is vice, see Saul and Jonah.

Excellence is habitual amalgamation of virtue, the wisest being love and mercy.

Polygamy splinters families.

Less conducive to intimacy, nurture, quality but rather competition.

LORD'S law is one wife, consort acceptable in necessity, not ideal, best avoided.

[E.g. King Charles should have had a divorce. Israel had no choice, he was circumstantially connived, and Sarah was barren.]

Cowardice is worse than death, you lose your soul.

Far more difficult to create than to destroy. Nine months to a second. Many ways to die, one way to live.

Many ways to lie, one way to tell the truth. Easier to sin than be righteous, though both habituated.

Might is in temperance. Peaceful competition less urgent but much more challenging than war. Necessity created by lack of a safety net.

Aristotelian proof of ngrams

For any set of letters of size n , there is a distribution of constructible words, hence a word length k density. Intersect what is possible or $(n \text{ choose } k)$ binomial with what is valid in English. Longest lengths are least likely in both distributions, thus in the intersection. Thus if you iteratively remove longest words you get the least probable possibility, essentially Bayesian statistics, also the essence of trading.

Strive for excellence, but do not worship an ideal life, for what is not fatal can be remedied.

Perfect in imperfection, ideal free.

Often setting an impediment becomes a disguised gift, e.g. Stephen Hawking and Hellen Keller, patriarchy vs equivalence, Judaism vs world religions, and humanity vs superpowers. Likewise often gifts become an impediment by spoiling, e.g. wealth, telepathy, shape shifting. No surer way to ruin.

When is a gift not a gift?

Xmas entitles, Hanukah rewards not burning out.

Junk food and carbonated soda Coca Cola lack nutrition, they live next door to small kindnesses.
Hatred goads us to strive, that is its purpose, not to kill or maim.

The LORD hated Esau.

Pressure condenses diamonds.

Thank the LORD for adversity, likewise for the Adversary.

Reproof is kindness, embracing challenges elevates.

Fools grasp for control, the wise empower by education. Nothing is more damaging than a lie, a prison for the mind.

Gender equivalence is sterile.

Free will is illusory. The LORD causes things to be, either tipping the scales or explicitly making.

With failure, distaste, and folly, humans learn too quickly. Learn slowly.

Sin: atone, expiate, offering.

Liberty eludes definition.

MK: Raiden/Shao Khan and Sindel

KOF: Kyo Kusanagi (L), Iori Yagami (M), K

The Matrix:

NEOcortical NuEvO Testamento

Smith is good.

Motivate people using ideals and emotions.

Intelligence prevents problems before they occur, wars are best won without fighting.

In love and life, I have not seen benefit to suppression of true love. And when this rare quality is present obstacles are overcome.

Not balls or gut, as if not doing something goes against your soul.

LORD projects archangels, they are incomplete aspects of divinity. Roman/Korean (K, ... martial), Greek/Hellenist (G, H, ... drama),

Christian (N, ... sappy), Mohamadan (M, ... compromise), Japanese (J, ... refined).

Hebrew/Buddhist suffers from pollination, currency, and over logic, lacking soul, so it metamorphs into Jewish (J-wish).

The vices of excellence. (Sadly understandable given unprovoked harlot usurper wife. The D-ivorce.)

Take best from everyone.

One world order is the Tanakh, divine moral authority, digital logic.

Yet diversity of governments and religions is good, respect culture.

Love and trust can become idols.

Enjoy CHrIstMASs, made in CHINA with bubbly Koko Kola syrup.

The best revenge is success.

Freedom of speech vs threats?

Different forms of assault: verbal, physical, emotional, psychological.

Words can provoke physiological response, e.g. death threats.

A mob of people threatening to murder Jews can induce stress, terror, and relocation to safety.

An abrasive wife drips venom.

Gauge degree of aggressor responsibility vs target self control.

One parallel is Trump's liability over the Jan. 6 riots. Assembly is protected, riot is not, the distinction being physical violence.

Also intent versus attempt versus deed, were votes tampered?

Trump not morally pure but does some good. Should purify, mikvah.

Cultural references:

Disney's "The Sorcerer's Apprentice"

McDonald's "M" outposts

Time Flies (Father Time Flies)

Holy trinity as one family is an idol.

One of Jesus's jobs is to horrify. Opposites define each other. See the good in bad, e.g. Jezebel's raw sex appeal.

Submission versus obedience. Giving in versus willing choice. Best Servants think for themselves, who needs robots or drones?

Alexander relative King Richard II, wildly unpopular. Parallel of Richard Lord Rahl War Wizard in Sword of Truth books, also Confessor Kahlan. Credit N.

Alpha versus beta behavior. One child raised properly is worth 10,000 who are not. Pollination does not pay dividends.

Patriotism is a virtue, blind patriotism the vice of idolatry.

Scepticism and faith are both virtues.

Intelligent people evolve. Do not despise the LORD's reproof.

Democracy more robust against bad actors, yet any system is at best as good as its people. Vulnerability is mass brainwashing, where centralized power vulnerability is individual character.

Harder to change large group.

Council of vetted judges less vulnerable to populism or aristocracy, also not an individual.

LORD favored judges and prophets, yet promised to establish kingdom in perpetuity. What is kingdom?

Management amounts to babysitting and birdwatching.

Unearned authority corrupts, and mandatory succession is by definition unearned.

Titular kings can be vested with more authority as needed, and likewise stripped. Like dictators of old, of necessity and for a season, preferring gardening to war.

Closest modern analog is presidency where time is forcefully limited not voluntarily resigned.

Clinging to power beyond competence and need is evil.

No law not in the common interest ever lasts, force is futile.

Favor empowerment over control, education over war.

System structure necessary to prevent evil, then the structure becomes the evil.

Thought is the deepest motive, thus the most lasting achievements are religious and scientific not political.

Koshering (K) kills all filth

LORD: discharge euphoric.

Masturbation is lame but sometimes necessary, developing self control preferable. Anti-Talmud, anti-Monastic, humans are sexual beings.

Biblically, avoid foul images and do not covet your neighbor's wife.

Trinity site, Plutonium (Hades), "death I am become", death of God, Killer Einstein friends with Godel incompleteness logician... Alex born in El Paso near White Sands.

Sling an Einstein (one stone).

David liked men (Jonathan ... Nathan), hence Moses's blasphemy wrt the earth's biodiversity. Like Islam/X-tian universalisation folly.

Difference between virtue and vice often quantity and context.

E.g. Eros. Sex with wife is a virtue, vice is extramarital excess.

E.g. Hope without action is futile.

E.g. Love the wrong woman you die.

E.g. Faith in idols you burn.

E.g. Hate your weakness you excel.

Honor righteousness versus respecting competence.

Corollaries of Rights to Life and Liberty in a Secular State

Rationally humans have fundamental and inalienable rights to life and choice as far as these do not impinge on others' lives and choices. Corollaries include rights to privacy, one's body, LSD, suicide, and the prohibition of abortion and the death penalty.

In case of rape, life supercedes choice as children can be forsaken. In case of fatal delivery, prioritise higher probability of survival.

In case of dysfunctional disability e.g. Down's syndrome, can always choose suicide after birth.

Rationally and assuming right to kill, mother and father have equal claim to foetus thus both must agree.

The right to kill varies with religion. Circumstantial abortion, e.g. for rape and incest, is a religious right. Its implicit universalisation is directly contrary to a secular state. Many religions violate right to life and liberty. People have the right to their beliefs, yet practice must conform to secular morality.

Concluding, if you want an abortion you should travel one way to a country that either is non secular permitting circumstantial religious abortion or does not respect right to life.

Mosaic law is black and white, yet punishments immoderate, nonrelative, nongraded, mostly death. Question is to what degree did Moses supercede divine authority? He was banned from the promised land. Jesus was prophesied in minor capacity in Isaiah, perhaps king, yet teachings full of false prophesy: abolish the law, mercy for everything, worship serotonin. Digital morality gradated sentencing, punishments ought reflect crimes or be more merciful. Also death is a legitimate punishment, not to be celebrated except for the most vile.

COVENANT

The LORD does not belong to the Hebrews, nor does belief in the LORD, as light belongs to everyone. Conversion is not tribunal, but by circumcision and Biblical mandate. Jews cannot exclude honest individual believers they hate.

The Covenant is between man and God, not man and mob. Or woman.

LORD will perpetuate the covenant through chosen blood by oath, but covenant is not exclusive to blood, nor does blood assure it.

The Covenant is an agreement holding one to a bar. Actions elevate.

Blood purity worship is idolatry, with uniformly horrible results, yet it is often preferable to marry your own.

God created the world not man; woman attaches by nature, hence name.

Judgement: action, intent, and circumstance. Deliberate misalignment of action and intent with intent to cheat not humor is fraud.

Spirit vs letter of law. Distinction can be used as specious excuse to invalidate or bypass religious law. Humans are imperfect, spirit vs letter distinction has more significance for them than the LORD via prophesy. When letter is ambiguous, choose meaning over letter, i.e. how something is said and context.

K is HALO-genated. False X-tian saints.

PRIMALITY THEORY of permutations:

Garbage in, at best garbage out.

Start with primal patterns, also look for highly nonrandom results to identify phrase primality.

Human behavioral tendencies:

Blood is primary, ego is secondary.

EGO

Must you think as I think, do as I do?

Conquer by force, seduction, time.

Do not expect equanimity on top to be reciprocated when on bottom, expect reprisal and enslavement.

Fairness and debt are soon forgotten, as memory is insectlike and selective, man's span 100 years.

People remember grievances, and forget blessings that enable life.

The mob has no memory at all.

The righteous path is straight and narrow, thus it is far easier to destroy than to create. Higher glory belongs to women who nurture and men who heal, ie. to priests and scholars.

Women naturally turn men's necks and hoard all the glory, which is why men belong on top, so they can feel important in a world dominated by feminine virtue. The essence of masculinity is self control.

Christianity is cheaper. Of necessity some traditions are not as deep or old.

Everyone cannot be Abraham, it goes against Creation, the Gaussian curve.

Ego and idealism lead to jealousy and hatred, the dark side of the force, desiring the ruin of world diversity.

Psychologically, it is easier to worship an abstract than face an emanation.

If the LORD begat woman as the weaker but fairer gender it is upon men to help them. Georgia is the weakest link, thus the focus of enemies is to destroy her character, which they did quite successfully,

"worst person in history".

Religious tribal behavioralist not racist.

LORD founded tribe, blood rightly important to every nation on earth.

Yet LORD above blood (Abraham), maintains tribe by covenant, can choose to fall out (Jesus), and also can petition to join (Ruth).

Blood rightly given primacy, especially royal blood chosen by LORD (David). Yet foreigners not treated unfairly.

Blood should be given every opportunity to rejoin tribe and not treated as equal to foreigner (Moses).

Bygone virtue of LOYALTY made into a perjorative in the name of universality.

Given equal choice, better to choose your own (Samson). Yet kin is not above the Law (Solomon, Jezebel).

"The devil is in the details":

Eveline shithead.

Biblical treatment of foreigners kind, (partaking of Passover seder).

Living amongst people one typically adopts their ways. Max tithe of foreigners makes sense, as longtime inhabitants can be given religious choice to assimilate and leave tithe.

Regal Vetting:

Bible requires kings to handwrite copy of Torah, ... obviously not followed.

LORD values tent of David in perpetuity, yet power not in perpetuity to preempt incompetence before it filters itself on peoples' heads (shit). Fear of permanent loss of power religiously groundless.

Make practically groundless by maintaining strong family position.

Vetting:

1. Religion

(min handwrite Torah),

2. Depth

(min Doctoral),

3. Breadth

(min rank Kernel),

4. Flexibility

(min Trilingual)

5. Maturity

(min Age salted 40).

Law of covenanted flesh or of land?

Are foreigners subject to Mosaic law while in Israel?

What should separate secular law enshrine?

Degree of tolerance of religions after revelation?

Degree of tolerance of observance of Judaism?

The LAW is black and white, right and wrong. Yet we consider action, intent, and circumstance in judgement, as Moses in considering manslaughter. Relativity in sentencing:

lenience for youth and ignorance and exactitude for deliberate evil.

Socioethics:

No best human system, diversity prevents easy control.

Individual rights more primal than collective.

Blood endures philosophies change, which is why Torah revealed to tribe.

(K)iller the real Marshal.

What other way to kill God than to destroy digital morality by making everything relative via Christianity?

The LORD'S commandments are absolute, that is why Orthodox Jews wear black and white, as a reminder.

And to kill all the diverse and beautiful races and religions by making everything the same? X

How seductive are the idols of moral relativism and universal equivalence?

And how reminiscent of Einstein?

"God does not play dice."

Alexander brainy relatives:

Banach, Schrodinger, Thomson

HOLY JUDGEMENT

"Donbass Russian":

abrasion sun

abandon sir

assassin bond

dinosaur ass

UNORDAIN ASS

"Donbass Ukrainian":
dinosaurian bank
abrasion unkind
abandon Russia
dinosaur Kain
UNORDAIN KAIN

[Correct]
"Donbass disputed":
UNBAPTISED
autopsied DDs
disabused Don/son
dissuades bond
eastbound Sid
astounds spied/Sid
Budapest Odin/sins/sons/Sid
disbands despot/ousted/dupes/Deus
subpoena Sid
UNBIASED STOPS

"Crimea Russian":
America ruins
Caesar ruins/minus/Muir/urns
MESSIANIC (8)
massacre ruin
musician errs
amnesia sir
airiness Ram

"Crimea Ukrainian":
America Kain/ruin
rainmaker uncia/Cain
Karen cranium/maniac/caiman
Marianna ickier/icier/Eric
nickname Auria
Riemann auric

[Correct]
"Crimea disputed":
misdirected
miseducated rip
DIADEM PRIEST/PUREST/CRIST/TRUCE

[Correct, Biblical]
"Gaza Israeli":
glaziers (window glass)
regalia Isa
grail Isa
Ariel Isa
LIAR Sega/Sage
girls AAA
LEIA Grazia(fashion UK)/arias/ragas(Indian classical)/sizar(undergrad at Cambridge or Trinity, also
honest, fair)/airs/Risa/rags/rigs/sari/gas/Isa/sir
sire AAA

"Gaza Palestinian":
ALIENATING/Leninist/slanting
penalising AAA
nasalizing pet/tea
PALATINE GAINS
Italians pagan
NATANIEL PIG
paganise Aztlan
pleasing (44) Nazi
stapling Nazi
stealing Nazi
ANGEL PINATA/TAIPAN/SAINT

[Koko puff]
"Gaza disputed":

ADIEUS/STUPID
upstaged aid
studied
ADIDAS GETUP/PUTZ
ESAU DITZ/PAID
AGUSTE DIAD/PAID/DAD
suited (22)
Adept Gaius/Saudi
duped Asia
Zetas paid/Aug
Deus Data
Ides Data
Zeta Gaius/Saudi

[Correct]
"Taiwan Chinese":
Athenians Wei
Einstein
Nathan ices

"Taiwan disputed":
inaptitude sad
DISUNITED

"ugliest country in history":
righteous instruction
unrighteous clitoris/silicon/trinity
honourless trinity
constitution hurley
scientology untruth
eroticising unholy
nicotinise yoghurt
siring honeylocust
Ginnie Christ Lotto

"Faisal Siddiqui" (222):
filius aids/Sid
Qaddafi Isis
liquid
squalid
Saudi Iliad/fails

"Jordan Nosanchuk":
Noah's Ark

"Marianna Lukovna Flis":
Aaron Kaufman/villain
Saul oilman Frank
Sulla Roman avian/Finn

"Alexander Oleg Daniv":
David regal annex
Nevadan regal/Godel/Oiler

"Alexander Luka Daniv Flis":
David Saul Aaren Felix

"semen content of Colgate toothpaste":
Phaeton testament footstool

"The Talmud": mutated

[WEED - proof in Bible]
"Why was Solomon corrupted":
Octahedron Olympus

[MICHAEL - atypical of the most accomplished general of antiquity.
Transylvanian "Flys-tran".
Vlad's tranny granny likes porking up the fanny.]
"Why was Vladimir the Impaler":

whitehall adversary/vampirism

"When did Jordan become Nathaniel's vassal":
dandelion blameworthiness/treasonableness/charlatanism
dandelion charlatanism jawbones

[Why such an incompetent successor of a virtuous man?]
"Marcus Aurelius and Commodus":
murder salammoniac/calumnious/scandalous/succussion/acidulous/audacious
Mordred Cassius communal
demon commissar
diadem classroom

"worst person in history":
serotonin sophistry/worships

"worst life in history":
Flis noteworthy/worthiest/tortoise

"Most Valuable Player":

"Angel of Death":
halogenated (K), God El hate

"moral relativism": varietal, Travis

"Luck is the LORD"

The LORD of Hosts
The LORD the King

"Coolest prophet":
preschool, choose Potter

"Why is Satan a troublemaker?":
(K)ay blameworthiness
"

Satan and Michael":
adamantine, Canaanites, Canadians
Nathaniel scam, Nathan mislead

"Why is Travis so pathetic?":
ASTROPHYSICIST hate (Cocoa puff K)
psychiatrist votes/waves

"Is Ginny K's wife":
sensing, YESSING, Winnie, wifing
King Nisei/wises/wins

"Who incited Israel to evil?":
Octagon evilest

"Grandmaster": Dr. Eastman

"Truelove conquers all":
levarterenol (l-norepinephrine)

"Diamond Grandmaster":
ARMAGEDDON DISARM (333)
adamantine dorms/dog/God/Rod
emanation Mars
mastermind grandad/dragon
ringmaster Adam
TARDIGRADE MONAD
ordination Adam
tragedian ransom
AGAMEMNON TRIAD
anointed Adam
GODDAMN gordian/dragon/Nimrod/monad/RODIN

"Alexander and Faizal": Nazarene, Ferdinand

"A half truth is a whole lie":

Flesh HIAWATHA outlier/liter

Flesh authorial wealth

Alleluia fortieths/frothiest/hesitator/softheart/worthiest/theorist/wartish/whoreish/wraithes/airshow/
ATHEIST?/fairest/faithes/fathers/foresaw/hastier/stewart/threats/thwarts/tither/torahes/twister/wariest/
whitest/wreaths

ARISTOTLE wailful/lawful/wilful/Alfie/Allah/Elihi/halal/Lilah/whale/fail/flea/hell/Leah/life/wail/wife

"change is a constant":

"hasten slowly":

"God does not play dice":

apologetic, scientology

[Ko to Flis]

Richard Marx -

"Right Here Waiting for You":

Arthur wife Georgie/gorgon/throne

Arthur Thorin foggy

Georgia unworthier/inheritor/unthrifty/fortieth/inferior/hornier/trinity

Georgia Trinity whore

"Richard Marx - Right Here Waiting for You"

Cantharidate forgery/forgoer/horrify/foxier/error [Erica]

exterminator fiduciary/highchair/acidify/Georgia/Richard

Arthur Georgia dominatrix

*Arthur Michigander airworthier [J]

Georgia aircraftmen/documentary/inferiority/retardation/criminated/Dutchwoman/defamatory/dominatrix/

mariticide/matriarchy/medication/mediocrity/unworthier

Georgia Richard marry fortieth (No!)

LORD:

"polygamy splinters families":

Sinless immortal Alfie

Sinless meatloaf pilgrim

magisterialness floppily

generalissimo misapply/pitfalls

pointless playgirls

profeminists impale

Gorilla impalement

ASYMMETRY flagellosis/flagpoles/lifespans/signalise/signifies

Sire immolating apples

illegalisation pyres

"A woman of great value" [J]

"The pain will be obviated":

elevation pitiable

"You will burn by flesh on pyre."

"Ashkenazim versus Sephardim":

Khazar underemphasises/persuasiveness

Messiah unimpressed

Ramakrishna despises

Dauphin Messiah maker sir

"Most powerful archangel":

Thermonuclear glows,

Challenger taprooms/Formosa/uproots/warmups (555)

"Smartest archangel":

Metatarsal Gen,

Caesarian

"Evilest Archangel":

Leviathan

Eighteen vasa (Newtonian model)
Heavenliest (23) Carl

"Samael the Venom of God":
Halogenated (K), homogenates (universalise), homologated (racing), megadeathes, Gethsemane, Magdalenes,
meatloaves
meatloaves goodmen/goofed/demon/Hodge
Magdalene homos

"Jordan and Nathaniel":
Alexandrina, dandelion, lionheart, Leonhard, Nintendo, ordained, rational

"Lebedovych and Marianna":
ARCHENEMY DAVID/Aladdin

"David and Jonathan":
joint Havana DNA

[Agamemnon dies in bathtub;
Queen of Sheba is Jay;
Baba childhood bath Alexander, wants him immolated]
"David and Bathsheba":
Baba shithead/advised/invaded

"Samson and Delilah": dandelion hassal

"Alexander Shapiro Grothendieck":
exoneration Hagar deciphers
Pericles axehead throning

"World War Three":
retard whore/hero
dorthea erl/err
Leah terror/error/retro/wrote
LORD weather/Arther/wrath/hate
WEED harlot/LOATH/TORAH/wrath
error whaled/death/Leah
reward throw/towel

"georgia travis demoted":
Agosto diadem giver
dreamer tatoos
tardigrade vise

"Marianna demoted":
diadem Reamonn

[Discovered at UNM ... Lobos]
"Alexander haldol lobotomy":
bandleader Loyola
maternal Loyola
Loyola bondholder/landholder/methadone/Albertan
mother landlady/blooded
dethrone lambda
demote Randall
Albert deadman/axeman/daemon/damned

"Alexander lobotomised":
DELIBERATE SOLOMON
META REBELLION/landlord
bloodstained Rome
disablement ordeal

"Alexander HIV infected":
needlecraft divine

"Alexander asked Jordan to prom": earned promote Jordan/Oakland

[totally wrong]
"Alexander asked Jinwen to prom":

earn womanliness pork
earn demote Okinawan/Parkinson/Nikolas

"Alexander skips prom":
earn diploma/soldier/armless

"Alexander cures HIV": underachiever

[underachievement]
"Alexander proves Riemann Hypothesis":
extraordinariness shovelman/Hasheem/nymphes/Penelope/Yasmeen
demineralises Pharaoh
Phaeton demineralises senhor

"Alexander scapegoat" (4442):
exonerates alpaca
earn palace god

"Alexander self sabotage" (4440):
exonerate glassed
Albert godless
earn bosselated

[Jordan>Ginny>Erica]
"Alexander self excision":
californian/RECONDENSES/RENAISSANCE/Floridian/financiers/fleeciness/friendless/LORDLINESS/narcissine
RECONDENSES FILIAL/ALFIE/FELIX/ALEX
renaissance foiled
LORDLINESS FIANCEE/cain
EARN DEIFIES CANE
LORD fleeciness/financial/licensee/faceless

...
FRIEDA (1007) LONELINESS
ANNEX socialiser/OILFIELDS
ANNEX FRIEDA ELOISE(asylum)/CELLS/LOSES/EXES
Cain federalises/friendless/felonries
Cinderella foxiness
EXCELSIOR DISANNEX/SEINFELD

...
LIFELINE cesarean/EARNED
EARN fleeciness/LIDOCAINE/oceanside/LIFELINE/cleanses/fiancee/FOXINESS/lionised/SILICONE/DEIFIES/aliened/
casino
earn Aeneid foils/loses

"Alexander buys lidocaine":
DISOBEDIENCE lauryn
DIABOLIC annulars/unearned
INEXCUSABLE ORDAINED/ALADDIN/LORDED
lorded cannibalise
annul disobeyer/excelsior/exorcised
excelsior undeniably/banana

[If J surgery, unanaesthetized]
"Jordan buys lidocaine":
cannabidiol/cannibalise
dandelion Icarus Job
unordained Jacob

"Jordan excises brand":
condenses Jarrid (Enoch ... Cohen)/bird/Rabi/raja
ordain earned/debera/Jared/Edens

"Marianna excises brand":
Messianic banned/Aaren/annex/Debra/earn

[last resort]
"Alexander self immolation":
LIFELINE (2022) salamander/monster/Salomon/tornado
MINERALISE Donatello/meatloaf
NATANIEL MISLEADER

OILMAN FELLATIO RENAMES
demote (2111) millenarian
demotion reinflames
elates iliofemoral/Maimonidean/manifolder
LORD emanation Alfie

"Save the soul not the life":
elevation lotus

(Genesis 3:6)
"the tree was desirable to make one wise, she took from its fruit and ate; and she gave also to her husband with her, and he ate."
Apple ... iphone, Apple Records

(Genesis 21:32)
"Abimelech": Michael

(Psalms 110:4)
"Mechizedek": emceed, miked
[Eminem]

(Ezekiel 48:35)
"and the name of the city from that day shall be, 'The LORD is there.' "
"The LORD is there":
Shiloh retter (savior)
Detroit seer

(Genesis 49:10-11)
Until Shiloh comes,
And to him shall be the obedience of the peoples...
He washes his garments in wine,
And his robes in the blood of grapes.

K Relativist, (L absolute):
"he will intend to make alterations in times and in law ... his dominion will be taken away, annihilated and destroyed forever" (Daniel 7:25-26)

"But before faith came, we were kept in custody under the law, being shut up to the faith which was later to be revealed. Therefore the Law has become our tutor to lead us to Christ, that we may be justified by faith. But now that faith has come, we are no longer under a tutor." (Galatians 3:23-25)

"My covenant I will not violate,
Nor will I alter the utterance of My lips." (Psalm 89:34)

"If He would render Himself as a guilt offering": (Isaiah 53:10)
DEMINERALISATION FLEURDELIS
WRONGHEADEDNESS FIRELIGHTER/FORFEITURE/FLAMEOUT
reward demineralise lighthouse/ghoulish/foolish/elliott/eight

...
lifeline undergraduate foolisher/glorifies/wormholes/forgoes/moorish
lifeline airworthiness model Freda
lifeline femur airworthiness godhead
LIFELINE RETROGRESSION DIADEM

"He will see His offspring,
He will prolong His days": (Isaiah 53:10)
lifeline professorship wholesaling/godliness/yielding/Delilah/gasoline/goalless/highness/holiness/
lionised/odyssean

"the smith who BLOWS the fire of coals" (Isaiah 54:16):
Themistocles abolisher/Waterloos

"the destroyer to ruin" (Isaiah 54:16):
Tortures dethrone
Detroit honesty/thrones/unhorse
Yehudit rottener

" 'Behold the days are coming,' declares the LORD,
'When I shall raise up for David a righteous Branch;
And He will reign as king and act wisely

And do justice and righteousness in the land.
In His days Judah will be saved,
And Israel will dwell securely;
And this is His name by which He will be called,
The LORD our righteousness.' " (Jeremiah 23:5-6)

"The LORD our righteousness":
ghoulishness tortured
eighteen holdout/horrors/lotus
godliest southerner
horseshoeing duteous
rigorousness turtle
houseguest dishonor
Esther shouldering/unrighteous/dishonours/honourless/horrendous/horridness/ungodliest/unholiest
restores neurologist/lighthouse (Belle Isle, Caltech?)/hungriest/doghouse/holdout/hideout/surgeon

XTIANITY ENTHRONES DEATH

"Because you have said, 'We have made a covenant with death,
And with Sheol we have made a pact.
The overwhelming scourge will not reach us when it passes by,
For we have made falsehood our refuge and we have concealed ourselves with deception.' " (Isaiah 28:15)

"And your covenant with death shall be canceled,
And your pact with Sheol shall not stand;
When the overwhelming scourge passes through,
Then you become its trampling place." (Isaiah 28:18)

"twenty-third for Delaiah"
(1 Chronicles 24:18)

"He makes the depths boil like a pot" (Job 41:31) [Leviathan ... Potholder ... Weed ... Dandelion]

"Indeed, the very hairs of your head are all numbered." (Luke 12:7) ... Algebraic Topological Weed counting holes.

"For what purpose does frankincense come to Me from Sheba, And the sweet cane from a distant land?" (Jeremiah 6:20)

"the women knead dough to make cakes for the queen of heaven; and they pour out libations to other gods in order to spite Me.' 'Do they spite Me?' declares the LORD. 'Is it not themselves they spite, to their own shame?' "(Jeremiah 7:18-19)

"For behold, I am sending serpents against you, Adders, for which there is no charm, And they will bite you,' declares the LORD." (Jeremiah 8:17)

"Rejoice in the wife of your youth." (Proverbs 5:18)

"There is a time for being ahead,
a time for being behind;
a time for being in motion,
a time for being at rest;
a time for being vigorous,
a time for being exhausted;
a time for being safe,
a time for being in danger."
(Tao 29:7-14, ... Solomon)

"And His name will be called Wonderful Counselor, Mighty God,
Eternal Father, PRINCE OF PEACE."
(Isaiah 9:6)
Peace Shalom Salaam Solomon

(Daniel 7:9)

"And the Ancient of Days took His seat":
shithead condensation
condensation hesitated/shithead/stateside/steadfast/steadiest/toastiest/sheathed
Cantonese antithesis/astonished/dishonesty/handshakes/Anastasië/dynasties/fantasies/fattiness/Shintoist/
sainthood/satisfied/shiftest/snooziest/stinkiest/Tokyoites

"Haman, the son of Hammedatha" (Esther 3:1 ... Ham... Hamas): Mohammed Nathan

"Pur, that is the lot, was cast before Haman" (Esther 3:7)

"Then after sixty-two weeks the Messiah will be cut off and have nothing" (Daniel 9:26):
transcendentalist eighteen Elysium tattooist/textbooks/beehives/obviates
blameworthiness Washingtonians effectuality
interdenominational backlashes ghettoises/yeshivoth
interdenominational wastebaskets lighthouse theft
Almightiness Yahweh authoritativeness/heterosexualities/transcendentalist/denuclearisation/
conservationist/constitutional/decartelisation/defenestration/dictatorialness/noneffervescent/
educationalist/honourableness/international/incredibleness/indestructible/intercessional/recondensation/
revolutionises/unfriendliness/westernisation
Almightiness Yahweh recondensation levitates/absolute/beehives/elevates/faithful/obviates

(Genesis 2:24)

"For this cause a man shall leave his father and his mother":
schoolmistresses millenarian Theravada/featured

(Genesis 2:24)

"and shall cleave to his wife":
ELEVATION DELILAH/Sascha/whale/Alfie/FLESH
avianise death
Anastasia lovechild/Delhi/DEVIL/CHOW/vice
lovechild wealthiness/Anastasia/alienates/essential/leastwise/Taiwanese/wifeless
Lilith evanesced/enslaves/scandal
evanesce halfwit/shitload/idiot

...

Leviathan Achilles/Delilah/fiasco/asshole/lawless
Cleveland faithless/falsities/asshole
Achilles deflation
Shithead Evelina/fiancee
Casanova wifeliest/weediest/deifies/fleshed
Seinfeld vacillates/oscillate/volatile/WHITEHALL/ACHILLES/CALLISTO/violates

(Genesis 2:24)

"And shall cleave to his wife; and they shall become one flesh."
YAHWEH DELILAH SCHOOLMATE FASHIONABLENESS/clandestineness/nonethicalness
YAHWEH ADOLESCENT SCHOOLMATE DELILAH HEAVENLINESS/Vaselines
Yahweh adolescent schoolmate Lebanese devilish/villain
adolescent schoolmate Lebanese (lifeline halfway)/(avian hellish/Welles/deify)/(deifies Allah)
Yahweh Anastasia lovechild enfeeblement
Yahweh Lilith defenselessness detachable/heathendom/malevolent
Yahweh evanescence disestablishment/anathematise/loathsomeness/assimilates
...
YAHWEH THESSALONIAN DELILAH SCHOOLMATES BEETHOVEN/CLEVELAND
Yahweh Thessalonian Beethoven Delilah Damocles
Yahweh Thessalonian levelheadedness/methodicalness/affectionless/effectiveness/melancholical/achievements
Yahweh Thessalonian Beethoven
demoiselle/schlemiel/shamefaced/academics/acclaimed/accolades/classical/melodical/homeless
Yahweh cannabidiol loathsomeness/lovelessness/malevolence

(Genesis 3:14)

"On your belly shall you go,
And dust shall you eat
All the days of your life":
dishonourableness/distrustfulness/unrighteousness/rebelliousness/unfaithfulness/ungratefulness/
unsuitableness

...

[envenomed, belly ... belle]
"On your belly shall you go":
ANGEL Hurly/SOUL

(Genesis 3:15)

"And I will put enmity
Between you and the woman":
automanipulation intended
manipulation unintendedly

(Genesis 3:16)
"I will greatly multiply
your pain in childbirth":
METAPHORICALLY gullibility/unpityingly/unwittingly/unguiltily

(Genesis 3:17)
"Cursed is the ground because of you":
odouriferousness cheated/behead/BETCHA

(Genesis 3:19)
"For you are dust,
And to dust you shall return.":
TYRANNOSAURUSES deflator

[Eastern]
(Genesis 3:24)
"And at the east of the garden of Eden He stationed the cherubim";
"He stationed the cherubim":
archenemies/Mithridates/Archimedes/Christian/Romanistic

[Elon Musk loves thrusting rockets,
attempts to bribe Alexander into marrying a German]
(Genesis 3:24)
"and the flaming sword which turned every direction":
technologist inventor Archimedean/unremarried/chairmaned/daydreamer/hardhanded/hardheaded/archenemy/
archfiend/chinaware/deacidify/Friedrich/Manchuria/American
AMERICAN TECHNOLOGIST INVENTER (212) FUHRER/YEHUDI
ARCHENEMY DAVID TRINITROTOLUENE/interreligious/nonintercourse/reintroduction/liechtenstein/unenlightened/
unfriendliest/constitution/friderichsen
ARCHENEMY DAVID LICHTENSTEIN DETOURING
archenemy David constitution defender... /redefiner/weeding ?
archenemy David Fridericsen dethroning [N]

...
"Adolf Hitler":
fellatio/fellator/idolater
loath Fred

["Erica Standhart": cantharidate]
(Genesis 4:1)
"I have gotten a manchild with the help of the LORD.":
CANTHARIDATING homophile/potholed/wifehood/withheld/demote/vetoed

[Travis means "tiller of the soil"]
(Genesis 4:2)
"Cain was a tiller of the ground":
cantharidating foul [chicken]
congratulation (1002) heifer/herald
flesh eroticisation

"Cain brought an offering to the LORD of the fruit of the ground." (Genesis 4:3 ... fruitcake)

"Therefore whoever kills Cain, vengeance will be taken on him sevenfold" (Genesis 4:15 ... Seven of Nine,
Catherine Janeway, Star Trek Voyager)

"And Kenan lived seventy years, and became the father of Mahalalel." (Genesis 5:12 ... Halal)

"Then Abram said to Lot, 'Please let there be no strife between you and me, nor between my herdsmen and
your herdsmen, for we are brothers.' " (Genesis 13:8)

"Please let there be no strife between you and me" (Genesis 13:8):
blameworthiness Aberdeen Pluto

[Gravedigger Judah]
"Come and let us sell him to the Israelites and not lay our hands on him; for he is our brother, our own
flesh." (Genesis 37:27)

"confinement" (Genesis 40:3) "budding" (Genesis 40:10)
Feynman, Yasodhara

"three" (Genesis 40: 10, 12, 13, 16, 18, 19, 20)

"on the vine were three branches ... grapes" (Genesis 40:10) [restored]

"three baskets of white bread" (Genesis 40:16) [executed]

"hang you on a tree; and the birds will eat your flesh off you" (Genesis 40:19)

"seven cows, sleek and fat; and they grazed in the marsh grass" (Genesis 41:2,3) [SEVEN COW, marshal]

"seven" (Genesis 41:2,3,4,5,6,7,18,19,22,23,24,26,27,29,30,34,36, in Pharaoh's dreams)

"Now it came about as they were emptying their SACKS, that behold, every man's BUNDLE OF MONEY was in his SACK; and when they and their father saw their bundles of money, they were dismayed."
(Genesis 42:35 ... Goldman Sachs)

"brother Benjamin, his mother's son": northeasterner Simmons
(Genesis 43:29 ... Simmons trader)

"for we cannot see the man's face" (Genesis 44:26 ... You shall not see My face ... faceless man)

"you shall eat the fat of the land" (Genesis 45:18 ... prodigy)

"Rachel died ... and I buried her there on the way to Ephrath (that is, Bethlehem)." (Genesis 48:7 ... G Rachel?)

[Marshal's wand]
(Genesis 49:10)

"Nor the ruler's staff from between his feet":

BLAMEWORTHINESS TORTURERS
reinstatement horseshoe/errorless
TRAITOROUSNESS BETHLEHEM
TRUSTWORTHIEST MENORAH
Albert erroneousness

...
"Until he comes to Shiloh":
Themistocles [N]

...
"Nor the ruler's staff from between his feet, Until Shiloh comes":
blameworthiness trinitrotoluene Hercules
Albert Einstein Themistocles unremorseful/honourless

"And as for you, you meant evil against me, but God meant it for good in order to bring about this present result to preserve many people alive." (Genesis 50:20 ... There is good in bad)

"And the sons of Uzziel: Mishael" [Uzziel son of Kohath] (Exodus 6:22)

[... Taste for power, just where did he get the idea?]

"Then then LORD said to Moses, "Say to Aaron, 'Take your staff and stretch out your hand over the waters of Egypt ... that they may become blood.'" (Exodus 7:19)

"And you shall keep it [lamb] until the fourteenth day of the same month, then the whole assembly of the congregation of Israel is to kill it at twilight." (Exodus 12:6)

"Then the LORD said to Moses, 'Behold, I will rain bread from heaven for you' " (Exodus 16:4)

"there was a fine flake-like thing, fine as the frost on the ground" (Exodus 16:14) [unleavened bread, unlike Oldsmobile in Nathan's Testament]

"And the house of Israel named it manna, and it was like coriander seed, white; and its taste was like wafers with honey." (Exodus 16:31)

"the LORD will have war against Amalek from generation to generation." (Exodus 17:16) [Amalekite: MIKAEL, Ismael, Islam, Tesla, Kali, Leia, Meta, Kai, MIT, Sam, set]

"And Moses chose able men out of all Israel, and made them heads over the people, leaders of thousands, of hundreds, of fifties, and of tens. And they judged the people at all times" (Exodus 18:25-26 ... NOT herd democracy)

"But if the slave plainly says, 'I love my master, my wife, and my children; I will not go out as a free man,' ... his master shall pierce his ear with an awl; and he shall serve him permanently." (Exodus

21:5-6)

[CONSORTS]

"If he takes to himself another woman, he may not reduce her food, her clothing, or her conjugal rights. And if he will not do these three things for her, then she shall go out for nothing, without payment of money." (Exodus 21:10-11)

[VIOLENCE]

"if he gets up and walks around outside on his staff, then he who struck him shall go unpunished; he shall only pay for his loss of time, and shall take care of him until he is completely healed." (Exodus 21:19)

"If a ransom is demanded of him, then he shall give for the redemption of his life whatever is demanded of him." (Exodus 21:30)

[VIRGINITY]

"And if a man seduces a virgin who is not engaged, and lies with her, he must pay a dowry for her to be his wife." (Exodus 22:16)

[STUDENT LOANS]

"If you lend money to My people, to the poor among you, you are not to act as a creditor to him; you shall not charge him interest." (Exodus 22:25)

[HORDES]

"You shall not follow a multitude in doing evil, nor shall you testify in a dispute so as to turn aside after a multitude in order to pervert justice; nor shall you be partial to a poor man in his dispute." (Exodus 23:2-3)

[PLANT RIGHTS]

"And you shall sow your land for six years and gather in its yield, but in the seventh year you shall let it rest and lie fallow" (Exodus 23:10-11)

"You are not to boil a kid in the milk of its mother" (Exodus 23:19) :
demineralisation butterfly
shithead Tinkerbell (887) immaturity/trinity
meatloaf bloodthirsty enthrone

["Palestinians"]

"You shall make no covenant with them or with their gods. They shall not live in your land, lest they make you sin against Me; for if you serve their gods, it will surely be a snare to you." (Exodus 23:32-33)

[IMITATION, X-tian not blood]

"Then he took the book of the covenant and read it ... So Moses took the blood and sprinkled it on the people, and said 'Behold the blood of the covenant, which the LORD has made with you in accordance with all these words.'" (Exodus 24:7-8)

"the cloud covered the mountain" (Exodus 24:15)

[IMITATION, Jesus]

"And Moses entered the midst of the cloud as he went up to the mountain; and Moses was on the mountain forty days and forty nights." (Exodus 24:18)

"he brought the ark into the tabernacle" (Exodus 40:21)

"Every grain offering of yours, moreover, you shall season with salt, so that the salt of the covenant of your God shall not be lacking from your grain offering; with all your offerings you shall offer salt." (Leviticus 2:13)

"all fat is the LORD'S" (Leviticus 3:16)

"It is a perpetual statute throughout your generations in all your dwellings: you shall not eat any fat or any blood." (Leviticus 3:17)

"Fire shall be kept burning continually on the altar; it is not to go out." (Leviticus 6:13) [Zoroastrian]

"He also took all the fat that was on the entrails and the lobe of the liver, and the two kidneys and their fat; and Moses offered it up in smoke on the altar." (Leviticus 8:16, filters)

"Whatever in the water does not have fins and scales is abhorrent to you. (Leviticus 11:12)

"For I am the LORD your God. Consecrate yourselves therefore, and be holy; for I am holy. And you shall not make yourselves unclean with any of the swarming things that swarm on the earth." (Leviticus 11:44)

"And Aaron shall have lots for the two goats, one lot for the LORD and the other lot for the scapegoat." (Leviticus 16:8, Lot is Aaron)

"Then Aaron shall lay both of his hands on the head of the live goat, and confess over it all the iniquities of the sons of Israel, and all their transgressions in regards to all their sins; and he shall lay them on the head of the goat and send it away into the wilderness by the hand of a man who stands in readiness." (Leviticus 16:21, James wrt Alexander)

[HYGIENE]

"You shall not lie with a male as one lies with a female; it is an abomination." (Leviticus 18:22)
: anathema housewifeliness

"You shall not lie with a male as one lies with a female":
unwholesomeness whitehall meatloaf Leia

"The priest shall also make atonement for him with the ram of the guilt offering before the LORD for his son which he has committed, and the sin which he has committed shall be forgiven him." (Leviticus 19:22 ... Ram of the guilt offering)

"And in the fifth year you are to eat of its fruit, that its yield may increase for you" (Leviticus 19:25)

[HYGIENE, not immorality.

Sodomy is mixing feces with blood, condoms mandatory. E.g.: HIV.]

"If there is a man who lies with a male as those who lie with a woman, both of them have committed a detestable act; they shall surely be put to death." (Leviticus 20:13)

[HYGIENE, E.g.: Ebola]

"If there is a woman who approaches any animal to mate with it, you shall kill the woman and the animal; they shall surely be put to death." (Leviticus 20:16)

"If there is a man who takes his brother's wife, it is abhorrent; he has uncovered his brother's nakedness. They shall be childless" (Leviticus 20:21)

"If there is a man who takes his brother's wife":
airworthiness sweetheart Bohemias

"They shall not take a woman who is profaned by harlotry, nor shall they take a woman divorced from her husband; for he is holy to his God." (Leviticus 21:7 ... divorcee consort rationale over abandonment)

"Then the LORD spoke to Moses, saying, 'Speak to Aaron ...'"
(Leviticus 22:17-18, persistent dynamic of speaking directly to Moses, secondhand to Aaron)

[emanation]

"I will make My dwelling among you, and My soul will not reject you. I will also walk among you and be your God, and you shall be My people. I am the LORD your God" (Leviticus 26:11-13)

[God Most High vs Almighty]

"I will take of the Spirit who is upon you, and will put Him upon them; and they shall bear the burden of the people with you, so that you shall not bear it all alone. (Numbers 11:17)

"Joshua the son of Nun" (Numbers 11:28)

[Good sentiment]

"But Moses said to him, 'Are you jealous for my sake? Would that all the LORD'S people were prophets, that the LORD would put His Spirit upon them!' " (Numbers 11:29)

[Dr. Brandon Quayle Reynolds]

"Now there went forth a wind from the LORD, and it brought forth quail from the sea" (Numbers 11:31)

[The M]

"But the LORD said to Moses, 'If her father had but spit in her face, would she not bear her shame for seven days? Let her be shut up for seven days outside the camp, and afterwards she may be received again.' " (Numbers 12:14)

[Equality ideal]

"Now Korah the son of Izhar, the son of Kohath ... rose up before Moses ... 'You have gone far enough, for all the congregation are holy, every one of them' " (Numbers 16:1-3)

"the rod of Aaron for the house of Levi had sprouted and put forth BUDS and produced blossoms, and it bore ripe almonds." (Numbers 17:8)

[Rock yielding]

"assemble the congregation and speak to the rock before their eyes, that it may yield its water." (Numbers 20:8)

"Aaron ... rebelled against My command at the waters of Meribah" (Numbers 20:24)

[LOTR Gandalf and Balrog,
Miriam dies at Kadesh]

"You shall not pass" (Numbers 20:18)

[Harry Potter

Hormah, Hor, horcrux, serpent, sir]

"the name of the place was called Hormah. Then they set out from Mount Hor ... And the LORD sent fiery serpents among the people and they bit the people, so that many people of Israel died."
(Numbers 21:3-6)

[WOT Dragon, basis of flags]

"And Moses made a bronze serpent and set it on the standard; and it came about, that if a serpent bit any man, when he looked to the bronze serpent, he lived." (Numbers 21:9)

[Wells, ... Wellesley]

"they continued to Beer, that is the well" (Numbers 21:16)

[Mattanah... Manhattan, semi-holy ground of Nahaliel ... Nathaniel, NY]

"And from the wilderness they continued to Mattanah, and from Mattanah to Nahaliel" (Numbers 21:18-19)

[Jaz, ... Yaz, Yasmine, Yah's mine]

"came to Jahaz" (Numbers 21:23)

[As Abraham Genesis 12:3]

"Balaam the son of Beor ... For I know that he whom you bless is blessed, and he whom you curse is cursed." (Numbers 22:5-6)

[Zechariah 9:9 'your king ... mounted on a donkey']

"But God was angry because he was going, and the angel of the LORD took his stand in the way as an adversary against him. Now he [Balaam] was riding on his donkey and his two servants were with him." (Numbers 22:22)

"he did not go as at other times to seek omens" (Numbers 24:1)

[Bourne Jason, Adam eye opener]

"The oracle of Balaam the son of Beor,
And the oracle of the man whose eye is opened" (Numbers 24:3)

"And the name of the Midianite woman who was slain was Cozbi the daughter of Zur, who was head of the people of a father's household in Midian." (Numbers 25:15)

Zur, Zurich

"Cozbi the daughter of Zur" (3343):
Dorothea butcher

"they [Israel] also killed Balaam the son of Beor with the sword" (Numbers 31:8)

[not kill]

"you shall drive out all the inhabitants of the land from before you" (Numbers 33:52)

"But if you do not drive out the inhabitants of the land from before you, then it shall come about that those whom you let remain of them will become as pricks in your eyes and as thorns in your sides" (Numbers 33:55)

"Let them [daughters] marry whom they wish" (Numbers 36:6)

"The LORD your God who goes before you will Himself fight on your behalf, just as He did for you in Egypt before your eyes, and in the wilderness where you was how the LORD your God carried you, just as a man carries his son" (Deuteronomy 1:30-31)

[Effective]

"We left no survivor." (Deuteronomy 2:34)

"For only Og king of Bashan was left of the remnant of the Rephaim ... [his bedstead] Its length was nine cubits" (Deuteronomy 3:11)

"And you shall love the LORD your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your might." (Deuteronomy 6:5)

"You shall fear only the LORD your God" (Deuteronomy 6:13)

"man does not live by bread alone, but man lives by everything that proceeds out of the mouth of the LORD" (Deuteronomy 8:3)

"the LORD your God was disciplining you just as a man disciplines his son" (Deuteronomy 8:5)

[Holy conquest]

"Do not say in your heart when the LORD your God has driven them out before you, 'Because of my righteousness the LORD has brought me in to possess this land,' but it is because of the wickedness of these nations that the LORD is dispossessing them before you."
(Deuteronomy 9:4)

"two tablets of stone written by the finger of God" (Deuteronomy 9:10)

"For the LORD your God is the God of God's and the Lord of lords" (Deuteronomy 10:17)

[Israel unobservant]

"For if you are careful to keep all this commandment ... your border shall be from the wilderness to Lebanon, and from the river, the river Euphrates, as far as the western sea." (Deuteronomy 11:22-24)

[FIN, ... Finnish]

"anything that has fins and scales you may eat" (Deuteronomy 14:9)

[No long term debt]

"At the end of every seven years you shall grant a remission of debts." (Deuteronomy 15:1)

[Welfare, medicaid]

"However, there shall be no poor among you ... you shall not harden your heart, nor close your hand from your poor brother, but you shall freely open your hand to him, and generously lend him sufficient for his need in whatever he lacks." (Deuteronomy 15:4-8)

"For the poor will never cease to be in the land" (Deuteronomy 15:11 Jesus)

[piercings signify slavery]

"then you shall take an awl and pierce it through his ear into the door, and he shall be your servant forever" (Deuteronomy 15:17)

"unleavened bread, the bread of affliction (for you came out of the land of Egypt in haste)" (Deuteronomy 16:3)

[Feast of Booths]

"Seven days you shall celebrate a feast to the LORD your God" (Deuteronomy 16:15)

"Three times in a year all your males shall appear before the LORD your God in the place which He chooses, at the Feast of Unleavened Bread and at the Feast of Weeks and at the Feast of Booths" (Deuteronomy 16:16)

[LORD favors governance of judges]

"You shall appoint for yourself judges and officers in all your towns which the LORD your God is giving you, according to your tribes, and they shall judge the people with righteous judgement." (Deuteronomy 16:18)

[KINGS - NO MULTIPLICATION]

"you shall surely set a king over you whom the LORD your God chooses... you may not put a foreigner over yourselves who is not your countryman. Moreover, he shall not multiply horses for himself ... Neither shall he multiply wives, lest his heart turn away; nor shall he greatly increase silver and gold for himself." (Deuteronomy 17:15-17)

"Thus you shall not show pity: life for life, eye for eye, tooth for tooth, hand for hand, foot for foot." (Deuteronomy 19:21)

[Honorable siege warfare]

"you shall strike all the men in it with the edge of the sword. Only the women and the children and the animals and all that is in the city, all its spoil, you shall take as booty for yourself" (Deuteronomy 20:13-14)

[Absalom, Jesus, Judas]

"he who is hanged is accursed of God" (Deuteronomy 21:23)

[No pollination]

"No one of illegitimate birth shall enter the assembly of the LORD: none of his descendants, even to the tenth generation, shall enter the assembly of the LORD." (Deuteronomy 23:2)

[No pornography]

"your camp must be holy; and He must not see anything indecent among you lest He turn away from you." (Deuteronomy 23:14)

[Anti-slavery]

"You shall not hand over to his master a slave who has escaped from his master to you." (Deuteronomy 23:15)

[Anti-prostitution]

"You shall not bring the hire of harlot or the wages of a dog into the house of the LORD your God" (Deuteronomy 23:18)

[INFLAMMATION: Natan]

"The LORD will smite you with consumption and with fever and with inflammation" (Deuteronomy 28:22)

[Seven of Nine]

"you shall flee seven ways before them, and you shall be an example of terror" (Deuteronomy 28:25)

"You shall betroth a wife, but another man shall violate her" (Deuteronomy 28:30)

[Modern USA]

"The alien who is among you shall rise above you higher and higher, but you shall go down lower and lower." (Deuteronomy 28:43)

"turn to the LORD your God with all your heart and soul" (Deuteronomy 30:10)

"He guarded him as the pupil of His eye." (Deuteronomy 32:10)

"Vengeance is Mine, and retribution" (Deuteronomy 32:35)

[NONPARTISAN]

"do not turn from it [law] to the right or to the left, so that you may have success wherever you go." (Joshua 1:7)

"a harlot whose name was Rahab" (Joshua 2:1)

[Scarlet in Gone with the Wind]

"tie this cord of scarlet thread in the window" (Joshua 2:18)

"And it shall be that the one who is taken with the things under the ban shall be burned with fire, he and all that belongs to him, because he has transgressed the covenant of the LORD" (Joshua 7:15)

"So the sun stood still, and the moon stopped" (Joshua 10:13)

"And the rest of the sons of Kohath received ten cities by lot" (Joshua 21:5)

"But Adonai-bezek fled; and they pursued him and caught him and cut off his thumbs and big toes" (Judges 1:6)

"Adonai-bezek": Aeneid Ko

[Lapp=Finnish]

"Now Deborah, a prophetess, the wife of Lappidoth, was judging Israel at that time. And she used to sit under the palm tree of Deborah" (Judges 4:4-5)

"for the LORD will sell Sisera into the hands of a woman." (Judges 4:9)

[Jael pacifying Sisera, analogous Job/J diarist dairy scheme.]

"So she opened a bottle of milk and gave him a drink" (Judges 4:19)

"But Jael, Heber's wife, took a tent peg and seized a hammer in her hand, and went secretly to him and drove the peg into his temple" (Judges 4:21)

"Until I, Deborah, arose,
Until I arose, a mother in Israel."
(Judges 5:7)

[Megara from Hercules,
copy Tanakh to expiate 18]
"At Taanach near the waters of Megiddo" (Judges 5:19)

[Fashionista]
"Her wise princesses would answer her, ...
A spoil of dyed work embroidered,
Dyed work of double embroidery on the neck of the spoiler?" (Judges 5:29-30)

[OAKLAND]
"the oak that was in Ophrah" (Judges 6:11)

[Leah]
"bring out my offering and lay it before Thee" (Judges 6:18)

[FLIS]
"fleece of wool" (Judges 6:37)

[Laplander ... Finnish]
"You shall separate everyone who laps" (Judges 7:5 ... 300 men)

[Abimelech: Michael, ... Amalekite,
slaughters brothers like Cane or Kay, cause of Vlad's bloodthirst]
"Then he [Abimelech] went to his father's house at Ophrah, and killed his brothers the sons of Jerubbaal, seventy men, on one stone." (Judges 9:5)

[Bloodthirsty, pitiless]
"So Abimelech went up to Mount Zalmon, he and all the people who were with him; and Abimelech took an axe in his hand and cut down a branch from the trees ... and set the inner chamber on fire over those inside, so that all the men of the tower of Shechem also died, about a thousand men and women." (Judges 9:48-49)

[Jesus equivalents, nothing has changed. The LORD creates snares to test men.]
"Then the sons of Israel again did evil in the sight of the LORD, served the Baals and the Ashtaroth" (Judges 10:6)

"And there was a certain man of Zorah, of the family of the Danites, whose name was Manoah" (Judges 13:2)
["Son of Man", Anderson]

"a swarm of bees and honey were in the body of the lion" (Judges 14:8):
feeble-mindedness featherbrain
feeble-mindedness Robinette honor
blameworthiness Newtonian beheaded/defrayed
transformation dandelion/disobeyed/enfeebled/falsehood/headlined/beheaded
TRANSFORMATION YAHWEH HONEYBEE FELONIES
DANDELION NEWTON BETRAYER MESSIAH
NATHANIEL MORDRED NEWTON YAHWEH BOOBIES
foreordination Thessalonian weedy
foreordination Nathaniel Odyssey
FOREORDAINMENT BOSTONIAN FLESH YAHWEH
foreordination honeybee deathblow/fateleness
restorability honeybee madonna defense/offends
THESSALONIAN YAHWEH DEMOTION ROBBERY
SHITHEAD WORLDBEATER honeymoon/noninsane/womanise/awesome/FEYNMAN/Heisman/offense/showoff/YASMEEN
WORLDBEATER EMANATION ODYSSEY WIFE

"Then Samson said to them, 'Let me now propound a riddle to you' "
(Judges 14:12) [Tom RIDDLE / HARRY Potter ... Lesson: do not gamble, people will skew the odds.]

"three hundred foxes" (Judges 15:4) [Flis ... Лис "fox"]

[Spider ... Moghedien of WOT]
"Delilah took the seven locks of hair and wove them into the web" (Judges 16:14)

[annoy ... Anne Frank, nosy Job]

"And it came about when she [Delilah] pressed him daily with her words and urged him, that his soul was annoyed to death." (Judges 16:16)

"A razor has never been on my head, for I have been a Nazirite to God from my mother's womb." (Judges 16:17)

"Then the Philistines seized him and gouged out his eyes; and they brought him down to Gaza" (Judges 16:21) [broken glass ... Глаз "eye"]

"Dagon their god" (Judges 16:23) [Dragon]

" 'Call for Samson, that he may amuse us.' So they called for Samson from the prison, and he entertained them. And they made him stand between the pillars." (Judges 16:25) [jester, comedian, ... pillar of fire]

"the house fell on the lords and all the people who were in it" (Judges 16:30) ["Bringing Down the House", film about MIT students in Vegas]

"And the man Micah had a shrine and he made an ephod and household idols" (Judges 17:5) [Shriners charity, Anne Frank, Jesus ben Joseph all sympathy milking.]

[Ruth's daughter-in-law Marianna]

"Do not call me Naomi; call me Mara, for the Almighty has dealt very bitterly with me." (Ruth 1:20)

"you are a woman of excellence" (Ruth 3:11)

[Non greedy polygamy is the foundation of the House of David]

"May the LORD make the woman who is coming into your home like Rachel and Leah, both of whom built the house of Israel; ... may your house be like the house of Perez whom Tamar bore to Judah" (Ruth 4:11-12)

[No mistake; King David thrice descended of consorts]

" 'A son has been born to Naomi!' So they named him Obed. He is the father of Jesse, the father of David. Now these are the generations of Perez: to Perez ... Boaz" (Ruth 4:17-21)

"Hannah had no children ... Now this man would go up from his city yearly to worship and to sacrifice to the LORD of hosts in Shiloh" (1 Samuel 1:2-3)

[Samuel Nazarite]

"but wilt give Thy maidservant a son, then I will give him to the LORD all the days of his life, and a razor shall never come on his head." (1 Samuel 1:11)

[potholder ... weed]

"Then he would thrust it into the pan, or kettle, or caldron, or pot; all that the fork brought up the priest would take for himself." (1 Samuel 2:14)

[Really really bad]

"And therefore I have sworn to the house of Eli that the iniquity of Eli's house shall not be atoned for by sacrifice or offering forever." (1 Samuel 3:14)

"And the head of Dagon and both the palms of his hands were cut off" (1 Samuel 5:4)

[Georgia brain tumor, Alexander rat]

"five golden tumors and five golden mice" (1 Samuel 6:4)

[Cartman humbled]

" 'And watch, if it [ark of LORD] goes up by the way of its own territory to Beth-shemesh, then He has done us this great evil. But if not, then we shall know that it was not His hand that struck us; it happened to us by chance.' Then the men did so, and took two milch cows and hitched them to the cart" (1 Samuel 6: 9-10)

[20 years!]

"And it came about from the day that the ark remained at Kiriath-jearim that the time was long, for it was twenty years, and all the house of Israel lamented after the LORD." (1 Samuel 7:2)

[herd mentality]

"that we also may be like all the nations" (1 Samuel 8:20)

"a man from the land of Benjamin" (1 Samuel 9:16)

[Genesis 49:27 "ravenous wolf"]

"And as for your donkeys which were lost three days ago, do not set your mind on them, for they have been found." (1 Samuel 9:20)

[Shaul Exodus 6:15 next to Kohath, both later rebellious, donkeys fortell lesson of Saul - don't be an ass!

Flexible mind.]

"When the men of Israel saw that they were in a strait (for the people were hard-pressed), then the people hid themselves in caves, in thickets, in cliffs, in cellars, and in pits." (1 Samuel 13:6, strait is Detroit)

"Then Jonathan said, 'My father has troubled the land. See now, how my eyes have brightened because I tasted a little of this honey.' " (1 Samuel 14:29)

[Names associations: Saul, Jonathan, Amalchi, Mara, Michael]

"Now the sons of Saul were Jonathan and Ishvi and Malchi-shua; and the names of his two daughters were these: the name of the first-born Merab and the name of the younger Michal." (1 Kings 14:49)

"an evil spirit from the LORD terrorized him [Saul]" (1 Kings 16:14)

[David's blood is of Ephraim]

"Now David was the son of the Ephrathite of Bethlehem in Judah, whose name was Jesse" (1 Samuel 17:12)

"the soul of Jonathan was knit to the soul of David, and Jonathan loved him as himself." (1 Samuel 18:1)

[streaking]

"And he also stripped off his clothes, and he too prophesied before Samuel and lay down naked all that day and all that night." (1 Samuel 19:24)

[David and Jonathan]

"And they kissed each other and wept together, but David more." (1 Samuel 20:41)

[David Saul pact ... Alexander]

"The LORD will be between me and you, and between my descendants and your descendants forever." (1 Samuel 20:42)

"The sword of Goliath the Philistine" (1 Samuel 21:9)

[Faithful as a Dog]

"Doeg the Edomite, the chief of Saul's shepherds" (1 Samuel 21:7)

"Then the king said to Doeg, 'You turn around and attack the priests.' And Doeg the Edomite turned around and attacked the priests, and he killed that day eighty-five men who wore the linen ephod." (1 Samuel 22:18)

"I know that you [David] are pleasing in my sight, like an angel of God" (1 Samuel 29:9)

[David and Jonathan]

"Your love to me was more wonderful
Than the love of women. (2 Samuel 1:26)

"Shall the sword devour forever? Do you not know that it will be bitter in the end?" (2 Samuel 2:26)

"Now when Ish-bosheth, Saul's son, heard that Abner has died in Hebron, he lost courage" (2 Samuel 4:11)

[Peacetime assassination]

"How much more, when wicked men have killed a righteous man in his own house on his bed, shall I not now require his blood from your hand, and destroy you from the earth?" (2 Samuel 4:11)

"Nathan, Solomon" (2 Samuel 5:14)

[David wants to build LORD a house, so LORD builds David a house.]

"And your house and your kingdom shall endure before Me forever; your throne shall be established forever." (2 Samuel 7:16)

"revelation" (2 Samuel 7:27)

"Bethah and from Berothai" (2 Samuel 8:8)

"the sword shall never depart from your house" (2 Samuel 12:10)

[Jordan]

"I will even take your wives before your eyes, and give them to your companion, and he shall lie with your wives in broad daylight." (2 Samuel 12:11)

"she [Bathsheba] gave birth to a son, and he [David] named him Solomon. Now the LORD loved him and sent word through Nathan the prophet, and he named him Jedidiah [beloved of the LORD] for the LORD'S sake." (2 Samuel 12:24-25)

[Absalom hairy]

"he weighed the hair of his [Absalom's] head at 200 shekels by the kings weight" (2 Samuel 14:26)

["pitched a tent", erection]

"So they pitched a tent for Absalom on the roof, and Absalom went in to his father's concubines in the sight of all Israel." (2 Samuel 16:22)

"you [David] are worth then thousand of us" (2 Samuel 18:3)

"Behold, I saw Absalom hanging in an oak." (2 Samuel 18:10)

"So he [*Joab*] took three spears in his hand and thrust them through the heart of Absalom while he was yet alive in the midst of the oak." (2 Samuel 18:14)

[Asherah]

"Now Absalom in his lifetime has taken and set up for himself a pillar which is in the King's Valley" (2 Samuel 18:18)

[ANTITHESIS OF JESUS/ABSALOM]

"Today you have covered with shame the faces of all your servants ... by loving those who hate you, and by hating those who love you ... For I know this day that if Absalom were alive and all of us were dead today, then you would be pleased." (2 Samuel 19:5-6)

[Squalid ... Faiz]

"Then Mephibosheth the son of Saul came down to meet the king; and he had neither cared for his feet, nor trimmed his mustache, nor washed his clothes, from the day the king departed until the day he came home in peace." (2 Samuel 19:24)

[Integrity]

"And Mephibosheth said to the king, 'Let him even take it all, since my lord the king has come safely to his own house.' " (2 Samuel 19:30)

"When the angel stretched out his hand toward Jerusalem to destroy it, the LORD relented from the calamity, and said to the angel who destroyed the people, "It is enough! Now relax your hand!". And the angel of the LORD was by the threshing floor of Araunah the Jebusite." (2 Samuel 24:16)

(2 Samuel 24:18) [Angel of Death]

"threshing floor of Araunah the Jebusite": Albert Einstein Auguster

"And Adonijah [usurper] sacrificed sheep and oxen and fatlings by the stone of Zoheleth [Serpent Stone]" (1 Kings 1:9)

"Nathan spoke to Bathsheba ... 'please let me give you counsel and save your life and the life of your son Solomon.' " (1 Kings 1:11-12)

"had Solomon ride on King David's mule" (1 Kings 1:38)

[Joseph]

"In Gibeon the LORD appeared to Solomon in a dream at night" (1 Kings 3:5)

[Divide inverse of multiply]

"Divide the living child in two" (1 Kings 3:25)

[Abraham]

"Now God gave Solomon wisdom and very great discernment and breadth of mind, like the sand that is on the seashore." (1 Kings 4:29)

[John Lennon]

"his [Solomon's] songs were 1,005" (1 Kings 4:32)

"cut timber like the Sidonians" (1 Kings 5:6 ... logger ... logician)

[Monetary policy]

"And he overlaid the floor of the house with gold, inner and outer sanctuaries." (1 Kings 6:30)

"the city of David which is Zion" (1 Kings 8:1)

(1 Kings 9:11)

"Hiram king of Tyre": ferryman Ko,
Moriarty Nike

"great amount of spices" (1 Kings 10:10) [Spicer ... Spic ... Spy]

[Beast]

"666 talents of gold" (1 Kings 10:14)

"throne of ivory ... and arms on each side of the seat" (1 Kings 10:18-19)

[Love as a vise ... meatloaf]

"Solomon held fast to these [foreign women] in love." (1 Kings 11:2)

"And he had seven hundred wives" (1 Kings 11:3):
weediness underhanded [Nathan]

[Hera ... Asherah ... Ashtoreth,
Milcom ... milk ... breasted]

"For Solomon went after Ashtoreth the goddess of the Sidonians and after Milcom the detestable idol of the Ammonites" (1 Kings 11:5)

[Immolate]

"Then Solomon built a high place for Chemosh the detestable idol of Moab, on the mountain which is east of Jerusalem, and for Molech the detestable idol of the sons of Ammon." (1 Kings 11:7)

[Nathaniel]

"Ashtoreth Milcom Chemosh Molech": Themistocles coacher

[Dr. Luay Hadad A. lobotomy]

"Then the LORD raised up an adversary to Solomon, Hadad the Edomite" (1 Kings 11:14)

(1 Kings 11:26)

"Jeroboam the son of Nebat, an Ephraimite of Zeredah":

foreordainment patronizes behemoth/beta

foreordainment penetrates (222) Bohemia/Jae

foreordainment Jehoshaphat erotomania/rabbinate/atoner/Barbee/rename

foreordainment Barbee anathematise/Jehoshaphat/heathenism/Amenhotep/ensheathe/Josephine/pantheism/

anathema/apathies/Japanese/Jamesian/monetise/nepotism/PHAETHON/Thompson/Amazons/fashion/Jasmine/Jonahes/

Mathias/mafioso/meanest/opiates/amazes/ashame/poison/septets

foreordainment Jasmine barefoot/bathrobe/betroth/Pharaoh/bettor/father

"Jeroboam the son of Nebat":

Barbee footnote/Jonathon

[Mislead disobedience;

Compare with Jonah's clemency]

"a lion met him on the way and killed him" (1 Kings 13:24)

[Rabbis are teachers, certified not ordained, only Cohen are priests.

... High places, getting high, weed.]

"Jeroboam did not return from his evil way but again he made priests of the high places from among all the people; any who would, he ordained, to be priests of the high places." (1 Kings 13:33)

(1 Kings 16:31)

"Jezebel the daughter of Ethbaal":

godfather beatable/bathtub/beetle/Allah/Bella/Belle/bezel/beta/hate/hell/zeta

(1 Kings 16:31)

"Jezebel the daughter of Ethbaal king of the Sidonians":

transubstantiation globalized joke

(1 Kings 17:1)

"Elijah the Tishbite":

Isiahi/Isiah beetle
Bet atheist

"Prophet Elijah the Tishbite":
Isiah better/beetle/potter/leper
lotteries Pip
obliterates Pip
Albert Pip hottest/titties

(1 Kings 17:1)
"Elijah the Tishbite, who was of the settlers of Gilead":
bloodthirstiest whitehall ghettoises
reestablishes theologise wholewheat/loathed
sweetheart diabolist stealthiest/foolishst/shallowest/faithless/falsities
sweetheart ideologist belittles/faithess/falsities

[To marshal ... LOTR Rohirrim]
"muster" (1 Kings 20:15, 25, 26, 27)

"Then a spirit came forward and stood before the LORD and said, 'I will entice him.' (1 Kings 22:21)
"I will entice him": Micheil went

[Parting waters]
"And Elijah took his mantle and folded it together and struck the waters, and they were divided here and there, so that the two of them crossed over on dry ground." (2 Kings 2:8)

[Whirlwind]
"there appeared a chariot of fire and horses of fire which separated the two of them. And Elijah went up by a whirlwind to heaven." (2 Kings 2:11)

[Salt purifies]
"And he [Elisha] went out to the spring of water, and threw salt in it and said, 'Thus says the LORD, "I have purified these waters." ' " (2 Kings 2:21)

[oil multiplies]
"pour out into all these vessels; and you shall set aside what is full." (2 Kings 4:4)

[resurrection via Elisha]
"behold the lad was dead and laid on his bed ... and the lad sneezed seven times and the lad opened his eyes." (2 Kings 4:32-35)

[Steward Death]
"And it came about as they were eating of the stew, that they cried out and said, 'O man of God, there is death in the pot.' "(2 Kings 4:40)

[food multiplies, 444]
"So he set it before them, and they ate and had some left over, according to the word of the LORD."(2 Kings 4:44)

[heal leprosy]
"Go and wash in the Jordan seven times, and your flesh shall be restored to you and you shall be clean." (2 Kings 5:10)

[Riemann]
"when my master goes into the house of Rimmon to worship there" (2 Kings 5:18)

[Snow White]
"a leper as white as snow" (2 Kings 5:27)

[axehead cane]
"when they came to the Jordan, they cut down trees. But as one was felling a beam, the axe head fell into the water; ... he cut off a stick, and threw it in there, and made the iron float."

[Elijah's spirit upon Elisha; marshal]
"the mountain was full of horses and chariots of fire all around Elisha." (2 Kings 6:17)

[Elijah marshal]
"For the LORD had caused the army of the Arameans to hear a sound of chariots and a sound of horses even the sound of a great army" (2 Kings 7:6)

"This is Jezebel." (2 Kings 9:37, pg. 333 Trinity)

[Voodoo]

"So the man of God [Elisha] was angry with him and said, 'You should have struck five or six times, then you would have struck Aram until you would have destroyed it. But now you shall strike Aram only three times.' " (2 Kings 13:19)

[Resurrection]

"and they cast the man into the grave of Elisha. And when the man touched the bones of Elisha he revived and stood up on his feet." (2 Kings 13:21)

[serpent]

"cut down the Asherah. He also broke in pieces the bronze serpent ... Nehushtan." (2 Kings 18:4)

"He [Hezekiah] trusted in the LORD ... he clung to the LORD" (2 Kings 18:5-6)

"the sons of Eden who were in Telassar?" (2 Kings 19:12)

[reed pierces, Pharaoh]

"Now behold, you rely in the staff of this crushed reed, even in Egypt; in which if a man leans, it will go into his hand and pierce it. So is Pharaoh king of Egypt to all who rely on him." (2 Kings 18:21)

[Angel of Death]

"Then it happened that night the angel of the LORD went out, and struck 185,000 in the camp of the Assyrians; and when men rose early in the morning, behold, all of them were dead." (2 Kings 19:35)

"He brought the shadow on the stairway back ten steps" (2 Kings 20:11)

[Nathan ... Phaeton ... Icarus]

"by the chamber of Nathan-melech the official ... he burned the chariots of the sun with fire." (2 Kings 23:11)

"And they [Babylonians] took away the pots, the shovels ..." (2 Kings 25:14)

"Ishmael the son of Nethaniah, and Johanan the son of Kareah, and Seraiah the son of Tanhumeth the Netophathite, and Jaazaniah the son of the Maacathite" (2 Kings 25:23)

Hello Kittis in the Age of Biblical Japanese

"Noah ... Japheth ... Javan ... Kittim"
(1 Chronicles 1:4-7)

"And the sons of Zerubbabel were Meshullam and Hananiah" (1 Chronicles 3:19)

[Beer]

"Beerah his son, whom Tilgath-pilneser king of Assyria carried away into exile" (1 Chronicles 5:6)

"Kohath ... Korah ... Uriel ... Shaul"
(1 Chronicles 6:22-24)

[thrust, come ... Discharge]

"Then Saul said to his armor bearer, 'Draw your sword and thrust me through with it, lest these uncircumcised come and abuse me.' " (1 Chronicles 10:4)

[Dragon ... Leviathan tempts]

"fastened his [Saul] head in the house of Dagon." (1 Chronicles 10:10)

[Multi-tribal non-Hebraic support in R⁴]

"Uriah the Hittite" (1 Chronicles 11:41)

"using both the right hand and the left to sling stones ... Saul's kinsmen" (1 Chronicles 12:2)

[Musk Ko's vassal]

"And David gathered together the sons of Aaron, and the Levites:
of the sons of Kohath, Uriel the chief, and 120 of his relatives" (1 Chronicles 15:4-5)

"Then David spoke to the chiefs of the Levites to appoint their relatives the singers, with instruments of music" (1 Chronicles 15:16)

[Allen Chen]

"Chenaniah, chief of the Levites, was in charge of the singing: he gave instruction in singing because he

was skillful." (1 Chronicles 15:22)

(1 Chronicles 16:33)

"For He is coming to judge the earth."
eighteen doctorate Fuji (apple)

[Reciprocal, fractions, division, David ... Ramanujan M]
(1 Chronicles 17:10)

"I tell you that the LORD will build a house for you."
worldbeater Delilah filius/Shiloh
worldbeater footstool Delilah/Lilith

(1 Chronicles 17:12)

"I will establish his throne forever":
restorativeness hero
restoration believer/verifies
revelationist flesh Helios/oiler/owlish/Shiloh/wisher/loser/Sheol/sire
AIRWORTHINESS LEFTOVER HELL
airworthiness vetoer flesh
OBLITERATION FREEWILL
EVILEST BERLINER ISOLATORS/harlot/Ishtar
ISSIAH IRREVERSIBLE THEFT
VILLAINESS ROTTWEILER/FERTILISER/foolisher/frostbite
relativeness followers/foolisher/horrible/horrifies
Overthrow (3343 ... Trinity)
Overthrow Albert fleshliness/lifeline/selfless

[Nathan heathen]

"According to all these words and according to all this vision, so Nathan spoke to David." (1 Chronicles 17:15)

(1 Chronicles 21:15)

"threshing floor of Orman the Jebusite":
Albert Einstein honourer/shogun

[Smith]

"He shall build a house for My name, and he shall be My son, and I will be his father; and I will establish the throne of his kingdom over Israel forever." (1 Chronicles 22:10)

"David divided them into divisions" (1 Chronicles 23:6)

"the eighteenth for Happizzez ... the twenty-third for Delaiah" (1 Chronicles 24:15,18)

[Nontrivial 12 month calendar]

"The twelfth for the twelfth month" (1 Chronicles 27:15)

[built on the threshing floor]

(2 Chronicles 3:1)

"the house of the LORD in Jerusalem on Mount Moriah":
foreordainment horseshoe Immanuel/Juliette/Matthieu/immolate/Jemimah (Job's daughter)/Mahomet/tollman/
Elohim/lethal/oilman
FOREORDAINMENT SOLOMON ARISTOTLE/AURELIUS
trinitrotoluene Mohammedans/falsehood/horseshoe/majordomo/Alessandro/Alejandro/Esmeralda/marshaled
trinitrotoluene falsehood menorahes
trinitrotoluene horseshoe Mohammedan
DETHRONEMENT ILIOFEMORAL
TREASONOUS/monstrous/atones/Samson
dethronement immolation horseshoe/fearless/refusal/releasor/assurer/flesh
dethronement immolation flesh hero
Dethronement James formulation/humiliation/millionaire/mournfullest/reformation
DETHRONEMENT FORMULATION JEALOUSIES/aerosolise/jailhouses/horseshoe/humorless

[Echoes Agamemnon and Helen]

"its brim was made like the brim of a cup, like a lily blossom; it could hold 3,000 baths." (2 Chronicles 4:5)

[Spice, spic ... stake, pole, polygamy destroying Israel, courtesy of J ...

Sheba means bitch in Korean]

"there had never been spice like that which the queen of Sheba gave to King Solomon" (2 Chronicles 9:9)

"there had never been spice like that":
representative deathlike/beelike/heathen/Aeneid/betcha/deceit/bitch

"Now the weight of gold which came to Solomon in one year was 666 talents of gold" (2 Chronicles 9:13)

[ivory, footstool, armchair]

"the king made a great throne of ivory and overlaid it with pure gold. And there were six steps to the throne and a footstool in gold attached to the throne, and arms on each side of the seat, and two lions standing beside the arms." (2 Chronicles 9:17-18)

"And he said, 'I will go and be a deceiving spirit in the mouth of all his prophets.' " (2 Chronicles 18:21)

"Zebadiah the son of Ishmael, the ruler of the house of Judah" (2 Chronicles 19:11)

[22]

"Ahaziah was twenty-two years old when he became king"
(2 Chronicles 22:2)

"yield to the LORD and enter His sanctuary" (2 Chronicles 30:8)

[Pardon good intent, spirit]

"For Hezekiah prayed for them, saying, 'May the good LORD pardon everyone who prepares his heart to seek God, the LORD God of his fathers, though not according to the purification rules of the sanctuary.' So the LORD heard Hezekiah and healed the people." (2 Chronicles 30:18-20)

[J metaphor]

"they captured Manasseh with hooks" {thong put through the nose}(2 Chronicles 33:11)
: Shakespearean Cosimo [N]

[Same as Solomon]

"Thus says Cyrus king of Persia, 'The LORD, the God of heaven, has given me all the kingdoms of the earth, and He has appointed me to build Him a house in Jerusalem, which is in Judah.' " (Ezra 1:2)

[Post-Breaking]

"The whole assembly numbered 42,360." (Ezra 2:64)

[Impalement]

"And I [Darius] issued a decree that any man who violates this edict [of Cyrus], a timber shall be drawn from his house and he shall be impaled on it and his house shall be made a refuse heap on account of this." (Ezra 6:11)

[god ElNathan racist]

"So I sent for Eliezer, Ariel, Shemaiah, Elnathan, Jarib, Elnathan, Nathan, Zechariah, and Meshullam, leading men, and for Joiarib and Elnathan, teachers."
(Ezra 8:16)

[Hebrews renamed Jews in Ezra.

Religious intermarriage ideal becomes flesh idolatry Tay Sachs. What of Joseph and Ruth, whose blood sired David? Moses and Zipporah? Etc. ... Sex offenders?]

"the holy race has intermingled with the peoples of the lands; indeed, the hands of the princes and the rulers have been foremost in this unfaithfulness." (Ezra 9:2)

"the holy race has intermingled with the peoples":
interrelationships gametocytes weed
interrelationship sleepyhead welcome

"Maaseiah, Elijah, ... Maaseiah, Ishmael, Nethanel" (Ezra 10:21-22)

"in the direction of the Dragon's Well, and on to the Refuse Gate" (Nehemiah 2:13)

[Focus, God's help]

"So the wall was completed on the twenty-fifth of the month Elul, in fifty-two days." (Nehemiah 6:15)

[Birth of Rabbinic Judaism great,

opposite of cleric Latin Bible, which hoards knowledge concealing deceit.]

"And they read from the book, from the law of God, translating to give the sense so that they understood the reading." (Nehemiah 8:8)

[Good effort but subtle errors,
All fat is the LORD'S.]
"Then he [Ezra] said to them, 'Go eat of the fat,' " (Nehemiah 8:10)

[Division negates multiplication]
"as prescribed by David the man of God, division corresponding to division." (Nehemiah 12:24)

[Contrary to Torah, grain offerings from sincere foreigners welcome.
Also Nehemiah knows that Israel was scattered.]
"they excluded all foreigners from Israel" (Nehemiah 13:3)

[Why not politely return goods?]
"I threw all of Tobiah's household goods out of the room. Then I have an order and they cleansed the rooms; and I returned there the ... frankincense." (Nehemiah 13:8-9)

[Religion transcends language, and blood supercedes language, yet cohesion is admirable.]
"none of them was able to speak the language of Judah" (Nehemiah 13:24)

[Judaism still patriarchal, later converts to rigorous matriarchy.]
"Even one of the sons of Joiada, the son of Eliashib the high priest, was a son-in-law of Sanballat the Horonite, so I drove him away from me." (Nehemiah 13:28)

[Rabbis egalitarian, preservationist]
"Remember me, O my God, for good." (Nehemiah 13:31)

[Esther is intermarriage, book is right after Nehemiah.]
"let the king give her royal position to another who is more worthy than she" (Esther 1:19)

"Hadassah, that is Esther" (Esther 2:7)

[Ham pork sodomy, Haman, Hammedatha, ... Hamas]
(Esther 3:1)
"Haman the son of Hammedatha":
MOHAMMED NATHAN
MOHAMED MANHATTAN
Nathan ashamed/deathes/defames/defeats/demotes/hothead/shammed

[LOT]
(Esther 3:7)
"Pur, that is the lot, was cast before Haman":
blameworthiness catastrophe

"And many among the peoples of the land became Jews, for the dread of the Jews had fallen on them." (Esther 8:17)
[Contrast Nehemiah]

"on the day when the enemies of the Jews hoped to gain the mastery over them, it was turned to the contrary" (Esther 9:1)
[As the potter turns the wheel, whirlwind]

"it was a month which was turned for them from sorrow into gladness" (Esther 9:22)

[Satan the Adversary,
schemes a la Grothendieck,
Pur or Lot, cats purr.]
"For Haman the son of Hammedatha, the Agagite, the adversary of all the Jews, had schemed against the Jews to destroy them, and had cast Pur, that is the lot, to disturb them and destroy them." (Esther 9:24)

[Only the wicked die on a tree]
"he and his sons should be hanged on the gallows" (Esther 9:25)

[memorialise defeat of lot]
"Therefore they called these days Purim after the name of Pur." (Esther 9:26)

[Uz ... Oz. Job ... work ... force (N)]
(Job 1:1)
"There was a man in the land of Uz, whose name was Job":
dishonourableness Johnathan/Mahometan/Manhattan/heathen/Amazon/Newton
amazement heathenishness

[Job responsible for invoking N]

"But put forth Thy hand now and touch all that he has; he will surely curse Thee to Thy face." (Job 1:11)

...

"he will surely curse Thee to Thy face": recrystallise fleece/theft

[Repeated thrice]

(Job 1:16)

"While he was still speaking":

Pilate hellishness/highnesses

eighteen alpha/Hawaii/Issiah

whitehall gipsies

[Job not covenanted, from Uz]

(Job 2:3)

"although you incited Me against him, to ruin him without cause":

congratulation Mohammed Augustine wittiest/outwits

(Job 2:11)

"Eliphaz the Temanite, Bildad the Shuhite, and Zophar the Naamathite":

sentimentalization rehabilitate/redemptible/traumatized/brutalized/dramatized/embittered/humiliated/
maltreated/pauperized/redeemable/repudiated

(Job 3:1)

"And the night which said, 'A boy is conceived.' ":

denicotinised thighbones/advocates/avianised/*Hawaiians*/obviating/Occidents/*vacation*

Washingtonian acidities/shithead

shithead denicotinising/condensation

EIGHTEEN cocainisation [K]/VINDICATION/Bostonian/Chinatowns/Dionysian/Hawaiians/addiction/asininity/

antiacid

(Job 3:5)

"Let a cloud settle on it":

unselect tattooed

deselect tattoo

(Job 3:8)

"Who are prepared to rouse Leviathan":

overthrower Persephone/Alisander

apple overthrower denatures/dethrones

Persephone overthrower/retaliator/evildoer

Persephone evildoer thwart

Alisander perpetrator

Alisander Pharaoh potter

[Nathan's scheme]

(Job 3:12)

"And why the breasts, that I should suck?":

Cantharidate Odysseus/lotuses/Ulysses

acidulousness bathwater

[Queen of Sheba]

(Job 6:19)

"The travelers of Sheba hoped for them.":

elevate stormtroopers/horseshoed/staterooms/theftproof

[Godless CIA]

(Job 8:14)

"Whose confidence is fragile,

And whose trust a spider's web.":

counterespionagers falsifications/federalisation/hardheadedness/Christianised/faithlessness/fatheadedness/
heartlessness/idealizations/worthlessness

(Job 9:9)

"Who makes the Bear, Orion, and the Pleiades":

blameworthiness Aphrodite/dethroned/harpooned/Katherine/Dorothee/Phaethon/pharaoh/Aeneid

misalphabetise dethroned

"Didst Thou not pour me out like milk,

And curdle me like cheese"

(Job 10:10)

...

"Didst Thou not pour me out like milk":

Lordship demotion/Klement

"and curdle me like cheese":

CINDERELLA SCHEME/seducee/emceed/musked/dukes

[palate, Pilate, ... pilates, pirates (Oakland, Las Vegas), Palace Station Hotel and Casino]

"Does not the ear test words,

As the palate tastes its food?"

(Job 12:11)

[313]

(Job 13:3)

"And I desire to argue with God" (8808):

Agosto Aeneid righted/regret

wrongdoer eightsided/Aguste/death

traitorous Aeneid/weeded

EIGHTEEN DIARIST ODOUR

sweetheart gorgonia

ISAAH DETROIT UNDERDOG

Isaiah rounder doggie

guarantee digitised Odo

seigniorage Detroit

(Job 13:15)

"Nevertheless I will argue my ways before Him.":

blameworthiness lifesaver/verifies

[Jeremoth?]

(Job 13:28)

"Like a garment that is moth-eaten.":

EIGHTEEN attestation/MATERNALISM/antimatter/metatarsal/metatron/NATATORIAL/aristotle/lionheart/sanatoria/senhorita

(Job 14:13)

"That Thou wouldst set a limit for me and remember me!":

wholeheartedness (2223) tuttifrutti

blameworthiness retaliator demote

blameworthiness Mohammed flameout

[N on Alexander]

(Job 14:19)

"Water wears away stones":

eastern awarest

[Youth is folly]

(Job 15:10)

"Both the gray-haired and the aged are among us,

Older than your father":

...

GUARANTEE EIGHTEEN UNFORGETTABLE DOORMAT

eighteen dethronement HOTBLOODED/outrageous/betrayal/FOOLHARDY

eighteen dethronement betrayal YOUTH

eighteen unforgettable retrograde *HONOURARY*/MANDATORY

...

FOREORDAINMENT UNDERGRADUATE REGRETTABLE/shareholder

...

foreordainment battleground goddaughter/retrograde

foreordainment retrograde dragon detestable

foreordainment retrograde goddaughter unhealthy/unstable

foreordainment guarantee retrograde bathhouse/Buddha/ghosted/godhead

(Job 17:12)

"They make night into day":

damnation eight/kitti/thigh

(Job 18:7)

"And his own scheme brings him down":

commissar weeding

misdiagnosis condemner/renowned/crowned/homered/Hebrew

(Job 19:6)

"Know then that God has wronged me":
wrongheaded Newton

(Job 19:11)

"And considered me as His enemy."
ARCHENEMY MESSIAE NOSED
Archimedes Yasmeen/Aeneid
recondense maidenhead/Messiah/diadem/Yasmeen
indochinese Yasmeen/snares
Renaissance demonised/denied

(Job 19:18)

"Even young children despise me;
I rise up and they speak against me."

...
[M, McDonalds ... Ruth, Ruthenian]
"I rise up and they speak against me.": Metastasis Ukrainian

(Job 20:10)

"His sons favor the poor,
And his hands give back his wealth."
Christianisation Shakespearean/godforsaken/godlessness/wrongheaded

(Job 20:14)

"To the venom of cobras within him": esterification/confirmation

(Job 21:19)

"Let God repay him so that he may know it.": ophthalmodiastimeter

(Job 22:4)

"Is it because of your reverence that He reproves you":
restorativeness corroborative/recipricatory

(Job 22:23)

"If you return to the Almighty, you will be restored":
unforgettable Demetrius oilier
worldbeater eighteen fruit

(Job 23:20)

"The worm feeds sweetly till he is remembered no more."
motherless bloodthirstier

(Job 27:2)

"And the Almighty, who has embittered my soul":
blameworthiness Mohamed/death/eight

[Custom reversal: applause, apple.
LORD prime mover from Genesis.
Likewise beards, hats.]
"Men will clap their hands at him,
And will hiss him from his place."
(Job 27:23)

(Job 29:16)

"And I investigated the case which I did not know":
denicotinise denicotinise
eighteen denicotinisation David
eighteen cocainisation/condensation/chaoticness/chickenshit

(Job 29:17)

"And I broke the jaws of the wicked":
SWEETHEART HOODWINKED/JEDIDIAH/WIFEHOOD
WICKEDEST JORDAN KITEE
wickedest Ekaterina/Katherina/Katharine/Katherine/Dorothea/Dorothee/(Deborah Hanoi/joint/Jonah/Kain)/
(Frank weed)/Jordan/Aeneid/Frieda
cantharidise kowtow
death octahedron/archfiend/Christian/wardencies/Aberdeen

antichrist beheaded/weed
ANTIHERO JEDEDIAH

...

Jordan whitewashed/atheistic/beseched/bewitched/bitchiest/cheekiest/shitfaced/wickedest/Bethesda/cheetah/
SHITHEAD/sidekick/weediest/catfish/cheated/deceits/deifies/faithes/hotthead/kitties/witches

[Queen of Sheba, responsible for Beta Israel]
(Job 30:30)

"My skin turns black on me,
And my bones burn with fever."
dimethyltubocurarine [nicotinic receptor]

[333 Trinity, Diary ... dairy]
(Job 31:33)

"Have I covered my transgressions like Adam":
Alessandro Mackintoshes [apple]/Michigander
Alessandro Michigander emissary/mistake/messier/meteor/motive/Savior/Travis/krist
Alessandro mistake overachieving/rediscovering/overreaching
ALESSANDRO MICHIGANDER MOTIVE ASKER
ALESSANDRO ARCHENEMY TRAVIS DEVISE/EVOKED
ALESSANDRO ARCHENEMY MISTAKE DIVISOR/DRIVES
Alessandro Mackintosh redeemer/married/midyears/diaries
Mackintosh nasal diary oversevere
Mackintosh nasal degrader/dismissory
Alessandro Travis Michiganders/archenemies/Archimedes/Maimonides
archenemy Travis demineralises/generalissimo/ARMAGEDDON/Alessandro

...

Archimedes grandmaternal/skeleton/Transylvania
Archimedes grandmaternal vises
Archimedes skeleton avianise
Archimedes Transylvania deviser/misdoer/overdoes/oversees

...

Alessandro Schrodinger Miami
[I am that I am]
Alessandro Savior Christ avenged/endgame
ALESSANDRO AMERICAN SOVIET diverge/EMIGRES/grieves/HEDGER
ALESSANDRO DEMETRE KAY MESSIANIC
Maimonides retrogressive/charlataneries

(Job 31:33)

"By hiding my iniquity in my bosom":
Boston dumbing/numbing/Ginny/Hindu
uniting Bond Mommy
HinTing dominus/odious

(Job 31:35)

"Behold, here is my signature;
Let the Almighty answer me!":
blameworthiness Mithridates elementary/regalement/agreement/Emanuel/German
[elementary metaphor ... Alexander abused at IC grade school]
blameworthiness trinity daughter/ethereally/marshalled
blameworthiness eighteen sledgehammer [rouse Leviathan N]
sledgehammer instrument algebraist [Communism]

...

"Let the Almighty answer me!": EIGHTEEN

(Job 33:12)

"Behold, let me tell you, you are not right in this,
for God is greater than man."
[rotting sushi]
TETRAMETHYLENEDIAMINE TRINITROTOLUENE
tetramethylenediamine odoriferous (breathalysing Golgotha)/(algebraist gorgon)

(Job 33:14)

"Indeed God speaks once
Or twice, yet no one notices it." :
denicotinising Renascences/recondenses/transcended

...

(Job 33:18)

"He keeps back his soul from the pit,

And his life from passing over into Sheol."

(Job 34:3)

"For the ear tests words,
As the palate tastes food.":
sweetheart toothpaste seafood

[X, applause crosses hands,
Lots of American locales herein]

(Job 34:37)

"For he adds rebellion to his sin;
He claps his hands among us,
And multiplies his words against God."

...

"He claps his hands among us,
And multiplies his words against God.":
Christianisation highhandedness/lopsidedness/mindlessness/soullessness/dehumanises/godlessness/
heinousness/hellishness/hideousness/lawlessness/unappealing/ungodliness/unwholesome/womanliness
CHRISTIANISATION GODLESSNESS APPLAUDING/APPALLING
Christianisation DANDELION (2232) shadowless/applauded

...

America Washington Philadelphia gaslights
WASHINGTON UNRIGHTEOUSNESS HALOPHILIC
AMERICANISATION POMPOUSNESS DISGUSTING

...

unrighteousness disassimilation/disassociation
Messiah ghoul congregationalist
congratulation ghoulishness Messiah Hawaiian

[Moishe, Faiz]

"Behold now, Behemoth, which I made as well as you"
(Job 40:15)

[Air Jordan #23]

"He is confident, though the Jordan rushes to his mouth."
(Job 40:23)

(Job 40:24) [J hook]

"With barbs can anyone pierce his nose?":
Renaissance Christ neophobia/Pennie/Penny

[Nathaniel]

"Can you draw out Leviathan with a fishhook?" (Job 41:1)

(Job 41:20)

"Out of his nostrils smoke goes forth":
Footstool meritoriousness/righteousness/homogeniser[N]/horseshoeing/rigorousness/thoroughness
Solomon surgeries fishhook

...

"As from a boiling pot and burning rushes":
misalphabetise dragon/unbrand

[Detroit 'the D' weeded]

(Job 40:31)
"He makes the depths boil like a pot": misalphabetise potholed

[Fumigator, gator, crocodile (drug),
Florida gators, Florida gun Jordan]

(Job 41:33)

"Nothing on earth is like him,
One made without fear.":
Nathaniel foreordainment/underestimation/disinformation/homogenisation/integrationist/misinformation/
understatement/dethronement/masterminding
Nathaniel disinformation outgrowth/throwout/whiteout
NATHANIEL DETHRONEMENT FUMIGATOR/authorise/Hiroshima/righteous [scapegoat]
NATHANIEL MASTERMIND NEFERTITI/EIGHTEEN
NATHANIEL UNDERESTIMATION HOMEWORK
FOREORDAINMENT NATHANIEL MUGSHOT/THIGHES
foreordainment inhomogeneities
foreordainment eighteen humiliations/Oklahoman/mouthwash/walkouts/womanish/Salomon/Hawaii/Isaiah

foreordainment Einstein kilowattage/humiliate/megawatt/Tokugawa/ultimate/Kittie/Mikael
foreordainment Tokugawa enlistment/Einstein/enmities/insolent/Leninism/nihilism/menthols/element/elitist/
eminent

foreordainment emanation LIGHTHOUSE/ghoulish/ugliest/(THIGH SHILOH)
TRINITROTOLUENE FEMINISATION/HOMOGENISED/HOODWINKING/Maimonidean/Gethsemane/Washington

(Job 42:6)

"Therefore I retract,
And I repent in dust and ashes."
tenderheartedness authenticator Frieda
tenderheartedness counterfeit diarist ?

"And each one gave him one piece of money and each a ring of gold." (Job 42:11)

[Yoko Ono]

"1000 yoke of oxen" (Job 42:12)

(Job 42:14)

"Jemimah, ... Keziah, ... Keren-happuch":
marihuana/marijuana kimchee [weed spicy]

[Job fair ... get a job,
Jordan of Jemimah]

(Job 42:15)

"And in all the land no women were found so fair as Job's daughters"

...
"fair as Job's daughters": birdhouse

(Psalms 2:2)

"Against the LORD and against His Anointed [Messiah]":
international antagonists

[Travis Black widow web]

(Psalm 2:3)

"Let us tear their fetters apart," (3833):
traitress stepfather
"And cast away their cords from us!":
traitorous Cassandre

(Psalm 2:7)

"He said to Me, 'Thou art My Son, Today I have begotten Thee.' "

...
'Thou art My Son,
Today I have begotten Thee':
dethronement attestative/haughtiest/bathhouse/tattooist/obviates/Agosto/Aguste/eight
Agosto (5551) dethronement

...
'Today I have begotten Thee':
Beethoven agitated/hogtied/death

[Not Jesus]

"Do homage to the Son, lest He become angry, and you perish in the way,
For his wrath may soon be kindled."
(Psalms 2:12)

[LOGICIAN]

(Psalms 29:5)

"The voice of the LORD breaks the cedars;":
characterise beetroot
"Yes, the LORD breaks in pieces the cedars of Lebanon."
characterisation beekeeper

(Psalms 29:10)

"Yes, the LORD sits as King forever."
restorativeness gloried/godlike/soldier/Feliks/yields/deify/flesh/Godel/oiler/Sheol/lord/sire

[David and Absalom (G)]

(Psalm 38:7)

"For my loins are filled with burning":
insubordinate gillyflower

foreordination bullying

[David Eminem rapper]

(Psalm 38:12)

"Those who seek my life lay snares for me":

EMINEM HAYLEY STEELWORKER/fatherless

"LORD, make me to know my end,
And what is the extent of my days,
Let me know how transient I am."

(Psalm 39:4)

(Psalm 46:10)

[A Psalm of the sons of Korah.]

"Cease striving and know that I am God": recondensation Ashikaga/Isaiah

(Psalms 60:7)

"Ephraim also is the helmet of My head;":

Pharaoh flesh deity Elohim meta

SHITHEAD metamorphism/polymerism/immolator

iliofemoral death Sammy tepes

haloperidol Messiah Meta

haloperidol Smith Hasheem

SLEEPYHEAD ISAIAH THEOREM

SLEEPYHEAD ALASTEIR THIEF

sleepyhead immolator atheism

ALASTEIR (3222) mesothelioma/MISEMLOYED/POLYMATHES/shoplifted/sleepyhead

ALASTAIR FLESH MOHAMMED

Alastair Ismael demotes

Alastair Pilate mommy

Mithridates employees Omaha ?

...

"Judah is My scepter [lawgiver]":

ARCHIMEDES JUST

Christmas dupe

Physics majeure

SERAPHIM

JAMES SUPERCITY

Christ Judas/Maude

(Psalm 74:14)

"Thou didst crush the heads of Leviathan":

acidulousness Detroit hatted

(Psalm 77:10)

"It is my grief, That the right hand of the Most High has changed.":

dethronement shithead satisfactory/castigatory/Christmas

dethronement Mithridates (667) tightfist/Asiatic/Cathay/fiasco/Isaiah/Sascha/thighs

[Division metaphor for selection]

"He divided the sea, and caused them to pass through" (Psalms 78:13)

(Psalms 86:2)

"Do preserve my soul, for I am a godly man":

lifesaver monogamously/Alamogordo/Armageddon/polygamous/grandma/napalmed/Reynolds/rounder/superman/

supermom/Amadeus/dragon

(Psalms 96:13)

"Before the LORD, for He is coming":

LOBOTOMISED FOREIGNER

homeschooling debtor

SCHRODINGER HILBERT/THEOREM

Friedrich geometer/theorems

Chesterfield foregone

biotechnologies reformed/freedom/homered

(Psalms 96:13)

"For He is coming to judge the earth.":

fornicator hogtied/thighes

eighteen haircutter/motherhood/traitorous

HARCOURT (1666) eighteenthes/demotions
MICHIGANDER THOROUGHTEST
Friedrich Thomson
Schrodinger Matthieu

...
octahedron featheriest
Mithridates henceforth/foregone/honouree/hunter/regent/throne

(Psalm 104:14)
"He causes the grass to grow for the cattle":
hourglass sweetheart softheart/greatest/torahes/torches

(Psalm 104:18)
"The high mountains are for the wild goats":
demineralisation tattooeer
trinitrotoluene shithead
foreordination lighthouses/thoughtless
underestimating aristotle
fundamentalist airworthiest/whitehorse
reinstatement gladiator/ghoulish

(Psalms 104:26)
"And Leviathan, which Thou has formed to sport in it.":
CHRISTIANISATION FORMULATED PHAETHON

[Flint lead water crisis]
"The flint into a fountain of water."
(Psalms 114:8)

"Let your fountain be blessed,
And rejoice in the wife of your youth.
As a loving hind and a graceful doe, Let her breasts satisfy you at all times;
Be exhilarated always with her love." (Proverbs 5:18-19)

"And rejoice in the wife of your youth":
Friederic fountain/Newton
Friederic Yahweh unjoint
FRIEDERIC JOHNATHON
foreordination thief
counterfeit honeydew/Aeneid
denunciatory heifer/fruit
INTERFERENCE JUDAH
COORDINATION (420) HEIFER [K0]
NEWTON (2323) RECERTIFIED
octahedron juniority/unworthy
fornication weedier/Yehudit
fornicator definite/enjoyed/feinted/honeyed/jointed/hunted
feinted fornicatory/antiheroic/Catherine
enthroned judicatory/acidifier
HARCOURT INFINITE ODEY [ODYSSEUS]

(Proverbs 8:22)
"The LORD possessed me at the beginning of His way":
emanation eighteen lordship (555) hostesses/bestowed
emanation flesh eighteen goddess
worship
emanation lordship highness
emanation lordship honeybee detests
emanation whitehorse longsighted/fleshiness/holiness

(Proverbs 8:30)
"Then I was beside Him, as a master workman":
Messiah Smith emanation (456) reward
Messiah Smith midwesterner Kaaba

(Proverbs 16:25)
"There is a way which seems right to a man,":
Christmastimes throwaway/negatory

...
"But its end is the way of death.":
BUDDHA ANTITHESIS/honestest

weediness audit/dotty

(Proverbs 17:3)

"But the LORD tests hearts":
Beta truthless

(Isaiah 28:18)

"And your covenant with death shall be canceled":
elevate recondensation Buddha
elevate transcendental Aladdin/obadiah/Buddha
Cleveland electrocution/unconscionable/understandable/dishonourable

[LORD GOD Most High created L, K]

"Behold, I Myself have created the smith who blows the fire of coals,
And brings out a weapon for its work;
And I have created the destroyer to ruin." (Isaiah 54:16)

[LORD to Zerubbabel: Barbee]

(Haggai 2:23)

"I will make you like a signet ring, for pI have chosen you":
recrystallising eigenvalue (lambda)/lovemaking/meaningful/honeymoon/inflaming/lawmaking/Oklahoman/
Hawaiian/Okinawan/unifying
recrystallising lovemaking Yahweh
recrystallising honeymoon Kilauea/Hawaii
recrystallising Feynman ghoul ?

[Q]

"And if your eye causes you to stumble, pluck it out, and throw it from you. It is better for you two
enter life with one eye, than having two eyes, to be cast into the fiery hell." (Matthew 18:9 ... Matte)

Potter, pot (weeded, poker)
Potassium (K)
Soda, sod, Sodom
Lot, lottery, zealot
Con, econ
Bran, Brandon Stark, brand, remembrance
Kenneth (South Park hoodie), Kendall Square (MIT)
Cranbrook Kingswood rainbow, Lake Jonah, Buddha riding whale
Nazirite, Nazi, Nazareth
Gay, geisha
Galilee (Lilith ... hence Delilah)
Palatine Hill (Augustus), Emperor Palpatine (demote Vader .. Father)
Solomon Jedidiah (Red vs Blue)
nigro ("black" Latin, behavioral vs complexion), Nigeria; denigrate, niggardly, Schwarzenegger [German
"schwartz" black]
Pharisee, Parsee (Zoroastrian)
Cane, hurricane
Tor, tornado, Torah
Hanukkah ... Hakka (ferryman), Xmas
Purim (Esther), Easter
Pluto (Hades), Plutarch
Roman Cats ... martial women
Lateran, latrean, latrine (sod, sodomy)
Hamas (red triangle, Hong Kong Triad, Palestinian Flag, Trinity), ham (pork, swine)
Epistle, pistol (vs stamen), pistol (gun, Guan Yin, Confucius, Kali)
Scarlet (Gone with the Wind, Communist) vs Iscariot
Palestinian, Philistine
Chinese, machine (Shen Yun), machination
Prom, promise (Zerubbabel in Haggai 2:23)
Joseph, Josephine (Napoleon at MIT foreordained)
Cat, Katana, Miss Kitty
Donkey (Balaam), Don Quixote
transgression, transsexual
Pet, petty, petulance ("get a dog"), pity
Sardis (NYC W44th), sardines, Sardinian
Antony, Antoninus, Antoinette
craven, crave (submit to emotion)
Hexahedral, Hex (curse of David)

Aladdin, Saladin, salad (green)
Hodor "Hold the Door", Odor, Odo
Abel, Abelian
Apple (smartphone)
Octavio, octopus (... Muay Thai), octave (music), Oct (8)
August, Augur
brown (Gita), Brownian (chaotic, "death I am become"), brownstones (Boston), Bronze Age (copper, MIT Coop)
God, Godzilla (tyrannosaurus, vs Kong w. axe)
Fornicator, ... nico, cato
Paul (N), pole, poli, police, cop, Ko
hormones, whore, hordes
Gaza (Samson and Delilah), Gas-A (immolate)
Palestine, Philistine
Doge (Renaissance elected head of state)
Putin (путь, path) Raphael
Brent crude oil, sat next to Euler
Oy, oysters (ruin of Israel)
Marianna, marihuana
poach, pooch (dog)
Queen of Shiba, Toshiba

CONFLUENCE:

1. Daniel 9:26 (Messiah cut off),
2. Isaiah 53:10 (Intercessor);
demineralisation fleurdelis,
3. "You will burn My flesh on a pyre. I am the LORD.":
foreordainment hyperbola

Mortal Kombat Finishers:

Fatality
Animality
Babality ... Baba, Catholicism
Brutality
Friendship

Fragrant Urine in Chinese.

香尿
Xiāng niào

LANDMARKS

Spirit of Detroit.

"And interceded for the transgressors." (Isaiah 53:12)

Joe Louis "The Fist"
[Joseph dreamer, King Louis]

...
"The LORD has bared His holy arm" (Isaiah 52:10)
"And to whom has the arm of the LORD been revealed?" (Isaiah 53:1)

Renaissance Center

Hodor uses time wisely

Injury heals faster than insult.
No enemies unless self created.
Fear is the worst enemy the most powerful.

WEALTH

True wealth is the LORD's esteem, reflected in high honor, good family, and meaningful work.
Material wealth is having what others desire but have not, resources or skills.

"Ukrainian Neo Nazis":
aniseikonia UNA [double vision]

...
Psychology involved nuanced:
1. deny Russian, Hebrew ethnicity
2. forced Ukrainian assimilation
3. questioning implies insanity

4. intellectual belittlement
5. jealous schadenfreude
6. Munchausen's syndrome
7. silent antisemitism

"Alexander raised to believe he is stupid":
deliberateness evildoer apathies/death

[Ukrainian Catholics]

"Alexander grade school immaculate conception":
immunoelctrophoreric decagonal [AVERAGING]/nonlegal/conceal/scandal
guarantee omnipotence calamari/Hamilcar/marshal/Mordecai/radical
guarantee alpha reconsolidation/commercialised/decolonisation/macroeconomics/microeconomics/demineralised/
occidentalised/socioeconomic/coincidences/econometrics/reminiscence/deselection/omniscience
guarantee nicotine axehead Corolla/Apollo
congratulation preadolescence CHAMomile/Michael/Mohamed/Malachi/melodic
Archimedes executioner octagonal
Archimedes electrocution decagonal [Star Wars' Emperor]
Archimedes unapologetical concealment

["Zenon Kopacz second grade":
Koco escaped androgen
(His father is a pharmacist.)]

...
"Alexander public grade school":
Lord Lord Alpha science/genius

Lili'uokalani Papahanaumokuakea?

...
"Destroyed Atlantis":
Alessandro deity
Aristotle (222) sadden
Detroit analyst

"John Fitzgerald Kennedy":
LYNDON ANTIFREEZE/defeating/angered/enraged
DEATH NONFREEZING [LIQUID \$]
Lennon tragedy

"Lyndon Baines Johnson":
BLOODINESS JOHNNY
{prob=(3/1958)(5/61)=.000126}
blood noninsane/ninja
ninja blondness/boldness/boyhood/Lennon
Lennon noonday/banjo

"Lee Harvey Oswald":
slaveholder
warheads lovely
war ladylove [Russian]

"Jacob Leon Rubenstein":
ninja consulter/counselor/bouncer/clobbers
bouncer nonstable
reelection banjo
Lennon saboteur/bribees/justice/obscure
Jonson uncelebrate/Albertine
Baines encounter/Corleone/objector/renounce
Corleone Austin

...
saboteur Joceline
bribes nonnucleate
justice Boolean
TREASON JOCELINE ?!

[Only name containing LIQUID.
Childbirth speaks.
Penalty for adultery is death.]

...
"Jacqueline Lee Kennedy Onassis Bouvier":

inconsiderableness queenlike
noninjuriousness deceivable/cevadilla [poisonous plant]/believed/ladylike/likeable
injudiciousness venereal
avariciousness (887) unkenneled/queenlike
incredibleness nonaqueous
incredibleness jealousy(222) Queen
indiscoverable (1420) queenliness/jealousies
rebelliousness indocyanine [spy agent green medical dye]
villainousness (2292) Jordan Queen

...
LIQUID unreasonableness/insecureness/lovesickness/subservience/vocabularies

"Romulus and Aeneas"(2252):
Alessandro Name

"Romulus and Remus":
MURDER SAMSON
rounder alums
surname Romulus/Lord
assure Lord
Samson murder/ruler
Russ earldom [grandfather]
summoned Ursula ?

[Rome ... Romanov]
"Romulus Palatine Hill":
alleluia triumphs
EMULATION PILLAR
LIONHEART pallium
imperial shallot/autos/lotus
Alpha lumisterol [Vit D precursor]/illumines/minstrel/lintels/monster
mineral hilltops/patulous [branch]/pilulous [3D-elliptic]
null multiplier/pluralities
Israel pullulation [breed, swarm]/plutonium/ululation [wail]/platinum
SHAPIRO ALUMNI

[Riemann]
"Remus Aventine Hill":
relativism, Hellenism, Helvetian, universal, Einstein, Emanuel, Leninism, Riemann
...
relativism Helen
EMULATES LENIN
smith unleaven/envier/urinal
RIEMANN Helvetius/elusive/evillest/thieves/Levite
helmet universal/annuler/Israeli
annul thieveries/Hitlerism

"string theory is true":
theorist unites
rigor trustiest

"string theory is false":
theorist essaying
rigor essential
...
Torah esterifying

"String Theory":
rigor tenth/test
...
restoring Thy
oyster hint/Ting
sorry eight/hint/Ting
throne grit/sir
roi strength
Tyre shorting/signor

"String Theory of Everything":
theorist enthrone
rigor sovereign/eighteen/Stonehenge/Firestone

...
throne overnighthers/sovereign/fighter
footrest interreign
oystering foreigner
Hin Ting regretter/overseer
Trinity (1115) estrogen/foregone

...
VERIFYING ERYTHROGONE [red blood cell precursor]
theorist Green frothing

"Theory of Everything":
throne thievery/fighter/frothy/verity
verify heterogony/energy

String TOE ... shoelaces; foundations of physics.

...
Judges 7:1; Adoni-bezek [K] severing thumbs and toes of kings.

...
A word is a string of letters.
Aristotle [linguistics] vs Democritus [atomic].

[3/16/25]
"String Theory of Everything is true":
interuniversity gogetters/hotshot
erythrogenesis verifying
intuitiveness gogetter
thoroughness reverifying

...
verifying erythrogenesis/erotogenesis/heterogenous/heterogonies/orthogenesis/outrightness/TESTOSTERONE/
thoroughness
erroneous esterifying/etherifying
ESTROGEN esterifying/etherifying

...
VERIFYING OUTRIGHT (666) RESTORES
theorist Greene horrifying/virtuosity/frothing

[3/25/25]
"String Theory of Everything is false":
OVERGENERALISING horseshit/forfeits/sheriff/THEORIST
integrationist Geoffrey
restorativeness forfeiting/firelight

...
Torah heterogeneity/offensiveness
Torah Sovereign esterifying/etherifying

...
VERIFYING FLIS ERATOSTHENES [Hermes, pole; FALSE]
ERROR FLIS (2522) ANGIOGENESIS [BRANCH]/INVESTIGATES/NEGATIVENESS
negativeness forthrightly/rightest
theorist Greene falsifying/satisfying/gravitons/loathing/visionary

"flisunit at Gmail dot com":
stultification God
God stultification/multinomials
Gaius dictation [anthropologic]
stolid (1211) logician
ANTI * SODOMITICAL

[Ukrainian]
"slusarczuk at alum dot mit dot edu":
DEMOCRITUS DULLS [ATOMIC THEORY, well roundedness]
immaculate lustra/Ursula [ICUCS]
ACADEMIA DOLDRUMS/tortuous
culture automatism/multitasks/studious
RUSSIA allocate/commodate/loculate [break up]/modulate/allotted/attacked/lactated

...
LOCUST ADMIT (2005) automakers/outsmarted/emulator/maltreats/maturest
LOCUST ATOMIZE TRAUMAS
locust Israel matzot
metatarsal tumultuous/lockout/outsold
Romulus autodidact/acidulates/meticulous/coattails/academia

"worst decision in my life":
denicotinise worm

[Aaron, Leviticus 16:8]
"Caesar's great nephew Octavio":
Servant scapegoater

"Abraham's nephew Lot":
alpha menorah

"Alexander's brother James":
marathoner debases [WEED]
embolden harasser/Jaxartes/Earhart/Esther/haters

[False]
"Alexander's younger brother James":
grandmaster erroneous/honourable/honouree
unregenerate ambassador
grandmother reanalyses

"Alexander's nephew James":
repeal axehead
alpha ensnared
weed mannerless
earn Japanese

[No henhouse]
"HaShem El demoted Uncle Sam" (4441):
codename Methuselah
Methuselah McDonald
McDonald Samuel
henhouse deselect

Purim "lot" celebrates Esther
Haman, Hammedatha, ... Hamas

...
"Haman the son of Hammedatha, the Agagite, the adversary of all the Jews, had schemed against the Jews to destroy them, and had cast Pur, that is the lot, to disturb them and destroy them." (Esther 9:24)

...
"Haman the son of Hammedatha":
Nathan Mohammed feast/hates/oaths

...
[Like Arthurian legend,
Morgause and Mordred]
"Haman the son": Nathan

...
[Mohammed ... Hammed]
"Hammedatha the Agagite":
Meta Meta Haggai

...
[Mord ... death Cai K, Esther Easter]
"Mordecai and Esther":
echinodermata [starfish]
costarred Aeneid
Archimedes Aron
Aaron threesided

...
"King Ahasuerus":
Eurasian, Gaussian, Ganesha, Guineas, Krishna, Ukraine, genius, kaiser, Russia, Garik, Gaius, Hagar,
Sarah, Sasha, Khan
Gauss Ukraine
Guinea shark

...
Haman is N
Hammedatha is M
Esther is G
Mordecai is K
Ahasuerus is L

Brutalist Architecture

1. Renaissance Center Detroit
2. Metro Detroit Synagogues
3. Northwestern University Library
4. MIT Student Center
5. Boston City Hall
6. Beckman Mall Caltech

VALUES: VIRTUE VS VICE

Assume the attitude of taking responsibility for understanding how everything works.

Cultivate a lifelong love of learning and achievement.

Scholarship essential not optional.

What you do not know will destroy you. Ignorance is intolerable, accuracy is attractive.

...

Fighting, fornicating, gambling are vices. They exhibit skill, not virtue, yet understanding them is virtuous.

...

"sex drugs and rock and roll":

ungod Aleksandr

Oakland scoundrel/rounder

Michael Moore "the awful Truth"

Americans are sadly OBTUSE.

The Dictator (2012)

Sacha Baron Cohen

DD boob plot ... tits, tithe

priests of Aaron ... Cohen

Rounders (September 11, 1998)

Worm Lester.

Leviticus 19:27, no rounding.

Women suffer when men are emasculated.

Try over regret.

Pit trading is harsh. Manners get better prices.

Acid melts the flesh.

Cows ruminate.

Ideals kill.

Polygamy splinters families.

Consorts burden.

Blame yourself over others.

Honest disagreement is helpful, being mean is not.

Once begun is half done.

Well done over poorly begun.

Speak silently.

Imitation is forceless.

Honor from the dishonored is worthless.

"male": el

"female": feel

[Michelangelo wrong]

"The Man Without a Belly Button":

unemotional Yahweh

[NONMELODIC]

"The Beatles Revolution Nine":

elevate buttonholes/beetroot/Listerine
elevation Hilbert ?
truelove Elisabeth [SHEBA]

John Lennon's No. 9 Coincidences
Born Oct. 9 Liverpool,
Cavern Club on Feb. 9, 1961,
met Brian Epstein Nov. 9, 1961,
The Ed Sullivan Show Feb. 9, 1964,
Etc...;
The Beatles - "Revolution Nine";
John Lennon - "#9 Dream",
4:44 Apple Records,
peaked at #9 Billboard 100,
#23 British singles

"Jordan Georgia Virginia":
vinordinaire roi [alphabetical]
AVERAGING ORDINARII
dragon erring
divine Aaron

[N and G]
"Spyro the dragon and Sparx the dragonfly":
Nathanael pornographers/harpooner
hydrosphere fantasy tornado
Alexander anthropography
Alexander godhood fantasy
Alexander Throop Stanford

[1998 PS1; SHAPIRO]
"Spyro the Dragon":
Shapyro rodent/God
harpooner Syd
Phaeton sorry

"Sparx the dragonfly":
hydroplane/Alexandros/godfather

(Tao 1.1 trans. Legge)
"The name that can be named is not the enduring and unchanging name.":
EMANATE EMANATE EMANATE COUNTERSIGNING BUDDHA
math math math annunciation transcending
authenticate author (emanating mashgiach)/(emanates Michigan)
authenticate author emanating HaShem diadem
GUARANTEE AUTHENTICATE COMMANDMENTS
Ten ten ten ten ten decahedron mashgiach Gandhian
Chan Ho Nam authenticate guarantee/hummingbird
TERENCE TAO MATHEMATICIAN AUGUSTINE
management instruction educate highhanded

(Tao 1.1 by Mitchell)
"The name that can be named is not the eternal Name.":
EMANATE EMANATE EMANATE LORD CHINESE
emanate emanate emanate Christ Lennon
math math math transcendental beanie [Gauss]
Elohim emanate emanate transcendent
emanate mathematical Anderson/betatron/Ebeneser
commandments ten anthranilate [L1]/Hannibal/lantern/linear/tribal
COMMANDMENTS TEN TRIBAL TENET
ten ten ten ten ten ten decimal Abraham Moshe/Omaha
TEN TEN TEN TEN TEN TEN DECIMAL HASHEM ABRAHAM AO
Alisander behemoth teammate annectant
Alisander emanate emanate contentment/becometh
CHAN HO NAM entertainments/embitterment/maltreatment/reinstatement
CHAN HO NAM ENTERTAINMENT BETHESDA [Young and Dangerous]
...
archenemies heathendom/Bethlehem/Mahometan/Manhattan/Nathanael/Madalena
Archimedes boatman anathema Helene
Nathaniel testament boatman endearment/adherence

CHRISTENDOM ANATHEMA ANATHEMA BEETLE

...
TERENCE TAO MATH MATH MATH NATANIEL/AENEID
Terence Tao nemathelminthes enanthemata [worm "Rounders"]
math math math Constantine Albert [Archimedes' Fields medal]

[HYPOTHETICAL !
proposal to Attila the Hun CE 450;
Jordanes chronicles dream of broken bow ... Noah's rainbow?]

...
"Justa Grata Honoria":
Argonaut Torah
JONAH TARTARS/traitor
Jason arthur/guitar/aorta/Torah

"Attila the Hun":
Athena (22) hilt/Tut
Leah titan

"Political drama": calamari plot

Haters love to hate.

Memory loss and brainwashing: difficult to realise you have them.

[July 30, 1986; Nathaniel w. aliens]

...
"Flight of the Navigator":
Leviathan forgot
levitation Torah
Aaron violet/thief

Democracy directly votes vs Republic layers of representatives.
Abolishing a landed aristocracy creates an educated plutocracy, the principle unchanged: who controls
wealth has power.
Judges short circuit wealth.

...
System of government matters less than spiritual quality of people, hence primacy of good education.

Same law in war and peace.
E.g. David and Uriah.

M part Nordic Viking,
hence McDonalds,
Highlander Connor McCloud,
007 Sean Connery,
McDuck

Motion to replace elections with the lie-off.

"Yankee means masturbator."
namesakes betatron

Feminisation can be induced: drugs, plastic additives, pesticides, etc.
Why are almost none of the chemicals androgenous?

[Vasilios Cicero]
"It's all about the key shots, timing."
Messiah bullshitting/buttonholes/institute
Messiah institute ballyhoo/goat
Agosto (4434) Hellenism/Mitsubishi

Employment is the most noble human relationship.

"See Book of Job, Eve's jealousy."
sublessee Josef Jove
Josef Jay bluebook/loves

...
The Mourning Bride, Zara in Act III, Scene II:
"Heav'n has no rage, like love to hatred turn'd,

Nor hell a fury, like a woman scorn'd."

Permutational vs phonetic embedding to verify authorship across range of translations.

[Buddhist/Taoist]

"The Qur'an: A New Translation

Thomas Cleary":

TARSOMETATARSAL ANTHRAQUINONE/ANNUNCIATOR/AUTHORIAL/Nathaniel/Newtonian

tarsometatarsal author cayenne

tarsometatarsal Newton carnelian

metatarsal transequatorial

METATARSAL ANNUNCIATES YAHWEH

charlatanerie harassment/honourless

[Muslim Englishman;

literal melodic]

"The Koran Interpreted

Arthur John Arberry":

PENTAHEDRON ARBITRATOR (222) HUNTER/RUTH

pentahedron authority Teheran/earner

pentahedron heartbroken Ruthie

pentahedron retributory Arther/Athena

Jordan Robinette threatener

[Egyptian, OBE;

deep understanding]

...
"The Qur'an (Oxford World Classics) M.A.S. Abdel-Haleem":

...
MALARIAN SCHOOLTEACHER (2888) SUBLESSOR ALEX [JOBS]

malarian schoolteacher subleases Lord

Malarian schoolteacher female bud

malarian schoolteacher blameless/defrauded/sublessor/emeralds/exoduses/marquess/slalommed

...
excommunicator hellhole reward

...
MESSIAH WORLDBEATER ALESSANDRO/ALEXANDROS

Messiah worldbeater Alessandro cloud

Messiah worldbeater Alexandros

mollusc/shalom/squall/cloud

[Propagates]

"Original sin": signorina il

"Nephilim giants": Philistine

"The Great Flood":

Godel father/earth/Torah

LORD "Goliath".

Alexander world historical record for torture. CRIMELESS.

USA needs spiritual help.

"A powerful and oppressive nation" (Isaiah 18:2)

"divine democratic mandate":

CONTRAINDICATIVE

contraindicate diadem/David

antidemocratic Aeneid/David

INDOCTRINATED ACADEME

interacademic dominated/diamond

revindication teamed

Macedonian meditative/verdict/David

AMERICA VIETNAM NOTICED

"Alexander's greatest mistakes":

regardless statements

Aeneid steals armrest

testament realised

...
Transgress Mikael

Metatarsal denigrates/estranged
Streisand maltreats
Katerine messages
Rattlesnake disagreement
Kleenexes marriage/armrest
Kleenex traitresses/dramatists/mistresses/strategies
eagles exterminates/trendsetters/disesteems/rainmakers

"Nathaniel betraying Alexander":
engineer (2333) Bellatrix
Bellatrix Diana angry

"Actaeon Phaeton": cheapen tattoo

Jason Thessalonian,
Quest for Golden Fleece ... Flis,
"era of Jason": Josef Aaron;
Peleus Argonaut father of Achilles murdered by Medea via lamb in cauldron scheme;
FF8 Edea Kramer,
"Jordan Nosanchuk": Jason donna.

...
"Jason and Medea":
Seaman jaded/Jae
Adam donna/Anne
Jae nosed

...
"Jason and Creusa glauce":
Alessandro Juneau/ganja
GANJA (2220) dracunculoses [guinea worm parasite]/scandalous/scoundrel/cleanser/coalesced/concealed/
cruelness/arsenous/SEDUCER
cleanse dragon/Jordan

XpengX3 15:13 helicopter car

...
https://youtu.be/g9ch8yHthP4?si=_3JJg7t3JW0imSIU

...
"China Has Launched New Generation Transport SHOCKING The US":

...
CONGRATULATION WASHINGTONIAN PUTRESCENCE
Alessandro counterespionagers enchaining/nictating
HEPHAESTUS ALESSANDRO AUTHENTICATION/... counterattacking/interconnecting/incarcerating

...
rounder Hephaestus congregationalist/internationalist/transcontinental
rounder Hephaestus Thessalonian
anticarcinogen/antinarcotic/technocratic

...
Lichtensteiner coconspirated/supersaturating/traitorousness/counteracting/cantharidean/transgressing
LIECHTENSTEINER COCONSPIRATOR AUGUSTAN [X]

PLANNED OBSOLESCENCE.
Detroit automakers' mistake.
Maximize short term profit, accustom people to mediocrity,
go bankrupt long term, making consumers and citizens into cows.

Beating vs helping.

Honor righteousness, respect skill.

Geographic Facts:
Muslim lands are vast, spanning multiple continents; Israel is tiny, the only Jewish state in the world.
Islam prioritises Mecca and Medina, Jerusalem being tertiary, except as a target for radicals.

People care more for results than causes.

Expect the best, prepare for the worst.

BARBARIAN CHRISTIANS WORSHIP LIFE.
Death is a mercy.

...
[Robinette]

"lifetime imprisonment":
feminine imposter/Lottie/spirit

...
Why Christians abolished sacrifice, "psychological pussification":
sociolinguistic alpha
octopus poaching fails/Alfi

[burned alive to keep oath to LORD]
(Judges 11:34)
"Jephthah's daughter":
deathtrap Hugh
HERA UPSTAGED
death haute [Nathan IHES]

Every man a god, God is a worm.

"Chinese water torture":
Harcourt western

"Flat Earth Society":
STATECRAFT HOLE

Easy to feel, hard to think.

...
"Race religion politics":
electric polarising
electrician igloo
gorilla science

...
"Race religion and politics"
electric Indianapolis
railroad nicotinic
peregrination social
gorilla denicotinise

"Americans loathe Alexander":
charlatanerie (666) Adamson/axeman/daemon

VOTING

A large sample loses locality and gains crowd emotionalism.
Statistical convergence toward mean vs gaining covariance.
Myth is voting is best outcome, reality is mostly near average; yet can get exceptional candidates
inducing skew if competence matches salesmanship.
Not a deterministic process.

...
In the USA, representatives, senators, presidents, and lower judges are by aggregate vote.
Only higher judges and cabinet appointees are screened by peers.

Biblically judges are best.
Consider the populism of Absalom vs regal David, both came to ruin.
Cyclical extremes in governance, whereas judges are resistant to horde and corruption of individuals.
"Layers of judges": juryless defog/aged

ANTICATO

System of governance
vs genes and culture
vs external.
Difficult to attribute success, hence legitimate historical debate.

...
Genes vs culture: culture trumps.
Mongols conquered the world, later culturally pacified in Korea.
Germans ravaged the Romans, Hitler had the Reich, later pacified by the Americans.
British Empire now goodwill.

...
Europeans are democratic, similar blood similar culture to USA, dominion ended with feudal colonialism,
unsustainable.
Indians are very democratic, different blood and culture from USA, mediocre chaotic results.
China autocratic, different blood different culture from USA, America's greatest rival.
Japan democratic, similar blood and culture to China, pacified American ally.
Modern Israel covenanted and democratic, similar blood and culture to USA, lagging in education and

research.
Arab democracy ineffective, different blood and culture.

...
Hypothesise external sustaining American dominance.
Conclude singular focus driving Chinese success.

[The truth will set you free.]

...
"AMERICA IS THE BORG":
armchair beets/Bose/bees

...
Star Trek: Seven of Nine E, Borg Queen J. Also The Matrix.

Personal experience wrestling ghost of Nathaniel tempting with alien encounter.

Not only cultural assimilation, but ALIEN TECHNOLOGY. Implausible that democracy alone, a 3000 year old idea, could lead to such dominance.

...
"Alien technology in United States":
authentication sentinelled
nonethicalness antidote/ideology
constitution Athenian
HALLUCINOGEN DETESTATION [brainwashing]
intelligence dishonesty
astonishing Euclidean
GUILTINESS NATHANIEL/ATHENIAN
IDEOLOGY authenticates/antithetical [oppressive]/LICHTENSTEIN [Hitler]/
ANCIENTNESS [democracy]/annihilates/inauthentic/statistical/uncanniness/UNESSENTIAL
Goliath clandestinity/denunciation

...
"worst country in history": constitution

...
"North Atlantic Treaty Organisation":
COLONISATION ATHENIAN
Athenian transatlantic/antirational/colonisation/totalitarian
trinitroglycerin Thanatos/Nathan
Christianity Lateran
TOTALITARIAN CONSTANTINE

"Alexander marries Jordan Nosanchuk":
DENUCLEARISE HORROR

...
Nuclear weapons are poison: they defend nothing but bring ruin to all.
Develop nonapocalyptic arms, pray to never use them.

Justice is impartial to wealth, yet taxation is a collectively allocated power, thus there is no injustice in flat vs progressive tax rates, rather a difference in philosophy.

...
"Debating questions with no answer": brainteasing sententious

CONSERVATIONAL
Social engineering to homogenise races, castes, religions is artificial.
Intermarriage is the exception not the norm. Yet pure blood is an idol.

PRAGMATISM
All men are not created equal:
consider souls, genes, and culture.
Righteousness implies equality under law.
Respecting roots and dreams, create a meritocratic culture:
REAP WHAT YOU SOW.

Free will is partial.

Round out weaknesses, but focus on strengths.

Invest in education: seeing, studying, suffering.

Countries divide by ethnicity.

Mushroom cloud, penis shaped.
Erica Standhart [Cain, E] fungal behavior World War III.

Bhagavad-Gita As It Is, xiv:

...
"the clever Duryodhana challenged the Pandavas to a gambling match"

...
"the gambling, which was rigged, cheated the Pandavas of their kingdom"

...
"Krsna Himself took the role of messenger for the sons of Pandu and went to the court of Dhrtarastra to plead for peace."

...
"Krsna became the charioteer of Arjuna"

...
"Bhagavad-Gita begins, with the two armies arrayed, ready for combat"

...
"World War Three": LORD wrath
"The Revelation to John":
enthroned Elijah

...
[whitehorse, trumpets]
"On the other side, both Lord Krsna and Arjuna, stationed on a great chariot drawn by white horses, sounded their transcendental conchshells." (Gita 1.14)

...
[EIGHTEEN Chapters]
(Gita 1.15)
"Lord Krsna blew His conchshell, called Pancajanya":

YAHWEH ALESSANDRO ALEJANDRO/ALEKSANDR
/ALISANDER
Yahweh Alessandro Aleksandr chincona/Lincoln
Yahweh Alejandro Aleksandr Nicholas

...
YAHWEH ALESSANDRO JORDAN ALLIANCE
ALESSANDRO HEBREW OAKLAND JAPAN CYCLIC
Renaissance Aleksandr halcyon
Yahweh Aleksandr cannabino1 poacher

...
"The Supreme Personality of Godhead said: Time I am, the great destroyer of the worlds, and I have come here to destroy all people. With the exception of you [the Pandavas], all the soldiers here on both sides will be slain." (Gita 11.32)

...
[Yahweh emanated]
"the unborn" (Gita 10.12)

...
[God Most High]
"the unmanifested" (Gita 12.1)

El Paso, Texas. "God walks".
Blue city in red state ... purple
Old West; Q continuum in Star Trek.
UTEP Miners; data mining.
Vladimir Tepes "Dracula",
tEp Xi of Boston purple 22,
UTEP Mongolian architecture, cousin to Native American Indians; also has a Buddhist Temple.
Congregation B'Nai Zion has a pyramid, phone 2222.

...
"as the tortoise draws its limbs within the shell" (Gita 2.58)

...
"What is night for all beings is the time of awakening for the self-controlled; and the time of awakening for all beings is night for the introspective sage." (Gita 2.69)

[Augur means sign; see "Hercules".]

...
Jan. 20, 2024 Trump Inauguration,
MLK Day

...
"Venus Mars Jupiter Saturn Neptune Uranus":
SERVANT TRUMP JANUARIES PRESENT
servant Trump renaissant ensure
servant (4644) supersaturate miner

servant Messiae (802) usurpature/partner/patterns/Atreus [Israel]
servant instrument Japanese
Ser (5555) reinstatement/unremunerative

EMOTIONALISM

Hating adversaries is folly.
Truth and righteous judgement imply seeing the good in everyone.
Haters are easy to control and defeat.

Generational age difference.
Adam's sons were Cain and Abel.
Abraham's nephew was Lot.
Caesar's adopted son Octavio.

...

"The LORD possessed me at the beginning of His way" (Proverbs 8:22)
"Abraham My friend" (Isaiah 41:8)

[Arthurian: Morgause and Mordred; M's neighbor is Gauss]
"Nataniel mother": Marianne [Abel]

"Morgause and Arthur" (3335):
Amadeus Arthur/Utahn
rounder Gautama
DRAGON HAUTE

"Jordan Nosanchuk vassal Nathaniel":
voluntariness Oakland

Breakfast at Tiffany's is a nonideal "two swords" situation starring J and Y [library catalog]. Must see !

Liberty is mental. How can the ignorant bring freedom?

[Q duked, Heart intact "aortal";
See Ezekiel 22:22]
"Thich Quang Duc": thigh quad

Loose basketball metaphors:
Michael Jordan #23 [J],
Scottie Pippen #33 [Peregrine, ... Pippen in LOTR, K],
Dennis Rodman #91 ["the Worm" - Triton in Little Mermaid, Flis L ... B],
Kobe Bryant #8, 24 [Ko, Octavio, K],
Lebron James #23, initially Cleveland Cavalier [James, K]

[Black hole]
Christianity is singular, mythology is manifold.

LA is Alexander's dreams made real in movies and science.
"Garden of Eden, in flames":
Armageddon Flis

...

Caltech JPL ... JL

Living fossil, chased by destroyer.
Most of Alexander's relatives are not only dead families but also dead civilizations:
Egypt Pharaoh - destroyed
Ephraim David - destroyed
Greece Atreus - destroyed
Russia Nevsky - destroyed
Japan Hideyoshi - destroyed
France Louis - destroyed
Etc.

SUGAR PILL SNAKE OIL

Travis sold the West sugar pill snake oil, betraying their heritage and future to China, impersonating and scapegoating Alexander.

Good men live to old age.
VS
Only the good die young.

[Cohen, ... cozen, cozy]

[Imprecise paraphrase Isaiah 49:5]

"Second Pskovian Chronicle":

handpick convincer

princeliness Hancock/cacao

CHAPERON POACHES

All different:

haunted vs cursed vs damned.

Curse of David:

for sparing the life of a murderer and adulterer, an eternal curse.

Your wives will long for other men and the sword shall never leave your house.

Bathsheba David's wife: Queen of Sheba "bitch" in Korean, birdbath.

Alexander God-damned to Sheol for unwitting disobedience; LORD did not speak.

Alexander challenged for Adam's compelled transgression, haunted by Michael and Nathaniel, wife swapped by James and Michael.

Freewill is limited: associates are punished for your sins.

E.g. Jordan Oakland not entirely responsible for being rotten apple.

Fear is the worst enemy, the most powerful. There is nothing to fear.

"Universalism vs regionalism" and

"Ideologic crusade vs balancing books"

are the essence of the current wars.

"Two wrongs do not make right":

integrator Kong

demotion gorgon/Agosto

Ko demonstrating/warmongering/wrongdoing/stewarding

Washington doom

"Righteousness does not negate transgression.":

heterogeneousness integration dragon

erroneousness integration death

[FYI CIA]

International regional dialing codes:

USA +1, China +8

"an apple rotten to the core" (2300):

Penelope attractor/Actaeon/crooner

harpooner tentacle

phaeton penetrator/copartner

[How is J Job/Jeremiah/Euler so enchanted with Esau, and why is Ginny so relatively intelligent??

If Alexander abused, why not J?]

...

"Jordan pothead":

DEODORANT JAP

RHODANATE [cystic fibrosis]

JATROPHA DONE

[J atrophy, Jatropha Augusta? Cathartica?

Poison e.g. ricin, prevents triadic alphabet protein translation]

...

Aaron doped/hoped

pardon death

harpoon jaded/jae

Phaeton Dad

JONAH DOTARD [Biblical truth]

Noah adopter

throne Jap

...

Throop Dean/Jae

tornado PhD

dehorn data/toad

"James child abuse"(1878):

DISABLES ACE/JAE

Elijah amuses/caused/based/bused
Judah malice
Michael Judas
Amadeus lies
Scheme jails
Judaism bleaches
Ace Messiah
Humble acid
Deus Malachi

...
"child abuse": disable

"Eight hours of work per day":
Fishhook daguerrotype/retrograde
FREDERIK HOGWARTS/southpaw/author/THROOP/Torah/yahoo/Shay
SHAPIRO OUTWORKED/forgery/outgrow
OUTGROW HYDROSPHERE

..
REWARD RIGHTEOUS/fighter/fishhook/porosity/trophies/upright/highest/profits/thigh
reward THROOP foggy/keys

"Eight hours of work a day":
RIGHTEOUS WORKDAY
Autoworkers Idaho
graduater fishhook
Yahweh autogiros/auditor/rigorous
Yahoo authorised/farsighted/godfather/righteous/outrages/worthier
Agosto keyword

...
Reward FISHH00K/goatish/Agosto/thigh/yahoo/auto/Fiat

"Five hours of work per day":
reward Prokofiev/poorhouse/pushover/viperous/sheriff

"Five hours of work a day":
deify Kurosawa
Yahoo fireworks
Harvard fief/keys/wife/wise
Savior woodruff/defray/yahoo
Kay overshadow
Ieyasu hardwork

...
reward oafish/Shiva/Yahoo

"Isaac swapping Jacob Esau metaphor":
ACCURATENESS ISAIAH
autobiographic Japanese
chaperon scapegoatism
marijuana scapegoat/sabotage

"Now the first came forth red, all over like a hairy garment; and they named him Esau."
(Genesis 25:25)

...
"and Esau said to Jacob, 'Please let me have a swallow of that red stuff there, for I am famished.'
Therefore his name was called Edom [red]." (Genesis 25:30)

How to knock out Ol' Nick? Hit him in the stomach.
Who puts stock in godless men?
Faith drives behavior.
Bitcoin eating the dollar alive?

ALEXANDER DISLIKES POLITICS.
Politics dislikes Alexander.

...
Good policy is timeless.
People vote with every purchase.
Spend energy on results.

"Political drama": calamari Lot/pot/dot

Intelligence is entrenched.

6.001 MIT Scheme Lambda Calculus. Also C++ = B.

"The Revelation to John":

LEVOROTATION

...

Enthroned Elijah/Lotto

Veto Johnathon/Lionheart/Lantern

Lionheart TNT

lantern thief

Oiler Johnathon/heathen/tattoo

tattoo Elinore/Lenin

Lenin tattooer/Jehovah

JENNI ELEVATOR

eneration Lotto

Torah violent/toilet/violet

Jehovah retention

throne elevation/Helvetian

JOVE ANTOINETTE

X-Men: Beast, Wolverine, Jean Grey, Etc.

NYC: N&Y's City

[Vicing Yahweh by GT and spirits;

in film Arthur-Jordan is best;

want to sabotage by killing Jordan.

Also M, L part Mongolian, different from Manchurian, slandering J.]

...

["Erica Standhart": Catharine, ... Cathai or China]

"The Manchurian Candidate"(2004):

Cantharidate machine

Archimedean antacid/Nathan

...

Director JONATHAN Demme

...

"Raymond Prentiss Shaw":

MESSIAH PORTRAYS

TORAH DISPENSARY

steward hypnosis/nymphs [G,E]

password (1101) tyrannise/Riemann/Yasmine/Ishtar

EMANATION PHD

Samson handwrites/tradership/wardenship

smith Anderson/Odyssean

pardon swartheness/trashiness/hastiness/smartness

Windsor (1211) harassment/spymaster/ashtrays

PYRE WORDSMITH

Nimrod (1111) sharpness/shysters

shadow tyranniser

...

VERSUS

...

"Alexander marries Jordan Nosanchuk":

Manchurian Oakland serenaders

...

"Alexander unifies physics at Michigan":

Manchurian acidifying shapeliest

Squall Leonheart has a gunblade.

"New Testament is constructed":

Newton underestimates

awesomeness (333) uncredit/ruined

"Old Testament is truth":

AUTHOR MENDELIST [XY digital]

LOT ANTITHESIS

demonstrates Tut

lionhearted Tut

Messiah Lord Tut
Messiah turtle
atheists undoer
Deus isothermal/monetarist/Aristotle/lionheart/antihero/horseman/Alister/menorah/mineral/monster/thrones
Detroit astutest/humanest/unseals

The word of the Lord is unchanging.

Luminaries speak for themselves, but the LORD will repay sin.

James Bond is the octet rule for covalent molecules.

"Judas Iscariot and Jesus" (4440):
adjudication assure
Icarus (1111) astounded
Direction Judas
direct assassin
disunite cross/sodas
Jordan discusses/justices/assisted/suicide
suicide astounds
ASSISTED DINOSAUR/JORDAN

"Judas Iscariot and Jesus of Nazareth":
authorisation sacredness/assurance

Abraham and Isaac (N, son) echoes Judas and Jesus (G, daughter).

[Never recovered from trauma]
"Isaac ben Abraham and Isaac Newton":
Smithson Rebecca Diana
cannabis Christendom
cowardice Nathan amnesia
brand machination/chaoticness
omniscience reward

Constantine (2005).
"God and the devil made a wager"

...
Cancerous cough mirrors LORD signalling Jordan's attraction via itchy throat, supervising Georgia's 24/7
torture.

Pattern is possession and sabotage of Alexander, likewise of Jordan, likewise torture and war instigation.

UK is +44; In Chinese 4 is death, whereas 8 is good fortune. (?)

[vs Alexander scholar]
Chief executive officers are metaphorical killers.
Murder is evil, breaks 10X.

"Cursing, Privacy": Icarus prying [N]
Silly J, reprove privately, N agitating.
RELATIONSHIPS SHOULD HOLD WATER.

...
"And Ham, the father of Canaan, saw the nakedness of his father, and told his two brothers
outside" (Genesis 9:22)

..
"So he said,
'Cursed be Canaan;
A servant of servants
He shall be to his brothers.' "
(Genesis 9:25)

"What is holy?": Yah (111) owlsh
[Expand precise list of holy vs not.]

...
In the Torah, the firstborn were initially sanctified to the LORD [Exodus 13:2], changed to the sons of
Levi [Exodus 3:12], as the cost of the Passover.

Rule, judgement, and education require trust. Heaviest scrutiny falls on hard power, the soft power of
education disdained but most influential in the long run.

"Radicals are halogens,":
Herc Alessandro/Lordliness/signaller/analogies
paired with CATions:
Lithium Li+ (Lilith, antidepressant), Sodium Na+, Potassium K+.

ISRAEL ETHNIC TRIBE ACCEPTS CONVERTS.
vs KKK or Ku Klux Klan? Or Hamas?

Octavio uses multipronged attack.

Divide and conquer the West.
Conquer by corrupting morals.
Cruelty is not a virtue.
Americans are liars.
Healthy culture attracts (2232).

Preference for religious interbreeding.
Hybrids are vigorous.
Typically loyalty follows blood.
Demolish myth of pure blood.
Jews are mixed.

Ashkenazi Jews: Hebrews intermarried with peoples of Ukraine and Russia, later Germany.
Turks have link to Japanese.

...
[Intelligent and formidable]
Scythians (ancient Eastern Iranic equestrian nomadic people), skythikon (putrified snake venom arrows),
apokuthizein (scalping).

...
Scythian (230) [Jordan]
Scythian Khazars (1001) [Maude]

...
Kazan, Tatarstan, Russia,
Russian: казán, 'boiler' or 'cauldron',
flag crowned dragon,
Russian Зилант, Tatar yılan/елан, namesake of Elon Muskovitz,
myth of stink of burning snakes.

...
St. Basil's ... base of the Intercession, by Tsar Ivan IV, commemorates capture of Kazan.
Manifold bonfire candy cane J style, also bulbous, seed, Cid, Lord.

...
"Can you draw out Leviathan with a fishhook?" (Job 41:1)
"Out of his nostrils smoke goes forth,
As from a boiling pot and burning rushes." (Job 41:20)
"He makes the depths boil like a pot" (Job 41:31)

...
Noah->Japheth->Gomer->Ashkenaz
(Genesis 10:1-3, 1 Chronicles 1:4-6)
[Chronicler Nathan reborn Lenin]

...
"Blow a trumpet among the nations!
Consecrate the nations against her,
Summon against her the kingdoms of Ararat, Minni and Ashkenaz;
Appoint a marshal against her"
(Jeremiah 51:27) [Jae, Trump]

Hypocrisy:
Teach market efficiency, meanwhile export wealth.
Teach Jesus Christ, meanwhile slowly consolidate power.
Teach ideals, have them destroy society, meanwhile practice reality.
[Target youth: K-12, also N's FF7.]

Who sold out America to China?
Richard NIXON

vs
[Richard the Lionhearted,

...
Leonhard Euler or Jordan J
Richard Phillips Feynman Y

FF8 Squall Lionheart
SOT Richard and Kahlan

...
Richard Lamb CK CS,
Richard Florka steel trader DYC]

"Christianity buries the truth in mythology."
countersignatures (222)

...
In Arthurian legend, there is adulteress Guinevere and bastard Mordred.

...
In Greek mythology, Cupid promotes Chaos.

...
The Hebrews have Adam and the Snake helping cherub death.

...
22 is the alphabet, the cradle of the West.

"duty and respect misguided":
underestimate cupid
masterpiece studying

Charm helps evade justice.

Antibacterials are not loving.

Guard against contentment.
Life being good enough is a mental yoke, requisite to enslavement, for sharp pain necessitates change.
The sleep of death is complacency: having your livelihood outsourced.
[Joshua: "Everything is fantastic."]

Women like guitars because tones mirror their subtlety of emotion.

Alexander the Great of Macedon:
Soul of West vs East
Greek City States vs Persian Empire
States: Thessaly, Thrace, Macedon, Arcadia, etcetera. Cities: Athens, Sparta, Corinth, Megara, Etc. (&c)

...
Oliver Cromwell parallel, curbing the absolute power of monarchies.
Why his corpse should have been burned on a pyre: decapitated head on display for 30 years.

...
Alexander's idealist mistake was not interbreeding. Religious and cultural differences are very difficult for ordinary men, led to collapse.

"Medieval Ages": evil damages
Why were Medieval Ages ignorant, cruel, and filthy? Christianity.
The Romans built baths in England.

"Efficient Market Hypothesis":
antichrist tipoff
perfection mistakes/faithes
mistake theoretic fishy
reminisce payoff

Letter vs Spirit: detaching words from their meaning.

There is value in ease of communication. Yet multilingualism promotes IQ, and preserves culture and religion.

X ... President Xi vs Joseph

[King Arthur ... General Douglass MacArthur]
"English worldwide": whirlwind Godel

"Chinese worldwide":
SWINE LORDED
weed crowned/silicone
oiler decides

QUALITY SELLS ITSELF !

The American Borg similar to the Russians.

Best countries in the world to raise children: Finland, Japan. Why??

1. Tribal.
2. Education and culture valued.
3. Not targeted by K like Israel.

[Collusive child abuse]

Mothers are intuitive about their children. That M was unaware of extensive abuse at IC is absurd. She induced traumatic hour long OCD toothbrushing.

Rather Ukrainian culture is notorious for jealous sabotage.

[Hermaphrodites destroying my life: typically hateful wrath is Michael, false reasoning Nathaniel, serotonin and lust Georgia.]

"The Epistle of Small to the Americans":

MICHAEL SOMATOTHERAPIST
Themistocles impersonate

"Alexander liberates the word nigger": worldbeater interreign

A sailing mistake can be fatal, a lax hammer stroke crippling. Treat people with the same care and be blameless, for they have longer memories and are more dangerous.

Appreciation of Consequence:

A doctrine of profligate mercy is a seductive yet immature siren's call. It reflects neither the reality of life nor the nature of God. Consider, cowardice at key points will destroy your life irreparably, David is accursed perpetually over Uriah.

Akin to the fall of Adam, people overstep. Morality was established by the LORD, it is not for people to reinvent. Children are not entitled to their parents laurels.

The CIA will knife you in the back, then blame you for crying out.

Discrediting is preferred over disappearance, creating mental health problems the gold standard.

Office Space (1999) Apt. 222
[see Milton's "Paradise Lost"]

Pivotal points in life: religion, school, marriage. Something feels wrong, it is wrong.

...

A moment of courage over a lifetime of regret.

ZOMBIE APOCALYPSE:

Homes destroyed are rebuilt, lives lost are reborn. Not to justify evil, but attend substance over spectacle. The real travesty is lifelong human suffering, the living dead zombies of the modern world, and the horror they inflict on nature.

Lies and abuse create lifelong unwitting prisoners and slaves, dependants who then defend the system that debilitated them.

Aeneid attacks the mind not the body at its most vulnerable point in childhood, where the wounds are concealed, most difficult to heal, and seemingly character deficits.

The literal imprisonment of Christian justice is a metaphor for the real imprisonment of the mind.

MIT is Leninist in spirit, architecture, and philosophy. The idol of "one dome to rule them all", the universal best education. True to its Soviet roots, its standard is high.

It serves a useful function, culling a herd of fools using prestige. That brutalism improves education is a relativist fallacy, like saying that infidelity improves marriage. Personal attention and happiness in study improve education.

...

"MIT is hell", where the demons aggregate: Sadoway, Rasputin, Travis, Cain, etc.

MIT students literally set themselves on fire, and corpses from suicide are left to rot.

...

Concrete evidence is:

1. Librarian N's course numbers
2. MIT vs Caltech anagrams in Permutations 3.

*Corrupt character lose soul.

"Americans are barbarians.":

renaissance rabbi

[Women beat men]
"emotional violence":
neocolonial
clementine viola
Lenin Octavio
Milton Evaleen

*You feel when something is wrong.

[confused;
names rockets after cocks: Falcon (K), Dragon (N), everything X]

...
"Elon Muskovitz":
evolution [false]
Milton Zeus [Office Space]
MOLEST ZION/UNO
soviet monk/uno
Ko unmolest/envious/moisten/violet/stolen

[United States]
"worst country in history":
constitution showy
Christ tourist/sorrow/Triton/irons
trinity unworthy [verifies phrasing]

[Georgia Travis]
"worst person in history":
serotonin sophistry/worships
honeypot insists
shyster positron/proton
tortoise hypnosis/prison/sonship

Names are occupational.

[primary schoolteacher conspiracy at Immaculate Conception; Ursala, courtesy of James Ko.]
Alla Kopacz [Russian "gravedigger"] nee Schustov [Russian "clever"]
son Zenon Kopacz "Nick"
[Russian Jewish childhood friend]

Jalalabad Market 12500 Klinger St.,
[J-alala-bad, ... J-Allah-bad]
Physical evidence of Michael's sabotage, very fishy.

[Virginia: A0, Yom Kippur]
Sell people cheaply, they are worthless to you.

[New holy Land]
"Jews in maze of Manhattan":
Newton anathema

Musk's X represents ferryman for colonisation of Mars.

Donbass ... Don Bass; like Oct. 8 Israel, related to demineralisation.

If truth and righteousness are foremost, what of an adversarial trial system?
Exonerating guilt is evil; noting the good in the guilty merits clemency.

Free will is partial; the LORD causes things to be.

[Cereal bowl is weed, adult milk]
"I am the fruitloop of eternity":
metaphor infertility/Nefertiti/unfertilized/felinity/Elinore/felonry/trefoil/trinity/uterine/Orient/rotten/
Tiffie/*Triton*

...
promotion faithful/fatherly/hilarity/tartuffe/tutelary/Harley/turtle/Alfie

...
[see "The Devil's Advocate" ovaries, also Trump Tower.]

"An apple for an apple."
[J appalling]

Hanukkah (Hakka) is superior to Xmas because there are 8 days.

Purim (Esther), Easter is for Jesus.

Notable Israel attacked on 8 fronts, "octopus": Netanyahu AIJAC 11/27/24.
Gaza war began Oct. 7... 8.

"Alexander trains Greco Roman":
recondensation regal
centenarian dogears
centenarian Lord Omega
reannexation damocles

Alpha vs Beta is base, it represents mammalian primal dominance. Why there was no real Beta, it is so profoundly insulting.

"In God We Trust"

LORD suggested Jordan, therefore Alexander's preference is Jordan.

Alexander will marry Virginia if Jordan refuses; and if Jordan accepts he does not think it fair to leave Virginia childless at her age after waiting for me.

There is a modern bias that men are always the villains; it is contrary to Biblical experience and reality.

Boys get blamed as girls connive.

"Grinch begat Yoda": Georgia yacht

Yame (stop), Yama (death), Yamato (Japan)
Stop signs around the world, universalised octagonal red.
Rolling vs stationary stop.

Nikko Japan (Tokugawa), 'Ol Nick, Niccolo Machiavelli, Phoenicia (boatman)

...
James's double [Slippery]
"Nicolino Locche": Niccolo Cohen
(117-4-14 draws)

...
Losses notable:
10. Vicente Milan Derado PTS [M]
66. Abel Laudonio PTS [Cain ... Kay]
124. Alfonso Frazer UD [Alfy]
129. Antonio Cervantes RTD [Don Quixote, for Antonius]
...
[Need rules.]

Aleksandr Aleksandrovich Karelin (887-2) "Monster"
[887 Harcourt, Karl Gauss neighbor, 887 is prime]
[NASB1977 p. 887 (Luke 14:5) "Which one of you shall have a son or an ox fall into a well, and will not immediately pull him out on a Sabbath day?"]

Jordan's double is Audrey Hepburn.

...
"Paris When It Sizzles": 1:16:00 references Captain Ahab of Moby Dick, bait at end of hook [J].

...
"Sabrina" has James, Ginny, Jordan, and Alexander as the goldfish; David and Linus Larrabee w. cane and gravedigger references, borrowing David's automobile, Linus desiring a plastics merger.

"Corrupting character is insidious":
Christianisation usurper
Augustinians despotic
antichrist (4464) conspiracies
supersaturation Grinch

Alexander's grievances against James this lifetime by proxy:

1. IC child abuse for 8 years, Principal Ursula
2. Family infiltration, grandmother Baba is Michael, denigrates mother
3. Setup with K's wife Virginia

4. Stalked by Nathan, drugged and lobotomised
5. Isolated by Georgia Travis, 6 years torture, slander, rape
6. Sabotaged by Michael, lose wife
7. Sabotaged by Nathan, branded
8. Sabotaged by Nathan, wife ravaged by Esau (Johnathan)
9. Instigation of war in Israel 8/8/24
10. Communization of Russia, Lenin is Nathaniel; Cold War.

[Kay ... Kain swine behavior]

Octavio was spiritually allied with Cato in the Catiline Conspiracy, later murdering Caesar in *cold blood*, and transformed the Roman Republic into an Empire. His descendants did not vindicate his avaricious misjudgement; their names are infamous.

Notably Caesar was assassinated supporting the martial Roman culture, as Alexander was betrayed defending the liberty of countries worldwide, including China.

Despite his victories, Octavian is notably absent from Plutarch; the ancients distinguished between honor and success.

How many positions in a war? Four.

Red, Blue, Neither, Both.

Einstein's light beams go both ways, relative morality; whereas Alexander is neither.

e.g. Athenian Xtianity vs Marx-Leninism. [Potential WWII]

Jihad vs Populism. [Israel]

To risk nuclear war over marginal territory is insane, especially from a position of moral weakness.

Nuclear arms permit anyone to go all-in for the whole world, a highly unstable equilibrium. They should be eliminated altogether.

NATO is colonialist, and the US is Biblically "powerful and oppressive", "Goliath" from the LORD'S mouth, The Borg. Russia and China are more authoritarian and feudalistic.

Spectral decomposition of governments: populism, authoritarianism, feudalism, aristocracy, plutocracy, judges.

Types and measures of liberty:

incarceration rehabilitation, educational and economic mobility,

to incorporate, jurisdictional, movement, speech, of information, from espionage, from interference, to life and death.

"Legacy of Kain: Soul Reaver"

[Reap what you sow.]

"World War Three":

Dorthee raw

trader whore/lore

retard hero

See the Spice Girls on plurality.

"Wrath and cowardice display lack of self control":

dandelion catholic crackpot

Hong Kong Film:

Young and Dangerous.

"You will burn My Flesh on a pyre. I am the LORD."

Mercy as a weapon creates spineless worms.

From personal experience, the spiritual authors of the New Testament are hypocritical; for all their advocacy of mercy, they are lacking therein. Anything under the sun to destroy Alexander. They dispense but do not swallow the Kool-aid of James Jones.

Undeserved clemency deprives people of instruction and justice; leaving the possibility of clemency or expiation can inspire redemption.

Consider if the transgression is reversible.

Fear as a weapon creates drones.

MIT employs a brutalist evolutionary philosophy toward education, like its architecture. Mentorship empowers people.

Christianity combines morality with sophistry, prophesy with false reference; the product then impedes truth by loyalty.
The truth will set you free.

[Adaptation falsely extended to changing number of chromosomes]
"Evolution is false":
elevation soul/Flis
lifeline auto
Lot evilness/foulness/vileness/elusive/envious/felines

...
"Evolution is true":
Lot virtuous
truelove snout

"Win a battle lose the hearts of men.":
honorableness helmet/Alfie

Ignorance is a defense not an excuse. (See Adam.)

[MIT Math course 18, Physics 8]
"Mathematics is the Queen of the Sciences":
Messiah omniscience
Massachusetts enticement/nicotinic

Abortion.
1. Cellular life begins at conception.
2. Takes two to tango; both parents have rights to children.
3. Inappropriate relations.

...
What is "inappropriate", and who decides?

King James Bible,
Koren Tanakh with no Messiah,
Koran "God splits souls" catholic.

...
NASB 1977 vs revision ISBN 888.

Christian axiom abolishes the Law,
corollary is kings are above it.
Ruling style Augusto and Tokugawa.

Do little boys like Barbie dolls?
Do little girls like trucks?

Georgia and Nathan are mentally ill.

Brawling is beating, boxing is timing. Like a kind word, a proverb, or a joke.

Rumination is chewing cud. Revisiting memory causes pain; ceasing revisiting or erasing the memory stops the pain. Alternatively reframe the memory; change your attitude about it.

The Shawshank Redemption:
a refute of Christian ideals.
Old men are unequal to young.
Men are unequal to women.
A woman's touch is sorely lacking.
Death is often kinder than extended imprisonment.
Aggressive sodomy is barbaric.

Beyond a beat down, the purpose of abuse is to denature. As one fly ruins a jar of ointment, the psyche remembers insults.

FF7
"Sephioth": shepiro... Shapiro
"Jenova": Jae
"Sephioth and Jenova":
Phaethon Jordan

...
Jenova's head:
MADE IN HONG KONG

ALL RIGHTS RESERVED 1996
SQUER COMPANY LIMITED

[Not a Jew, see Ezekiel 22:22]
"Alexander the Hebrew":
hexahedral renew

Pornography ruins lives.

Backstabbing is gay.
Why we have holy oaths, invoking the witness and wrath of God.

"Swine eat their own excrement":
Antichrist Newton
enthronement (555) Crist

Human life is extremely fragile.

"Life begins at conception."
Napoleon geneticist/scientific

"God judges man not vice versa":
Sovereign Sadducean
recondense Judaism/gaius
Actaeon demonises

"The most savage animal is man":
Lamentation Messiah

"Reap what you sow." Torah Aesop
"Jordan": dragon ... dragon
"Job and Jeremiah": JORDAN JAE
"Nebuchadnezzar and Nebuzaradan":
Buddha Aberdeen Canaan

(Illiad 19.261-63)
"that I have laid no hand upon the girl Briseis":
trinitrotoluene Bangladeshis [12450 Klinger]
dandelion authoritativeness alibi
dandelion librarian Hephaestus

...
"I have laid no hand upon the girl Briseis":
highhandedness reprobation
honourableness revalidating/highlander
dandelion librarian SETUP

"Evil will not deliver those who practice it." (Ecclesiastes 8:8)

Chinese saying - 出污泥而不染.

Describes the Lotus, which often grows in muddy water, but emerges untainted by the mud.

Consider what it takes to attract a woman, all the usual stimuli work, generating contempt in a man the same as ass 'n titties in a woman. "Would she love me had I nothing?"

...
How would she treat me with the face of a demon? Homeless?
How would she treat me with my soul at her mercy? My power?
Seemingly.

[Political incorrectness has truth.]
National Characters:
America ... Erica (E); masculine women, backstabbing.
China ... Hin Ting (K); heterosexual matriarchy. Also Phoenicia.
Italia ... Tali (G); drama, matriarchy.
Ukraine or Ruthenia ... Kain, Ruth (E, M); backstabbing matriarchy.
Hindia ... Virginia (Y); patriarchy, gypsies.
Japan ... Jordan (J); patriarchal, nasal.
Israel (L); originally patriarchy, now shadow matriarchy, scholars.

"The devil's greatest trick was convincing the world he didn't exist."
Catholicisation Christening weediness regretted

Jordan [N]: truelove sweetheart, now a pothead sniffing for weed.

Virginia: honest love, deep history, fear of abandonment like Ishmael.

Georgia: means well, but sex and drama are incompatible, both our lives hell. Entertainment industry.

"Yucatan Peninsula":
Cataline, Nataniel, analyst
NATANIEL ANUS

...
Calamity, Cali, Baal, Ball, Asteroid, disaster, Astarte, Asherah, Hera
Traces of Ruthenium
Metaphorical extinction of Hebrews
Adam Tyrannosaur

...
Similar pattern of behavior from N in Solomon's shadow, Caesar's assassin, Lenin, Jesus.
Also wrt Alexander, as N wants marriage to Cain or Travis to kill his soul, which would provoke WWII.

Parsi dakhma, Buddhist self immolation see Jeremiah 7,8.
Not an ordinance or prohibition.

If 8 Mile made Eminem, James Ko made Alexander by instilling insatiable discontent in my soul.

Sexual metaphor for gender relations: men do the work, and can only ejaculate once.

[Jordan's PlayStation]
Las Vegas idea: gambling on games of higher skill versus shearing masses.
Jackpot in the Excalibur basement.
e.g. video games are huge worldwide, always fresh.
Attracting deeper pool, combine education and gambling for happier customers.
My cut is 10%, Biblical tithe.

Tattoos break covenant, thus weaponised on Holocaust victims.

Drug analogs:
Krokodil (desomorphine), Leviathan
Weed, dandelion
Cocaine, Ko
Nicotine, Ol Nick
Heroin (diacetylmorphine), hero
LSD, acid, Flis

[Incomplete ...]
Lord of the Rings (LOTR):

"Gandalf and Balrog":
ALF dragon
"Gandalf and Balrog of Morgorth":
Alamogordo fandango
Alamogordo Lord Nathan

[??? Incomplete]
LORD:
"You will burn My flesh on a pyre."
unremorseful playboy
polymerise unlawful

"You will burn My flesh on a pyre. I am the LORD."
foreordainment hyperbola

Consent vs need; need is nebulous.
E.g. Ruth had need, Boaz did not.
Boaz close relative of Naomi, yet no obligation (legal need) toward Ruth.

"Righteous polygamy requires consent."
retrogression Clementius/speculation/cautiously
miraculousness peregrine/eighteen/potter

[Generally best to avoid fornication, Darwin, dragon, Victor ... Hermes, messenger. Apologies.]

...

[Deuteronomy 22:28 setup]

"Wife Jordan Consort Virginia":

wrongdoer Iscariot/Octavian

Octavio (2222) dignifies

Crist (1887) foreordaining/DARWINIAN/Wagnerian/wardening/woodgrain/wrongdoer

deification warrior/Sargon/Savior

wardening FORNICATOR/VICTORIAN/Iscariot/Francis

avianise cornrowing/doctoring/crowning

...

DRAGON VERIFICATION

nicotinise woodgrain

warden fornication

"Christians worship monogamy":

Romanisation myopic

Romanticism prognosis

Shapiro Corinthians

CORONATION MASHGIHIM/Issiah/Miriam

On Marriage.

Concentration vs Pollination.

One man one wife, consort limit two with honest consent to preserve conjugal rights.

Marriage is not unbreakable.

...

Harlots coo. Bastards usurp;

e.g. Mordred and Arthur, using the vitality of excellent men against them.

Pollinating is unattractive, and parasitic consorts destroy families.

US Supreme Court: Flis vs US Gov

Men are not possessions, and neither are women. Marriage and consortship are contracts.

Why should a woman's pride be attached to exclusive possession of a man? Is the wife belittled by a consensual symbiotic consort?

Limited polygamy does not impede conception or rearing of children, so what cause for offense?

Are consorts only for need, or is respect of love legitimate, as with Ruth and Boaz, or David and

Abigail? This is not greed or lust.

Marianna is my mother, Sarah my second mother. Both were my wives, the finest women I have ever known, I will not part with them. Are they jealous? Does anyone take offense at my loving them both?

Christians assume polygamy is sexual gluttony a la Solomon, which monogamy aims to restrict, creating a trail of single mother X's.

Polygamy splinters families, but are there there not cases where limited splintering is best?

Suffering comes from the idolatrous illusion of possession and jealous pride attached to it, also from the idol of equivalence.

Women are equally important, the biological and behavioral asymmetry of consorts does not change this fact.

Men assume added responsibility and fight Christian social stigma; should they not be respected not demonised for fruitfully multiplying?

Implicit shadow matriarchy.

...

Biblically blessed polygamy highlighted in the book of Ruth: Rachel and Leah, Tamar and Judah, Ruth and Boaz. Forced circumstances, raising up deceased brother's wife, honest love.

Also consider the Muslims's male population obliteration in war.

Bible has two column format, Phaeton Testament should be standard page format.

[Sodomize people in their own homes: connive, rape, torture.]

America, Erica, CIA, Cain, China

Nathaniel (886) stalks Alexander, trying to connive him to Christianity.

"CIA stands for Cain up your butt":

Tyrannosaurus factoid/acidic/tactic/cubit/idiot

Sodomy is a curse.

A natural divergence from the mean that is filthy and has no reproductive function, only pleasure. A gay couple is unequal to a heterosexual marriage: cannot naturally reproduce, do not have the gender behavioral archetypes to raise emotionally healthy children.

"Sow deceit reap distrust."
supersecret Taoist

An adversary in youth is as fluoride for the tooth.

Interest is not interesting.

Dominance is not domineering.

Universalisation and relativity are dubious.

Feminist hypocrisy personifies the behaviors they would curtail, unjustly blaming men of today for the collective hypothetical sins of their forefathers.
Feminism is hysteria.

Prefer the LORD's esteem to the masses', likewise the respect of righteous and honorable people.

On Jordan
[Job, Anne Frank Dutchwoman]:
Feminine emotionality and pride with limited understanding.
Retaliatory.
A puppet, why she loves puppies.
Nosy sniffing around.
Bites the hand that feeds her.
Heathenism. Very sensitive.

...
Tragically targeted and corrupted as the weakest link for having loved Alexander.
Targeted by G via apple,
Targeted by K via M and Job.

Plato's Allegory of the Cave:
Having spent four millennia in rebellious delusion, does J leave?
Does living pinata Alexander accept the delusion of Christianity? No.

Most women are not Dutch, they are taught they ought to be. Neither are most men.

Finding truth and righteous judgement is like a jigsaw puzzle trial; no one has all the pieces.

Torture is self defeating.
Borg trade humanity for power.

[NO DRAGOONING]
Polygamy: permission vs need. Need hard to define: physical, cultural, emotional, etc.
Even with need, require permission.
Permission without need acceptable. Honest need increases likelihood of permission, also Biblically necessity is blessed.

LORD:
"Polygamy splinters families":
ILLEGALISE MATRIMONY/Romanists
PLAYMATE PERMISSION/MISPRISON

...
FALSENESS IMMORALITY
asymmetry signifies
impales profeminists
impalement gorilla
Romanism pitiless
legislate Islamism/Romanism

...
mineralise polygamist/lamppost/loyalist
IMMOLATE PAINLESSLY/signalises/silliness/sinlessly

[Playmates acceptable but Messianic distraction. N Haute.]

...
LORD [shouting]:
"How many holes? Four is excess, choose three."

...
schoolmistress whorehouse
Yahweh schoolmistress CONFEREES/HONOUREES

Yahweh Christ lecherousness/homelessness

[Jordan is Kahlan of SOT]

housemother confessor Yahweh

Mother Confessor Ulises Yahweh

...

Harcourt foolishness/selfishness/sexlessness/fleeciness/fleshiness/holiness

Harcourt Solomon excesses/fisheyes

Yasmine Chou wrestler

Messiah wrestler henhouse

Messiah correct henhouse

Messiah Ulysses throne/crown

wrestler succession

...

CONSORT (4644) MESSIAH schoolhouse/ESCHEWER/horseshoe/refocuses

Consort Messiah Euler eschews

CONSORT Yahweh schoolhouse/horseshoes/CRIMELESS/excelsior/Fleischer

consort Yahweh Flis horseshoes

consort Yahweh Fleisher

consort EXCELSIOR amuses [Nathaniel Haute IHES]

...

WHOREHOUSE ECONOMETRICS/CHRISTMASSES [BRAINLESS]

fornicator schoolhouse

Christmas cheerfulness

archenemies osteoscleroses

HENHOUSE FLIS ARMREST COCO [AVOID]

(Genesis 6:7)

"I will blot out man whom I have created from the face of the land,":

DICHLORODIFLUOROMETHANE EMBLEMATICAL HEATWAVE

...

"from man to animals to creeping things and to birds of the sky;":

SYNGENESIOTRANSPLANTATION COMMEMORATOR DIGITS/THIGH

commemorator transplplantation identifying

...

"for I am sorry that I have made them.":

father earthmover smith

terraformed mayhem

(Genesis 6:14)

"Make for yourself an ark of gopher wood":

foreknowledge paramour

(Genesis 6:17)

"And behold, I, even I am bringing the floor of water upon the earth":

trinitrotoluene bioenvironmental godhead

...

"to destroy all flesh in which is the breath of life, from under heaven;":

dichlorodifluoromethane reversibleness Yahweh

...

dichlorodifluoromethane detestableness irrelevant/Helvetian/LINEARITY/relative

...

DICHLORODIFLUOROMETHANE VERIFIABLENESS SWEETHEART

...

dichlorodifluoromethane anniversaries twelfthes

[Feb. 12; or 2/12]

...

dichlorodifluoromethane heavyhearted Listerine/lifeline

...

dichlorodifluoromethane eyewitness (4494) invertebrates [octopus ... Titanic]

dichlorodifluoromethane eyewitnesses Albert/heartbeat/Leviathan

...

"everything that is on the earth shall perish.":

representativeness airtight

REPRESENTATIVE GIANTS LITERAL

["Nephilim" or, giants (Genesis 6:4);

"Nephilim giants": PHILISTINE]

[NO BLOOD]

(Genesis 6:18)

"But I will establish My covenant with you; and you shall enter the ark-":

tetrahydrocannabinol substitution alleluia
tetrahydrocannabinol bolshevist unhealthiest [blood diseases]
tetrahydrocannabinol steakhouse illuminative/unhealthiest/villainies
blameworthiness authenticate Nathaniel Dorothy Lilly
blameworthiness relativistic Nathanael buttonholed

...
"you and your sons and your wife, and your sons' wives with you."
tyrannosaurus wondrousness divine
tyrannosaurus dinosaur Odyssey wifehood
FOREORDAIN DARWIN assiduousness/studiousness/shadowiness/UNSOUNDNESS/unsustained/astonishes/dishonesty/
odious/unassisted

[Film "Evan Almighty" 2007 BCE]
(Genesis 6:19)
"And of every living thing of all flesh, you shall bring two of every kind into the ark":
FOREORDAINED TRINITROTOLUENE teleVISIONALLY/WASHINGTONIANS/globalisation

...
"to keep them alive with you; they shall be male and female."
televisional whaleboat mayhemmed
EVOLUTION TIMESTAMPED
evolution alphabetised/baptismal/battlefield/TIMESTAMPED/blasphemed/deathliest/defeasible/deflatable/
detestable/mistakable/TIMETABLE

[Sodom ... sodomy = forced entry]
"Where are the men who came to you tonight? Bring them out to us that we may have relations with
them." (Genesis 19:5)

...
"So they pressed hard against Lot and came near to break the door." (Genesis 19:9)

[Red Tide]
(Exodus 7:20-21)
"all the water that was in the Nile was turned to blood. And the fish that were in the Nile died, and
the Nile became foul"

...
"Nile was turned to blood":
Red Tide Wollaston [shore MA]/Lawson [J, Mt. Fuji]

[No death penalty, notably lesbianism unforbidden; very small minority naturally gay men.]
...
(Leviticus 18:22)
"You shall not lie with a male as one lies with a female; it is an abomination."
UNWHOLESOMENESS EMOTIONAL FEMINISATION WHITEHALL LABILITY

[No rounding]
(Leviticus 19:27)
"You shall not round off the side growth of your heads, nor harm the edges of your beard."

...
[DHEA neurosteroid;
no rounding, or dulling the mind by gambling or fuzzy logic, analogic.
NO BUZZ CUTS.]
"You shall not round off the side growth of your heads":
dehydroisoandrosterone (DHEA) thoughtfully/tautologous/August
wrongheadedness illustrator/trustful/truthful/tutorial/authority/dutiful/faithful/SHORTHAIR
wrongheadedness shorthair lotto

...
"nor harm the edges of your beard":
heterogeneous
homogeneous barehead
guarantee reformer
head rounder geometry abhor
erroneous geometry

[Kay ... Cane]
(Numbers 17:8)
"the rod of Aaron for the house of Levi had sprouted and put forth buds and produced blossoms, and it
bore ripe almonds."

...
"sprouted and put forth buds and produced blossoms":
supernaturalness octopus fourths

String TOE ... shoelaces, base; foundations of physics;

"Adoni-bezek": Aeneid Ko

"And Adoni-bezek said, 'Seventy kings with their thumbs and their big toes cut off used to gather up scraps under my table; as I have done, so God has repaid me.'" (Judges 7:1)

[Sabbath]

(Nehemiah 13:19)

"just as it grew dark": dusk writer

(Psalm 2:2)

"The kings of the earth take their stand,
And the rulers take counsel together"

...

[Messiah]

"Against the LORD and against His Anointed":

INTERNATIONALISATION GANESHA

INTEGRATIONISTS DANDELION/GOLIATH/NATHANIEL

shithead (6888) niggardliness/orientalising/signalisation

Thessalonian antagonising/denigration/indentation/ghettoising

[is enthroned]

(Psalms 2:4)

"He who sits in the heavens laughs":

weightlessness Utahan/avian

Thessalonian highest/sweetie/thieves/eight/thigh/Hugh

elevation highness haute

thigh heathenishness/heavenliness/Thessalonian/unessential/elevation/Leviathan

...

Einstein evaluates/gatehouse/goulashes/assholes/ovulates/sausages

Einstein steal hogwash

Einstein Augst asshole

...

Utahan weightlessness/holinesses/highnesses/slingshot/eighteen/lionesses/evilness

Leviathan henhouses

EIGHTEEN astonishes/evaluation/Leviathan/salvation/unholiest/ASSASSIN

(Psalm 7:2)

"Lest he tear my soul like a lion":

Thessaloniki emulator

(Psalm 10:16)

"The LORD is King forever and ever": elevation sovereign Fred

[APPLE]

(Psalm 17:8)

"Keep me as the apple of the eye":

polymath safekeep/tepes

tepes meatloaf/playmate/polymath/healthy/helmet/alpha

...

"Hide me in the shadow of Thy wings":

shithead demotion

astonishment deified

MESSIAE GENIOHYOID [voice]

MESSIAH defending/deifying/identify/IDENTITY

Messiah Newton hogtied/thighed

Messiah thigh indented/honeyed

Hin Ting meadowsweet/shadowiest/defeatism/disesteem/shithead/sodomites/Mafiosos/weediest/yahwist [no identity]

YAHWEH (2922) DIMWITTEDNESS/SEMITENDINOSI [thigh]

YAHWEH THOMSON IDENTIFIES

Samson identified/eighteen/widowing

[MIT Course 18 Mathematics;

Bulls' Jordan, Pippen, Rodman.]

(Psalm 18:13)

"And the Most High uttered His voice":

GEOMETER EDUCATIONIST/enthusiastic/vindicated/acidities/shithead

sovereign domesticated/miseducated/Medicaid/shithead

sovereign diadem Scottie/ethic/octet/scout/stoic

EIGHTEEN CHRIST AUTOMOTIVE

[alignment validates structure]
eighteen Christ diadem hotshot
eighteen doctorate smith
EIGHTEEN MITHRIDATES OCTO

...
Mithridates detective/touchstone/devoutest/genocides/hothoused/covetous/doghouse/eugenics/genetics/
geodesic/viscount/Chinese/devious/heinous/shogun
Virginia Chou modestest/detestest/esteemed/demotes
Virginia scheme hothouse
Virginia custodee demotes
Travis (2885) homogenistic/documented/instituted/seducement/MEDICINES/comedies/custodee/demented/demonise/
emotions/misguide/outshone/demigod/demotes

...
HENHOUSE TRAGICOMEDIES/democratised/MEDIOCRITIES/demotivates/DISTRACTIVE/Archimedes/categories/cigarettes/
DISCHARGED/travesties/veracities/victimised/acidities
HENHOUSE DISCHARGE IDIOT

(Psalm 22)
[Jesus, permuted elsewhere]

(Psalm 27:1)
"The LORD is my light and my salvation;
Whom shall I fear?":
MARSHALL MATHERS IDENTIFYING HOLLYWOOD

...
"The LORD is my light and my salvation":
lamentation (2227) David syllogism
David slingshot (2282) immortal Hayley [comet]
dandelion (2229) alligator smith

...
"Whom shall I fear?": Marshall

...
"The LORD is my light and my salvation":
David mistranslation/immortalises/lamentation/Thessalonian
Thessalonian immortality/volatility/almighty/Vladimir/digital/goliath/David
immolation antislavery/highlander/
Siddhartha/Alisander/Leviathan/Streisand
David mineral mythologist/slingshot
Alisander Thomson almighty/digital
Streisand motivational

[logician]
(Psalms 29:5)
"The voice of the LORD breaks the cedars;":
elevate Frederick chessboard/doctorate

...
"Yes, the LORD breaks in pieces the cedars of Lebanon.":
tetrahydrocannabinol beekeeper/Fleischer/lordship/possessed
TETRAHYDROCANNABINOL POSSESSED FLEECE
FLEISCHER SLEEPYHEAD RECONDENSATION/noncarbonated/centenarian/cornerstone/restoration/scatterbrain/
transcendent/coronation
beekeeper crystallisation (2233) recondenses/horseshoed
recrystallisation recondenses hophead

(Psalm 29:10)
"The LORD sat as King at the flood":
tortoiseshell/folksinger/ethnologist/lionhearted/theologian/Alessandro/dishonored/floodlight/gladiator/
lordliness/Siddhartha/Aleksandr
Alessandro eightfold/Alfie
ALEKSANDR FLOODLIGHTS/TATTOOIST/SHITHEAD
ALEKSANDR FLIS TATTOOED/death/hated/goat/toad
Siddhartha footnote/gentlest/skeleton
shithead godforsaken/Aleksandr/allegator/footnoted/forgotten/tornadoes
TORNADO GOLDFISH

...
"Yes the LORD sits as King forever":
foresightedness/restorativeness/retrogression/revelationist/sovereign/transgressor/relativeness/
Thessaloniki
...
foresightedness kristal/krystal

transgressor shoveled/deifies
Thessaloniki destroyer/retrogress/restorer
relativeness hogtied/sorority
FLIS RESTORATIVENESS
FLIS SOVEREIGN RESTORES
ODYSSEAN retrogressive/firelighter/(ERRORLESS KITTIE)

[Weed, dragon, dandelion, Nathaniel]
(Psalms 37:1-2)
"Do not fret because of evildoers,
Be not envious toward wrongdoers.
For they will wither quickly like the grass,
And fade like the green herb."

...
"Do not fret because of evildoers,
Be not envious toward wrongdoers.":
countersignature interrelatedness observed
countersignature worldbeater offensiveness
Dandelion Guinevere costotransverse [rib joint] beetroot/foreswore
DANDELION OSTEORADIONECROSES EVERGREEN WOODRUFF
["Oldboy", CK amputee no limbs]
/tortuous/odorous

...
"Be not envious toward wrongdoers.":
WEED OBSERVATION OUTDOORS
RN
weed dragon brownstones/subversion/serotonin
weed Bostonian rounder
weed servant sorrowing/birdsong

...
"For they will wither quickly like the grass,
And fade like the green herb.":
Nathaniel diethylstilbestrol Friedrich
Yahweh referee [estrogen agonist]

...
"And fade like the green herb.":
Nathaniel refereed

(Psalm 37:17)
"But the LORD sustains the righteous."

[Jordan, Georgia]
(Psalms 37:32)
"The wicked spies upon the righteous,
And seeks to kill him."

[Trickle down economics]
"He who oppresses the poor to make much for himself
Or who gives to the rich, will only come to poverty." (Proverbs 22:16)

[Rounders 1998 Les]
"Lest you learn his ways,
And find a snare for yourself.
Do not be among those who give pledges,
Among those who become sureties for debts." (Proverbs 22:25-26)

"Do not move the ancient boundary
Which your fathers have set." (Proverbs 22:28)

"Have you found honey? Eat only what you need,
Lest you have it in excess and vomit it." (Proverbs 25:16)

(Proverbs 28:5)
"Evil men do not understand justice":
UNCONSTITUTIONAL (222) REDEEMED
Jerusalem innocentest/nonunionist
Constitutional unredeemed/revenues
constitution devalue nerd

...
"But those who seek the LORD understand all things":

knowledgeableness lionhearted Tudor/Russ/truth

(Proverbs 30:4)

"What is His name or His son's name?

Surely you know!":

TYRANNOSAURUS YAHWEH SOLOMON SIKHISMS

Tyrannosaurus Messiah Solomon Keynes

Yahweh emanation Solomon

Yahweh Messiah Solomon Antoninus

Messiah emanation Ulysses

Messiah Thessalonian workhorse

Messiah Isaiah enthrones Solomon/Kowloon/Romulus

womaniser Solomon swinishness/unawareness/renaissant/Ukrainian/Athenian/Austrian/Eurasian/Russian/Yankee

WOMANISER SOLOMON UNAWARE NESSY

HONEYMOON ULYSSES (5666) AIRWORTHINESS

...

Tyrannosaurus wholesomeness/homelessness/lonesomeness/awesomeness/immenseness/monkishness/winsomeness/Holinesses

TYRANNOSAURUS HOMELESSNESS HANOI [N]

(Proverbs 30:19)

"And the way of a man with a maid.":

Yahweh dominant

(Proverbs 31:10)

"For her worth is far above jewels.":

elevator horseshoe

Job elevates warrior/Aries

"I know that everything God does will remain forever; there is nothing to add to it and there is nothing to take from it" (Ecclesiastes 3:14)

[... Polygamy]

"If he takes to himself another woman, he may not reduce her food, her clothing, or her conjugal rights." (Exodus 21:10)

"food clothing conjugal rights":

CONSORT FLOODLIGHTING/JUDICATION

[Beast, analyst]

"there is no advantage for man over beast, for all is vanity."

(Ecclesiastes 3:19)

...

"all is vanity": analyst

[Like Jesus]

"for they do not know they are doing evil" (Ecclesiastes 5:1)

[Peregrin Took]

"Do not be hasty in word or impulsive in thought to bring up a matter in the presence of God."

(Ecclesiastes 5:2)

[Pointless economic growth]

"When good things increase, those who consume them increase. So what is the advantage to their owners except to look on?"

(Ecclesiastes 5:11)

[Buddha, ... Tokugawa]

"Patience of spirit is better than haughtiness of spirit."

(Ecclesiastes 7:8)

[Tom Riddle of Harry Potter]

"Divide your portion to seven, or even to eight, for you do not know what misfortune may occur on the earth." (Ecclesiastes 11:2)

[Name of the Wind, Kingkiller Chronicle]

"Just as you do not know the path of the wind" (Ecclesiastes 11:5)

[Genesis Adam]

"then the dust will return to the earth as it was, and the spirit will return to God who gave

it." (Ecclesiastes 12:7)

[Cloudcroft Mountain Hostel,
German owned,
Bought NASB for \$2,
Near Alamogordo White Sands,
Einstein's Trinity test site near
El Paso, attempting death of God]
(Solomon 2:14)

"In the secret place of the steep pathway":
astrophysical hatchet/heathen/Cathee

(Solomon 2:16)
"My beloved is mine, and I am his":
Dandelion misbehaves/Messiah

[ROUNDERS]
(Solomon 3:3)
"The watchmen who make the rounds in the city found me":
UNDERESTIMATION DUTCHWOMEN YAHWEH
/watchmen/Matthew/Yankee

(Solomon 3:6)
"Perfumed with myrrh and frankincense":
archenemy Frank Midwestern/undermines/Demetrius/feminised/fishermen/triumphe/Einstein/mutineer
archenemy Frank fishermen putrid

(Solomon 4:1)
"Your hair is like a flock of goats.":
hilarious footlocker
Harcourt alkalise yogi

(Solomon 6:9)
"But my dove, my perfect one, is unique":
omnipotence Demetrius
QUEEN DIVORCE SUBOPTIMUM
QUEEN DIVORCEMENT impetuous/SYMBIOTE
Queen vespertine tomboy
queen redemption combustive/Muscovite/symbiote

(Solomon 6:11)
"To see whether the vine has budded":
sweetheart beethoven/devotee

(Solomon 7:4)
"Your nose is like the tower of Lebanon":
Euler Frank sweetie Shinto/snooty

(Solomon 7:5)
"Your head crowns you like Carmel":
acidulous homemaker

[BE CAREFUL WITH CONSORTS]
(Solomon 8:5-7)
"There she was in labor and gave you birth.":
whitehorse Transylvania Deborah/Barbee
retrogradation Evelina Yahweh
evilness interrogatory
RETROGRESSIVE NATHANIEL

...
"Put me like a seal over your heart":
heteroerotism leapyear/plural

...
"Like a seal on your arm":
Salomon Euler

...
"For love is as strong as death":
EVERLASTING TORAH

...

"Jealousy is as severe as Sheol" (2220):

Israel assessees
Savior Ulysses asshole/Lhasa

...

"Its flashes are flashes of fire"
Israel assessorial

...

"The very flame of the LORD":
elevatory Homer

...

"Many waters cannot quench love":
enthronement Casanova

...

"Nor will rivers overflow it":
retroversion

...

"If a man were to give all the riches of his house for love":
overrighteous affirmativeness

...

"It would be utterly despised.":
prostitute belle
Lordliest deputised/weediest

(Isaiah 2:4)

"And He will judge between the nations,":
Jedediah (4404) eighteen
Agust obediential/dandelion/halloween/Newtonian/whitehall
Aeneid unenlightened/unhealthiest/deathliest

...

"And will render decisions for many peoples;":
semiprofessional ordinance/recrowned

...

"And they will hammer their swords into plowshares,":
interrelationship (5007) shareholders shalom
"and their spears into pruning hooks.":
Shapiro kindergartens

...

"National will not lift up sword against nation,":
institutionalisation nondollar

...

"And never again will they learn war.":
elevating yielder Hanna
Nevadian interregnal/eighteen
Nathaniel (2622) revealingly

(Isaiah 3:12)

"And women rule over them":
NETHERLANDER meow/moo/woe

...

dethrone manoeuvre/Emmanuel/unmoral/unravel
Emanuel overthrown/dethroner/Dorothee/honored

"For seven women will take hold of one man in that day" (Isaiah 4:1)

[Brandon Stark]

"Branch of the LORD" (Isaiah 4:2)

(Isaiah 5:26)

"He will also lift up a standard to the distant nation":
Russia antinationalist

(Isaiah 5:27)

"No one in it is weary or stumbles":
Russians wintertime
Russia (3131) ennoblement

(Isaiah 6:3)

"Holy, Holy, Holy, is the LORD of hosts":
footstool Odyssey/soldier/oiler/doll
tortoise floss/doll

Detroit floss/solo
Shiloh toothless

(Isaiah 7:7)

"It shall not stand nor shall it come to pass."
Christmas Thessalonian Apollo

(Isaiah 7:14)

"Behold a virgin will be with child":
challenger Lilith

...
"Behold a virgin will be with child and bear a son":
charlatanerie dandelion/idealising/villainies/evildoing
denicotinising (2022) worldview/heralded/Deborah/Barbie
recondensation Hildegard
worldbeater cannibalising/Scandinavian/cannabidiol/dandelion

...
"and she will call His name Immanuel":
demasculinise Helain
MUHAMMAD cleanliness/achilleine/Hellenise/sinicise/cleanse/Lilian
Michael (2888) maidenliness/unmanliness/Hellenisms
MESSIAH ALLELUIA MACHINE/Delilah

[Israel's ruin foreordained]

"For before the boy will know enough to refuse evil and choose good, the land whose two kings you dread
will be forsaken."
(Isaiah 7:16)

"In that day the Lord will shave with a razor" (Isaiah 7:20)

(Isaiah 9:6)

"And His name will be called Wonderful Counselor, Mighty God,
Eternal Father, Prince of Peace."

...
"Wonderful Counselor, Mighty God":
Deuteronomy lording ghoul
Deuteronomy Flis groundhog
rounder gynecologist/floodlights/honeylocust/Dutchwomen
foulmouthed goronised/recrowning/wrongdoing
Fleurdelis groundhog
Schrodinger monologue
homogeniser odourful/wrongful
Clementius wolfhound/godhood
interregnum Hollywood/godhood/Osgood/cloud/ghoul

...
"Eternal Father, Prince of Peace."
Alpha Creator pierce
Alpha potter caffeine
lantern patriarch/prophetic
fornicate repenter
CATHARTIC PENELOPE
Nathaniel reporter
chaotic fraternal/Lateran
falconer apprentice

(Isaiah 11:2)

"And the Spirit of the LORD will rest on Him":
shithead (7677)
impersonator (3533) identifies/Nefertiti
impersonator dethroned (111) filii
impersonator titleholder flis

...
foreordainment worshiped Lilith
foreordainment Detroit Lilith
DETROIT METROPOLITAN FINISHER
WHITEHORSE haloperidol/iliofemoral/Mithridates/pollinator/omnipotent/dandelion
whitehorse haloperidol Finn
whitehorse omnipotent Allistir/diarist
whitehorse dandelion shoplift
Mithridates friendship/penfriends/trillions

Mithridates Einstein follow
pinewood motherliness Filial/Harri/Alfi
pinewood mother Israelitish/thriftiness/Streisand/shithead/Allister
Streisand promotion freewill
Streisand motherhood litter
lifeline airworthiness lord

(Isaiah 11:10)
"root of Jesse":
jester, JOSEF [ancestral]

[Anagrams are an ANALOGY here, verse in direct reference to Babylon]

[Worm Rounders 1998]
(Isaiah 14:11-12)
" 'And worms are your covering.'
How you have fallen from heaven,
O star of the morning, son of the dawn!"

...
"How you have fallen from heaven" (222):
Yahweh menorah
Yahweh femoral/envenom
Yahweh femor (420) unleaven
Emanuel Helen hooray
Evaleen Romanov
Reamonn yellow

...
"O star of the morning, son of the dawn!":
foreordainment Agosto

...
(Isaiah 14:14)
"I will make myself like the Most High":
Elohim Almighty flesh/(Smith Flis)

[Philadelphia Constitutional Convention]

(Isaiah 18:2,7)
"A powerful and oppressive nation, Whose land the rivers divide":
overapprehensiveness antirevolutionaries Adolph
representativeness Philadelphia foreordain
PHILADELPHIA REPRESENTATIVES ENDORADIOSONDE RUINS
[spy monitor implants]
FOREORDINATION THESSALONIAN DAVID DESPISE

...
"a powerful and oppressive nation":
federal supervision/universitas/renaissant/supernova/Antoninus
FEDERAL SENATORS OPINION
PRESIDENT SLOVENIAN PROOF
PRESIDENT SAVIOR NAPOLEON
PRESIDENT SUPERNOVA (222) FIONA/Alfi/fool ... [G, Robinette]
president peninsular/propulsion/annapolis/Slovenian/supernova/universal
universitas (1222) nonfederal/preplanned

...
"Whose land the rivers divide":
DAVID EISENHOWER [US president]
WHITEHORSE ENSLAVED whitehorse vernalised [semen?]/disdained/invalided/sidelined/slandered/Disraeli/
divine/enslaved/saddened/sardined/adviser/David/evasive/reviled/savvied/servile/snailed/Aeneid
whitehorse David delivers/silvered
SWINEHERD DERIVATIVES [N]/ADVERTISED/deviltries/evildoer/varieties/idealist
Aeneid evildoer/shrewdest
REVELATION WISHERS [WWIII, nuclear apocalypse]

(Isaiah 18:3)
"And as soon as the trumpet is blown, you will hear it.":
automobile transportational newlyweds
mineralisation Alessandro hotshot

(Isaiah 19:20)
"Savior and a Champion":
casanova hairpin/Nimrod
scorpion avian/Adam
Marianna hasid/acid

Chaos primadonna

(Isaiah 22:20)

"My servant Eliakim the son of Hilkiyah":
Metatarsal feminine/monkeyish/keyhole
Metatarsal keyhole Finnish
Thessalonian elevatory

...

"Eliakim the son of Hilkiyah":
meatloaf (253) Helsinki/Shiloh
lifeline Isaiah/Taiko/smith
alkalinise thief

...

"Eliakim": Mikael

(Isaiah 22:22)

"Then I will set the key of the house of David on his shoulder,
When he opens no one will shut,
When he shuts no one will open."

[Oldboy movie for Lot's daughters,
K 'Ol Nick, Machiavelli]

(Isaiah 22:25)

"The peg driven in a firm place will give way":
Machiavellianly interviewed/definitive/identifier/reverified/EVERGREEN/PEREGRINE/prevented
grandmaternal chili
charlatanerie devilling/vilifying
challenging reverified
PEREGRINATING MACHIAVELLI

[host of heaven]

(Isaiah 24:22)

"And will be confined in prison":
acidifier bloodline/pinewood/poseidon

(Isaiah 25:7)

"Even the veil which is stretched over all nations":
Christianisation wretchedest/Chesterton/cleverest
Christianisation cleverest Hellen
Christianities covenant devotees
INTERNATIONAL COLLECTIVIST WEEDS
CATHOLICISATION WESTERNISED
CHRISTIANITIES OCTAHEDRON
Orientalisation wretchedness/westernised
...
transcendentalist cholesterol/WHITEHORSE/CHRIST
recondensation ethicalities/Israelitish/sweetheart/Christal/wealthess

(Isaiah 25:8)

"He will swallow up death for all time":
heliotherapies fallout/Adam
Mithridates helpful/hopeful
laureateship floodlit
FLEURDELIS WHITEHALL
ALLELUIA HALOPERIDOL/WHITEHORSE
Alpha iliofemoral/fleurdelis

(Isaiah 27:1)

"And He will kill the dragon who lives in the sea.":
handwritten shielding (887) hellhole
gasoline invalidates weedkiller/dethrone
gasoline revelationist headlined
Washingtonians (2122) weedkiller
Washingtonian evildoer Whitehall
...
Lordliness elevation diligent
Thessalonian elevated whirlwind
Thessalonian Revelation killed
Sovereign alkalinisation heeded

(Isaiah 49:6)

"I will also make You a light of the nations":

Thessalonian haematology/kilowattage/almightily/alleluia/meatloaf
Tokugawa infinitesimally/astonishment/elimination/annihilates

(Isaiah 49:7)

"To the despised One,

To the One abhorred by the nation":

Robinette hardhandedness/hardheadedness/hotheadedness

...

"To the One abhorred by the nation":

Robinette bayoneted ["ramrod"]/abandonee/beetroot/betatron/betrayed/dethrone

betrayed Antoinette

BETATRON BETATRON HONEYED

(Isaiah 52:14)

"So His appearance was marred more than any man":

recommendation (1444) empress Hanna

recondensation seraph/Yasmeen

[Jesus false Messiah]

(Isaiah 53:10)

"If He would render Himself as a guilt offering":

DEMINERALISATION FLEURDELIS

(Isaiah 53:12)

"Because He poured out Himself to death":

SHITHEAD (8806) OCTOPUS ALBERT

shithead Deborah completest

Hephaestus Albert touched

Prometheus autodidact

Themistocles Deborah defeat

(Isaiah 54:1)

"Shout for joy, O barren one, you who have borne no child":

schoolfriend overthrewer/Beethoven/Johnathan/betrayer/honorary

schoolfriend beethoven honorary

Jordan celebration (1110) brownnoser

Jordan Nosanchu overthrewer/interferer/irreverent/unbeliever/unworthier/Beethoven/evolution/wolverine/

Berliner/honouree

Jordan Berliner Hohenstaufen ?

...

Johnathan overincredous/hydrofluoric/irreverence/nonbeliever/odouriferous/undefensible

(Isaiah 54:2)

"Break forth into joyful shouting and cry aloud, you who have not travailed":

Jordan Nosanchuk unforgettable retaliatory/whitehall

Jordan Nosanchuk unforgettable retaliator adulthood/ladyhood/youthful/validity

Jordan Nosanchuk unforgettable Whitehall auditory

(Isaiah 54:5)

"For your husband is your Maker":

dinosaur yearbook

Afrikaner [Dutch] odorous/bosoms/sodomy

BIRDHOUSE FRANK

(Isaiah 54:16)

"Behold, I Myself have created the smith who blows the fire of coals":

recrystallise meatloaf (3833) Themistocles[N]/lobotomised

(Isaiah 54:16)

"And I have created the destroyer to ruin.":

Hades death reintroduction/nicotinate

Octahedron Aeneid servitude

nicotinate (2223) overseer

(Isaiah 59:6)

"Their webs will not become clothing":

misintelligence blowtorch

INTELLIGENCE HOMOEROTIC

electioneering oilcloth/Cosimo/Moscow
Monticello eighteen/Heisenberg/whitehorse
whitehorse (1444) intelligent/noneligible

(Isaiah 63:4)
"And My year of redemption has come":
foreordainment poached

(Isaiah 65:25)
"dust shall be the serpent's food":
tablespoonful dessert

(Jeremiah 6:20)
"For what purpose does frankincense come to Me from Sheba":
foreordainment treacherousness embosom cheap/poach
...
"And the sweet cane from a distant land?"

(Jeremiah 12:7-8)
"I have forsaken My house,
I have abandoned My inheritance;
I have given the beloved of My soul Into the hand of her enemies.
My inheritance has become to Me
Like a lion in the forest;
She has roared against Me;
Therefore I have come to hate her."

...
"I have forsaken My house":
Savior Yankees

...
"I have abandoned My inheritance":
nicotinamide Aberdeen
vindication Maryanna

...
"I have given the beloved of my soul":
Sheba homogeneity/evildoing/limelight

...
"Into the hand of her enemies.":
Dethronement fashion/Hanoi
enthronement (223) deifies

[See GENESIS 3]
(Jeremiah 12:12-13)
"On all the bare heights in the wilderness
Destroyers have come,
For a sword of the LORD is devouring
From one end of the land even to the other;
There is no peace for anyone.
They have sown wheat and have reaped thorns,
They have strained themselves to no profit.
But be ashamed of your harvest
Because of the fierce anger of the LORD."

...
"For a sword of the lord is devouring":
wrathfulness forgiver
revolutionise godhood

(Jeremiah 12:14)
"Thus says the LORD concerning all My wicked neighbors who strike at the inheritance with which I have
endowed My people Israel, 'Behold I am about to uproot them from their land and will uproot the house of
Judah from among them.' "

[Jeremiah: Jae]
(Jeremiah 20:14)
"Cursed be the day when I was born":
DOWNHEARTEDNESS BARBIE
wretchedness Deborah

[See Job 3:3]
(Jeremiah 20:15)

"Cursed be the man who brought the news
To my father, saying,
'A baby boy has been born to you!'
And made him very happy."

(Jeremiah 23:5)
"And He will reign as king and act wisely":
Crystal alkalinising/singlehanded/Kisanagi

...
Christ alkalinising/Disneyland
CHRIST WELLESLEY INDIANIAN/GINNI
EIGHTEEN NASAL ALKALINISING/SCANDALLING

["Yahweh Tsidkenu":
Yahweh kindest,
shithead key, Ieyasu dent,
weed haunts/stinky/Utahn]
(Jeremiah 23:6)
"The LORD our righteousness."
neurosurgeries/retrogression/righteousness/rigorousness/ghoulishness/gloriousness/outrightness/
resoluteness/thoroughness/togetherness/tortuousness/eighteenth/guesthouses/hideousness/lighthouses/
orderliness/roundhouses/theologist

...
RÉTROGRESSION DUTEOUS/LOTUS
Eighteen holdout
Rounder lighthouse/theologist/thoroughest

(Jeremiah 30:6)
"Ask now, and see,
If a male can give birth.
Why do I see every man,
With his hands on his loins, as a woman in childbirth?"

...
'Ask now, and see,
If a male can give birth.':
America Washington defensive

(Jeremiah 31:22)
"How long will you go here and there,
O faithless daughter?
For the LORD has created a new thing in the earth -
A woman will encompass a man."

...
"A woman will encompass a man."
nonsensical mamma/momma
NAPOLEONIC NASAL

(Jeremiah 31:27)
"I will sow the house of Israel and the house of Judah with the seed of man and with the seed of beast."

(Jeremiah 31:31)
"when I will make a new covenant with the house of Israel and with the house of Judah":
internationalisation levelheadedness effectuate/automatic/Matthiew

[313, 333, trinity false Messiah]

(Jeremiah 31:33)
"I will put My law within them, and on their heart I will write it":
dethronement MARIJUANA Twitter/Hitler
reinterpretation attitudinal/humiliated/illuminate/WHITEHALL/alleluia/Immanuel
reinterpretation alleluia Lilith
reinterpretation immanuel lilith
reinterpretation whitehall militant
TRINITY INTERPRETATION HUMILIATED/WHITEHALL
PERMUTATIONAL INDETERMINATE LILITH

(Jeremiah 31:33)
"And I will be their God and they shall be My people."
demineralisation Yahweh potbelly/pledged
alphabetisation pledgeholder
YAHWEH LORD GODEL SLEEPYHEAD INIMITABLE

(Jeremiah 33:15)

"I will cause a righteous Branch of David to spring forth":
straightforwardness neuropathological/autobiographical/unapologetical/acidification/glorification/
valedictorian/necrophiliac
acidification unalphabetise ghoul

[Proof Phaeton Testament fragmented, not prophesy]

(Jeremiah 36:28)

"Take again another scroll and write on it all the former words that were on the first scroll which
Jehoiakim the king of Judah burned."

(Jeremiah 37:15)

"they put him [Jeremiah] in jail in the house of Jonathan the scribe"

(Jeremiah 38:7)

"Ebed-melech the Ethiopian, a eunuch, ... heard that they had put Jeremiah into the cistern."

[Modern permutational echoes with identical outcome indicate LORD is responsible; discovered Oct. 8,
2024, one year anniversary of unprovoked attack]

(Jeremiah 47:1)

"That which came as the word of the LORD to Jeremiah the prophet concerning the Philistines, before
Pharaoh conquered Gaza."

(Jeremiah 47:4)

"On account of the day that is coming":
authentication octagon/Thomson/Agosto
authenticating Scotchman/Thomson
condemnation haughty/Toyotas/tattoos/Agosto
denunciation Toyota/tattoos/Agosto/Cathay/Cacao/fagots/Gotham/ghost

...

"To destroy all the Philistines,":
depersonalise hostility

...

"To cut off from Tyre and Sidon
Every ally that is left;":
counteroffensive retaliatory shalom

...

"For the LORD is going to destroy the Philistines,":
HYPERSENSITISING FLOODLIGHTED/foresighted/eightsided
foresightedness spotlighted trinity/Thorin/Triton/honor/holy
friendless spotlighting Detroit history

...

"The remnant of the coastland of Caphtor.":
catastrophe octahedon manhole
catastrophe octahedral footmen

[TRUMP immune puppeteered by N]

(Jeremiah 51:34)

"Nebuchadnezzar king of Babylon has devoured me and crushed me":
Nebuchadnezzar Abraham feeblemindedness
Nebuchadnezzar Abraham homogeniser befuddles
DANDELION BARBEE UNDERHANDEDNESS

...

"He has set me down like an empty vessel;":
sleepyhead astonishment/antithesis/weaknesses

...

"He has swallowed me like a monster,":
immoderateness whale
loathsomeness WEEDKILLER/MIKAEL
Aleksandr mesothelioma/whitewashes/WHITEHALL/homeless/Messiah
Alessandro whitehall
MESSIAH ALEKSANDR HELMET

...

"he has filled his stomach with my delicacies":
Themistocles Michael declassify/deacidify/childish
MICHAEL masochistically/atheistically/disassociates/CATHOLICISM/CATHOLICISED/Ecclesiastes/CHAOTICALLY

...

"He has washed me away.":
Yahweh ashamed

[Copied 10/10/24, two days after Oct. 8, 2024 one year anniversary copying and permuting verses of ancient destruction of Gaza.]

"on the tenth day of the tenth month, that Nebuchadnezzar king of Babylon came" (Jeremiah 52:4)

"And he [Nebuzaradan] burned the house of the LORD, the king's house, and all the houses of Jerusalem; even every large house he burned with fire." (Jeremiah 52:13)

[Potholder, weed]

"And they also took away the pots" (Jeremiah 52:18)

[Dates 12/25 Xmas]

"in the twelfth month, on the twenty-fifth of the month, that Evil-merodach king of Babylon, in the first year of his reign, showed favor to Jehoiachin king of Judah and brought him out of prison." (Jeremiah 52:31)

(Lamentations 1:18)

"For I have rebelled against His command":

Machiavelli foreordainment

Machiavellianism dethrones

Machiavellian homogeniser breast

reverification Magdalene

(Lamentations 1:22)

"And deal with them as Thou hast dealt with me":

hotheadedness humiliated

[Noah's covenant]

(Lamentations 2:4)

"He has bent his bow like an enemy": Babylonian smith

(Lamentations 4:10)

"The hands of compassionate women":

astonishment shamefaced

...

"Boiled their own children;

They became food for them":

foreordainment crocodile Bethlehem

dandelion homoerotic Bethlehem

recommendation Frederick Hollywood/wifeness

reconciliation motherhood Demetre

...

"Because of the destruction of the daughter of my people.":

Dorothee psychopharmacologies/psychotherapeutical/chemotherapeutics/neuropathologist/neuropsychologist/psychopathologist

[Edom is in modern Jordan,

south east of Dead Sea;

"Job and Jeremiah": Jordan Jae]

(Lamentations 4:21)

"Rejoice and be glad, O daughter of Edom,

Who dwells in the land of Uz":

CONGRATULATION HOMOGENISER JEZEBEL

congratulation alleluia defender/Ebenezer/freedom/redeemed

congratulation Alamogordo blindfolded

...

"But the cup will come around to you as well":

electrocution blasphemy

polymath celebrates

(Lamentations 5:16)

"The crown has fallen from our head":

Netherlander washroom

[Ezekiel bread]

(Ezekiel 4:12)

"And you shall eat it as a barley cake, having baked it in their sight over human dung."

[2/3 of way through Bible]

(Ezekiel 5:12)

"One third of you will die by plague or be consumed by famine among you, one third will fall by the sword around you, and one third I will scatter to every wind, and I will unsheathe a sword behind them."

(Ezekiel 5:17)

"I, the LORD, have spoken.":
evildoers Phaethon

(Ezekiel 7:2)

"An end! The end is coming on the four corners of the land.":
trinitrotoluene hardhandedness offence
underhandedness necromancer footnoting

[Numbers 17:8, rod of Aaron]

(Ezekiel 7:10)

"Your doom has gone forth; the rod has budded, arrogance has blossomed."

...

"the rod has budded, arrogance has blossomed":
treacherousness (1888) Alamogordo

(Ezekiel 8:17)

"they are putting the twig to their nose": prostitution eighteen

[See Psalm 37:17, save righteous]

(Ezekiel 9:4)

"put a mask on the forehead of the men who sigh and groan over all the abominations which are being committed in its midst."

(Ezekiel 9:11)

"man clothed in linen":
Michael (222)

[Whitehall ... Michael]

"So I shall tear down the wall which you plastered over with whitewash" (Ezekiel 13:14)

[Context idols in heart, foreshadowing]

(Ezekiel 14:21)

"to cut off man and beast from it!"

[GOD MOST HIGH,

in the time of Abraham]

(Ezekiel 16:49-50)

"Behold, this was the guilt of your sister Sodom: she and her daughters had arrogance ... Therefore I removed them when I saw it."

...

'Behold, this was the guilt of your sister Sodom: she and her daughters had arrogance':

GOD MOST HIGH straightforwardness recrystallises (hardhanded beta)/dethroned

GOD MOST HIGH countersignature authoriser wholeheartedly/(worldbeater flesh)

[Bird, dinosaur]

"A great eagle with great wings, long pinions and a full plumage of many colors, came to Lebanon and took away the top of the cedar."

(Ezekiel 17:3)

...

"Behold, the king of Babylon came to Jerusalem, took its king and princes, and brought them to him in Babylon." (Ezekiel 17:12)

(Ezekiel 18:4)

"Behold, all souls are Mine":
Alessandro Elohim

...

"the soul of the father as well as the soul of the son is Mine. The soul who sins will die."

(Ezekiel 20:33)

"I shall be king over you.":
vaingloriously bee

[The Negev is a desert.]

(Ezekiel 20:46-48)

"prophesy against the forest land of the Negev ... 'Behold, I am about to kindle a fire in you ... And all flesh will see that I, the LORD, have kindled it; it shall not be quenched.'"

"therefore strike your thigh" (Ezekiel 21:12)

(Ezekiel 21:27)

"Until He comes whose right it is, and I shall give it to Him.":

Christ smith Godel almightiness elevation

Christ lighthouse Almightiness elevation

[SMITH 22;

A modern example of immolation is Thich Quang Duc vs Catholics.]

...

(Ezekiel 22:22)

"As silver is melted in the furnace, so you will be melted in the midst of it; and you will know that I, the LORD, have poured out My wrath on you."

[Lion of Judah]

(Ezekiel 22:25)

"There is a conspiracy of her prophets in her midst, like a roaring lion tearing the prey. They have devoured lives"

...

"like a roaring lion tearing the prey":

Nathaniel Peregrine (333) Trilogy/Troika

PEREGRINE HIN TING KO ARIEL

PEREGRINE irrationality/antirational/annihilator/integration/

TRINITARIAN

peregrination halogenate/integrally

peregrinate alligator/Nathaniel

...

"They have devoured lives":

DEVIL DEVOTEES

[BITCHES]

(Ezekiel 22:27-28)

"Her princes within her are like wolves tearing the prey, by shedding blood and destroying lives in order to get dishonest gain.

And her prophets have smeared whitewash for them, seeing false visions and divining lies for them"

[LORD is merciful]

"And I searched for a man among them who should build up the wall and stand in the gap before Me for the land that I should not destroy it; but I found no one." (Ezekiel 22:30)

"Put on the pot ... the thigh ... Make it boil vigorously" (Ezekiel 24:3-5)

(Ezekiel 28:13-16)

"You were in Eden, the garden of God"

...

"You were the anointed cherub who covers":

NEWTON WEED CORROBORATIVE/TREACHEROUS

"And I placed you there.

You were on the holy mountain of God;

You walked in the midst of the stones of fire."

...

"And I have destroyed you, O covering cherub"

...

"covering cherub": Cohen vice

"Thus says the Lord GOD to these bones, 'Behold, I will cause breath to enter you that you may come to life.' " (Ezekiel 37:5)

"Thus says the Lord GOD, 'Behold, I will take the stick of Joseph, which is in the hand of Ephraim, and the tribes of Israel, his companions; and I will put them with it, with the stick of Judah, and make them one stick, and they will be one in My hand.' " (Ezekiel 37:19)

"And it was carved with cherubim and palm trees; and a palm tree was between cherub and cherub, and every cherub had two faces, a man's face toward the palm tree on one side, and a young lion's face toward the palm tree on the other side; they were carved in all the house all around." (Ezekiel 41:18-19)

"And they [aliens] shall be to you as the native-born among the sons of Israel; they shall be allotted an inheritance with you among the tribes of Israel." (Ezekiel 47:22)

(Ezekiel 48:35)

"The city shall be 18,000 cubits round about; and the name of the city from that day shall be, 'The LORD is there.' "

...

'The LORD is there':
Shiloh refter [Savior]
Detroit seer
Lot thresher

"Nebuchadnezzar had dreams; and his spirit was troubled and his sleep left him." (Daniel 2:1)

"And in that you saw the iron mixed with common clay, they will combine with one another in the seed of men; but they will not adhere to one another, even as iron does not combine with pottery. And in the days of those kings the God of heaven will set up a kingdom which will never be destroyed" (Daniel 2:43-44)

[Idolatry]

"But whoever does not fall down and worship shall be cast into the midst of a furnace of blazing fire." (Daniel 3:11)

[Magi?]

"O Belteshazzar, chief of the magicians" (Daniel 4:9)

(Daniel 4:13)

"an angelic watcher, a holy one":
ARCHANGEL NATHANIEL

[Cranbrook KINGSWOOD]

"Chop down the tree and cut off its branches,

...

Yet leave the stump with its roots in the ground,
But with a band of iron and bronze around it"
(Daniel 4:14-15)

[Nathaniel's NT beast]

"And let a beast's mind be given to him." (Daniel 4:16)

[Read the writing on the wall]

"Suddenly the fingers of a man's hand emerged and began writing opposite the lampstand on the plaster of the wall of the king's palace, and the king saw the back of the hand that did the writing." (Daniel 5:5)

[Daniel long-lived. Nebuchadnezzar, Belshazzar, Darius, Cyrus.]

"So this Daniel enjoyed success in the reign of Darius and in the reign of Cyrus the Persian." (Daniel 6:28)

(Daniel 7:9)

"And the Ancient of Days took His seat":
condensation shithead
Constantine atheist

(Daniel 7:13)

"And He came up to the Ancient of Days":
authenticate condensed/Feynman/Yasmeen

[Corporate America]

(Daniel 7:23)

"The fourth beast will be a fourth kingdom on the earth, which will be different from all the other kingdoms,"

"and it will devour the whole earth and tread it down and crush it.":

counterrevolutionaries annihilated/delawarean/hardhanded/hardheaded/Nathaniel/whirlwind
COUNTERREVOLUTIONARIES ANNHILATED WITHDRAWAL
counterrevolutionaries NATHANIEL withdrawal
trinitrotoluene authentication DELAWARE

(Daniel 7:25)

"and he will intend to make alterations in times and in law":
internationalisation Nathaniel dismantled/weediest

(Daniel 8:23)

"A king will arise":

Killer Asian
"Insolent and skilled in intrigue":
dandelion trinitities/Einstein
antireligious Einstein

(Daniel 8:24)
"And his power will be mighty, but not by his own power,":
BLAMEWORTHINESS HYPERBOLOID HINTING
bibliotherapy disgruntlement

...
"And he will destroy to an extraordinary degree":
ALEXANDER DETROIT AENEID WRONGDOER

...
"And prosper and perform his will;" (3008):
foreordain wardenship
lordship manifold/Alisander
mineral professorial/worshippers

...
"He will destroy mighty men and the holy people.":
MEPHISTOPHELEAN HOMOGENEITY

(Daniel 8:25)
"And through his shrewdness":
transgression deus
thigh rounder sadness
righteousness Nash/Rand

...
"He will cause deceit to succeed by his influence;":
acidulousness benefited

...
"And he will magnify himself in his heart,":
demineralising whitehall/analyst/Eastman/Ishmael/William/Lilian/Yasmin/Yahweh

...
"And he will destroy many while they are at ease.":
dethronement SHITHEAD lawyerly/Aeriël
DEMINERALISE DETHRONE YAHWEH

...
"He will even oppose the Prince of princes,"(8871 ... Harcourt):
Christ colonelship/conversion/fellowship/honorifics/necrophile/Persephone/principles/wolverines/FLEISCHER/
fleshier/lifelines/Nipponese
CHRIST FLIS NONVIOLENCE/necrophile/wolverine
Christ Fleisher Nonviolence/penelope
CHRIST NIPPONESE NECROPHILE
lifeline (4494) Christ Persephone
Phillip overseership Newton
Newton (3833) chronicler Phillip

...
"But he will be broken without human agency.":
congratulation bumblebee/humblebee/Klement

(Daniel 9:26)
"Then after the sixty-two weeks the Messiah will be cut off and have nothing":
William Andrew Stefani necessitate Beethoven
William Andrew Stefani excise Hohenstaufen hottest
William Andrew Stefani covenantee fishhook sweetest/fetuses/sextets
WILLIAM ANDREW STEFANI EXCISE (3131) AUTOGENES BEETHOVEN/honeybee/keystone
WILLIAM ANDREW STEFANI BEETHOVEN AUTOGENES fisheyes/Scottish/coffees/excises

...
"the Messiah will be cut off and have nothing":
UNAVOIDABLENESS AFFLICTION

(Daniel 10:13)
"Michael, one of the chief princes":
ANNE FLIS HOMERIC Coptic/thief
CONCEPTION FLEISCHER/Cheshire/Heraclès/miracles/fleecer
Flis confirmation/omnipotence/Promethean/conception
femoral nicotinise/Einstein

(Daniel 12:11)
"abomination of desolation":

nationalisation boom

[Reincarnation]

"then you will enter into rest and rise again for your allotted portion at the end of the age." (Daniel 12:13)

[Jesus Reminiscent]

"He will revive us after two days;
He will raise us up on the third day
That we may live before Him."
(Hosea 6:2)

(Hosea 6:7)

"But like Adam they have transgressed the covenant":
undemonstrativeness (2122) blackheart

(Hosea 7:7)

"All of them are hot like an oven":
OVEREMOTIONAL Athena/Helen

[Aaron's calf ... Samael,
craftsman ... raftsman]

"A craftsman made it, so it is not God;
Surely the calf of Samaria will be broken to pieces."
(Hosea 8:6)

(Hosea 13:14)

"O Death, where are your thorns?
O Sheol, where is your sting?":
YAHWEH YAHWEH HETEROGENEOUSNESS
Yahweh Yahweh trinitrotoluene doghouses

"Wail like a virgin girded with sackcloth
For the bridegroom of her youth."
(Joel 1:8)

"the apple tree" (Joel 1:12)
"the garden of Eden" (Joel 2:3)

[e.g. Maud]

"That I will pour out My Spirit on all mankind" (Joel 2:28)

"The sun will be turned into darkness,
And the moon into blood,
Before the great and awesome day of the LORD comes.
And it will come about that whoever calls on the name of the LORD
Will be delivered;" (Joel 2:31-32)

[Israel, not Palestine]

"Yet it was I who destroyed the Amorite before them ...
That you might take possession of the land of the Amorite."
(Amos 2:9-10)

"You only have I chosen among all the families of the earth;"
(Amos 3:2)

[Versus Commandment #2]

(Amos 6:10)
"Keep quiet. For the name of the LORD is not to be mentioned."
trinitrotoluene behemoth

[The Little Mermaid]

"And though they conceal themselves from My sight on the floor of the sea,
From there I will command the serpent and it will bite them."
(Amos 9:3)

[Yaffa ... Jap]

"So he went down to Joppa, found a ship which was going to Tarshish" (Jonah 1:3)

[Pothead]

"Weeds were wrapped around my head." (Jonah 2:5)

"Then the LORD commanded the fish, and it vomited Jonah up onto the dry land." (Jonah 2:10)

"the sun beat down on Jonah's head so that he became faint and begged with all his soul to die, saying, 'Death is better to me than life.' " (Jonah 4:8)

(Habakkuk 2:5) [... Hakka Ku/UK]

"He enlarged his appetite like Sheol,"

"And he is like death, never satisfied.":

Aeneid Aeneid relativist/deathliest/deviltries/heraldist/travesties/faithless/satisfied/SHITHEAD

[Ruler is measurement.]

(Micah 5:2)

"But as for you, Bethlehem Ephrathah,

Too little to be among the clans of Judah,

From you One will go forth for Me to be ruler in Israel."

...
'From you One will go forth for Me to be ruler in Israel':

iliofemoral heterogeneous lobotomy/Milton

iliofemoral homogeneous Berliner Lotto

unforgettable housewife oiler Mormon

(Micah 5:5)

"And this One will be our peace.":

denuclearisation elbow

" 'On that day,' declares the LORD of hosts, 'I will take you, Zerubbabel, son of Shealtiel, my servant,' declares the LORD, 'and I will make you like a signet ring, for I have chosen you,' ' declares the LORD of hosts." (Haggai 2:23)

...
'I will take you, Zerubbabel, son of Shealtiel, my servant':

trinitrotoluene Bolshevism/sleazeballs

...
'and I will make you like a signet ring, for I have chosen you':

demineralisation challenger

recrystallising honeymooning/manifolding/nonyielding

acknowledgement sovereign hilarious/unskilful/Frankish/Honolulu/Krishna

...
'I will make you like a signet ring':

mineralisation will

[Ed Cho colloquialism "throw down"; Zechariah at end of carpal tunnel,

See "Zach Fair" of FF7.]

"but these craftsmen have come to terrify them, to throw down the horns of the nations who have lifted up their horns against the land of Judah in order to scatter it." (Zechariah 1:21)

[Context is Zerubbabel mentioned four times in Zechariah 4:6,7,9,10]

...
"The LORD rebuke you, Satan! Indeed, the LORD who has chosen Jerusalem rebuke you! Is this not a brand plucked from the fire?" (Zechariah 3:2)

...
"The LORD rebuke you, Satan!":

Aleksandr beetroot

buttonhole eureka/drake

...
"Is this not a brand plucked from the fire?":

demineralisation corruptest/tortured/potter

[Bran Stark]

(Zechariah 6:12)

"a man whose name is Branch":

monarch Messiah Anne

"Behold, I am going to send you Elijah the prophet before the coming of the great and terrible day of the LORD." (Malachi 4:5)

...
"the great and terrible day of the LORD":

foreordained Albert herald

[Joseph dreamer Father]

"and to Jacob was born Joseph the husband of Mary, by whom was born Jesus" (Matthew 1:16)

(Matthew 3:1)

"John the Baptist": Phaethon

Matthew 1:23 [Isaiah 7:14] correct

Matthew 2:6 [Micah 5:2] wrong

Matthew 2:15 [Hosea 11:1] wrong

Matthew 2:18 [Jeremiah 31:15] wrong

Matthew 3:3 [Isaiah 40:3] wrong

Matthew 4:4 [Deuteronomy 8:3]

Matthew 4:6 [Psalm 91:11-12]

Matthew 4:7 [Deuteronomy 6:16]

Matthew 4:10 [Deuteronomy 4:10]

"Begone Satan!" (Matthew 4:10) [Satan is M or Mary; therefore, this is not Jesus. Incidence of Deuteronomy and Q source indicates Yahweh attribution.]

Matthew 4:15-16 [Isaiah 9:1-2] wrong

(Matthew 6:28) [Lilian]

"Observe how the lilies of the field grow": floodlight whitehorse

Matthew 8:17 [Isaiah 53:4] wrong

Matthew 9:13 [Hosea 6:6] misquote properly "loyalty"

(Matthew 9:9)

"called Matthew, sitting in the tax office":

falsification Michael weed

[Lilith is Serpent]

(Matthew 10:16)

"be shrewd as serpents, and innocent as doves":

representativeness cannonade/showcase [Cannon is Guan Yin]

[Messiah is "Prince of Peace" (Isaiah 9:6)]

"Do not think that I came to bring peace in earth; I did not come to bring peace, but a sword."

(Matthew 10:34)

Matthew 10:35-36 [Micah 7:6] correct; [Note "serpent" in Micah 7:17]

Matthew 11:5 [Isaiah 35:5-6] inconsistent

Matthew 11:10 [Malachi 3:1] wrong

Matthew 11:29 [Jeremiah 6:16] wrong

Matthew 12:7 [Hosea 6:6] misquote

Matthew 12:18-21 [Isaiah 42:1-4] wrong, misquote

Matthew 12:40 [Jonah 1:17]

Matthew 13:14-15 [Isaiah 6:9-10] correct

(Isaiah 6:9)

"Keep on listening but do not perceive":

religion nonobedience/contentions/conventions/deceptions

[tares, or, darnel, a weed resembling wheat]

"The kingdom of heaven may be compared to a man who sowed good seed in his field. But while men were sleeping, his enemy came and sowed tares also among the wheat, and went away."

(Matthew 13:24-25)

Matthew 13:32 [Ezekiel 31:6; Daniel 4:12] wrong

Matthew 13:34 [Psalm 78:2] correct

(Psalm 78:2)

"I will open my mouth in a parable":

Emanuel impalpability

manipulation hyperbole

...
"I will utter dark sayings of old":

religion tutorial

(Matthew 13:39)

"and the enemy who sowed them is the devil":
dismantlement weed weed soviet
weed weed dishonesty elevation

Matthew 13:43 [Psalm 37:6] correct
[See Psalm 37:2]

(Psalm 37:2)

"For they will wither quickly like the grass,
And fade like the green herb."

Matthew 15:4 [Exodus 20:12, Exodus 21:17] wrong; see primacy of Exodus 20:3.

Matthew 15:8 [Isaiah 29:13] correct

[Lilian]

"Jesus went along by the Sea of Galilee" (Matthew 15:29)

Matthew 16:27 [Jeremiah 17:10] correct

[Right before Chapter 18; J, penny]

"go to the sea, and throw in a hook, and take the first fish that comes up; and when you open its mouth,
you will find a stater [shekel]"
(Matthew 17:27)

...

(Matthew 18:1)

"Who then is greatest in the kingdom of heaven?":
EIGHTEEN FISHHOOK (8666) dethronement/enthronement

Matthew 19:4 [Genesis 1:27] correct

Matthew 19:5 [Genesis 2:24] correct; note one flesh not spirit

Matthew 19:7 [Deuteronomy 24:1] correct

Matthew 19:18 [Exodus 20:13-16] correct

Matthew 19:19 [Exodus 20:12, Leviticus 19:18] correct

[Jesus is the Serpent]

"They said to Him, 'Lord, we want our eyes to be opened.' "
(Matthew 20:33)

"For God knows that in the day you eat from it your eyes will be opened" (Genesis 3:5)

Matthew 21:5 [Zechariah 9:9] wrong; See Numbers 22:22 !

(Numbers 22:5) [BA Lamb]

"Balaam the son of Beor":

ABRAHAM BOSTON

Solomon Barbee/father

(Zechariah 9:9)

"Even on a colt, the foal of a donkey.": Nathanael fooled

Matthew 21:9 [Psalm 118:26] wrong

Matthew 21:13 [Isaiah 56:7, Jeremiah 7:11] correct

Matthew 21:16 [Psalm 8:2] correct

Matthew 21:33 [Isaiah 5:1-2] correct

Matthew 21:42 [Psalm 118:22-23] wrong

Matthew 22:24 [Deuteronomy 25:5] correct

Matthew 22:32 [Exodus 22:32]

wrong

Matthew 22:37 [Deuteronomy 6:5] correct

Matthew 22:39 [Leviticus 19:18] correct

Matthew 22:44 [Psalms 110:1] correct

Matthew 23:39 [Psalm 118:26] correct

[Einstein is German "one stone"]

"Truly I say to you, not one stone here shall be left upon another, which will not be torn
down." (Matthew 24:2)

[Topologize Einstein]

Matthew 24:2 "Einstein" textually near Matthew 24:15 "ABOMINATION OF DESOLATION" from Daniel, same thread. Likewise in Daniel, "one who makes desolate" (Daniel 9:27) near "A king will arise ... And he will destroy to an extraordinary degree" (Daniel 8:23-24), same Messianic thread.

[Topologize Michael]

Also note in Daniel the repeated textual nearness of mentions of "Abomination of Desolation" and Michael, respectively.

Daniel 9:27 and Daniel 10:13.

Daniel 11:31 and Daniel 10:21.

Daniel 12:11 and Daniel 12:1.

Also note textual nearness of "schemes" (Daniel 11:24, 11:25) [N, work of A. Grothendieck Shapiro] and "Kittim" (Daniel 11:30) [J, Hello Kitty] to "abomination of desolation" [K, death] (Daniel 11:31).

[Death takes the soul, by definition]

(Daniel 9:27)

"one who makes desolate":

Death Kowloon

skeleton shadow

Matthew 24:15 [Daniel 9:27, 11:31, 12:11] correct

Matthew 24:29 [Joel 2:10, 3:15, also 2:31] maybe

[Joel 3:10 contradicts Isaiah 2:4,

Joel 3:19 contradicts Isaiah 19:20,

Joel 2:28 supports Isaiah 11:9]

(Joel 2:28)

"That I will pour out My Spirit on all mankind":

AUTOMANIPULATION MILLIONS

IMMORTALISATION UNPOPULARITY

trinitrotoluol antihumanism/illuminati/inhumanity/Nathanial

Matthew 24:30 [Daniel 7:13] correct

Matthew 24:31 [Leviticus 23:24] wrong; possible metaphor

Matthew 26:31 [Zechariah 13:7] correct

(Zechariah 13:7)

"Awake, O sword, against My Shepherd," [echoes Genesis 3:24]

...

"And against the man, My Associate,":

mathematician Odyssean Santa

...

"Declares the LORD of hosts."

...

"Strike the Shepherd that the sheep may be scattered;":

PARASYMPATHETIC ESTHER ESTHER DETESTED

Esther Esther Esther decapitated/thickheaded/decimated/epitaphes/medicated

...

"And I will turn My hand against the little ones."

[Whore ... rabbid rabbit]

(Matthew 26:36)

"Gethsemane": get semen, gametes

Matthew 26:64 [Daniel 7:13] wrong

(Daniel 7:13)

"One like a Son of Man was coming,": kingliness Canaan

...

"And He came up to the Ancient of Days":

authenticate condensed Yah

[Judas Iscariot]

"Potter's Field" (Matthew 27:7)

Matthew 27:9-10 [Zechariah 11:12-13] correct [see Exodus 21:32]

[Siren]

"a man of Cyrene named Simon" (Matthew 27:32)

[Latin calva "bald head" ... Cali]

"Golgotha, which means Place of a Skull" (Matthew 27:33)

[Lot ... see Psalm 22:18]

"casting lots" (Matthew 27:35)

(Psalm 22:16-18)

"For dogs have surrounded me;
A band of evildoers has encompassed me;
They pierced my hands and my feet.
I can count all my bones.
They look, they stare at me;
They divide my garments among them,
And for my clothing they cast lots."

...

[echoes Jezebel]

"For dogs have surrounded me;":

HOMOGENEOUS DEFRAUDS

...

"A band of evildoers has encompassed me;":

ABSALOM comprehensiveness/fearsomeness/archenemies/archimedean/recondenses/renaissance

...

"They pierced my hands and my feet.":

DEATH decipherment/MASTERMINDED/ARCHENEMIES/impeachment/masterpiece/predestined/ARCHFIEND/ARCHIMEDES/
christened/tyranny

death tyranny impeded/misdeed/schemed

...

"I can count all my bones.":

unconscionable

...

[Impossible for David would have been killed, therefore prophetic.]

"They look, they stare at me;":

heatstroke

...

"They divide my garments among them,":

GEORGIA DAVID ENMESHMENT

GEORGIA DYNAMITE vestment

...

"And for my clothing they cast lots.":

CHRISTENDOM OCTAGONAL [RED]

CONDEMNATORY CALLISTO/GOLIATH

Matthew 27:43 [Psalm 22:8] correct

Matthew 27:46 [Psalm 22:1] contradicts Matthew 26:31

(Matthew 27:46)

"ELI, ELI, LAMA SABACHTHANI?":

Michael banalies/Isabella/Lilith/Helen

Lilith Chinese Baal

...

"MY GOD, MY GOD, WHY HAST THOU FORSAKEN ME?":

goddaughter Thomson fakes/sham

[Elijah is death]

"But the rest of them said, 'Let us see whether Elijah will come to save Him.'

And Jesus cried out again with a loud voice, and yielded up His spirit." (Matthew 27:49-50)

(Matthew 27:56)

"Mary Magdalene": German Adam/dame

"Therefore, give orders for the grave to be made secure until the third day, lest the disciples come and steal Him away and say to the people, 'He has risen from the dead,' and the last deception will be worse than the first." (Matthew 27:64)

[Lara Croft; Snow White; resurrection ... re-erection]

"Mary Magdalene and the other Mary came to look at the grave ... his [alleged angelic tomb raider] garment as white as snow" (Matthew 28:1-3)

"Lara Croft Tomb Raider":
fabricator retard
obliterator drama
arbitrator femoral/oracle

[Spiritually false; see Isaiah 54:16.
Physically true; see Isaiah 7:14]
"Jesus, Son of the Most High God" (Mark 5:7)

[Multiplication X]
"How many loaves do you have?" (Mark 6:38)

[X-tians filthy, dark ages ... X rated]
"some of His disciples were eating their bread with impure hands, that is, unwashed." (Mark 7:2)

[dubious]
"Thus He declared all foods clean." (Mark 7:19)

[Q]
"And if your eye causes you to stumble, cast it out" (Mark 9:47)

Mark 9:42, 46, 48 [Isaiah 66:24] correct

[Isaiah 66:24, last verse]
"For their worm shall not die,
And their fire shall not be quenched":
trinitrotoluene feeblemindedness Richard
worldbeater mineralise recondensation fortitude/Detroit
...
"And they shall be an abhorrence to all mankind":
dethronement Aleksandr Babylonian[beast]/Hannibal/Hanoi

[Moral Relativity, Einstein next]
"for they all put in out of their surplus, but she, out of her poverty, put in all she owned, all she had
to live on." (Mark 12:44)

["one stone" Einstein destroyer,
see permuted 2 Samuel 24:18]
"Do you see these great buildings? Not one stone shall be left upon another which will not be torn
down." (Mark 13:2)

[Vampire; descendant of Impaler]
"And He said to them, 'This is My blood of the covenant, which is poured out for many.' " (Mark 14:24)

(Mark 15:7) [analogous]
"Barabbas": Rab's Baba

[Star Trek's Seven of Nine,
Resurrection echoes Matthew]
"He first appeared to Mary Magdalene, from whom He had cast out seven demons." (Mark 16:9)

Luke 1:17 [Malachi 4:6] false; Elijah is Caesar Augustus

"Now it came about in those days that a decree went out from Caesar Augustus, that a census be taken of
all the inhabited earth." (Luke 2:1)

...
"Now again the anger of the LORD burned against Israel, and it incited David against them to say, 'Go,
number Israel and Judah.' " (2 Samuel 24:1)

...
(2 Samuel 24:18)
"threshing floor of Araunah the Jebusite":
Albert Einstein August

Luke 2:32 [Isaiah 42:6, 49:6] false, false

(Isaiah 42:6)
"As a light to the nations":
Thessalonian goat
Nathaniel tattoos/Agosto/ghosts
Agosto annihilates/Athenians/Nathaniel/Leninist

[Yoda] "Joda" (Luke 3:26)

"the son of Adam, the son of God." (Luke 3:38)

Luke 4:18-19 [Isaiah 61:1-2] false

[Echoes Eden and apple ... snake]

"For each tree is known by its own fruit." (Luke 6:44)

[Seven of Star Trek Voyager]

"Mary who was called Magdalene, from whom seven demons had gone out" (Luke 8:2)

[Bethesda's "Black Widow"]

"He withdrew by Himself to a city called Bethsaida."

[Proximity]

(Luke 11:11) "snake"

(Luke 11:12) "scorpion"

(Luke 11:15) "Beelzebul": Belle, Bee

(Luke 11:30) "Jonah" [J]

(Luke 11:31) "Queen of the South" [Sheba, J]

(Luke 11:31) "Solomon"

(Luke 11:32) "Jonah"

(Luke 11:33) "lighting a lamp"

(Luke 11:37) "Pharisee"

...

(Luke 11:51) "blood of Abel" [Cain]

(Luke 11:52) "key of knowledge" [K]

...

(Luke 12:5) "the One"

(Luke 12:6) "sparrows"

(Luke 12:7) "hairs"

(Luke 12:10) "Holy Spirit" [LORD]

[EIGHTEEN mentioned 3x, Bond]

"And this woman, a daughter of Abraham as she is, whom Satan has bound for eighteen long years, should she not have been released from this bond on the Sabbath Day?" (Luke 13:16)

[p. 887, 887 Harcourt,
Alexander A. Karelin 887-2]

(Luke 14:5) "Which one of you shall have a son or an ox fall into a well, and will not immediately pull him out on a Sabbath day?"

[p. 888 The Prodigal Son;

Nicolino Locche]

(Luke 15:15, 21)

"he sent him into his fields to feed swine" [Fields medal Archimedes]

...

"Father I have signed against heaven and in your sight; I am no longer worthy to be called your son."

(Luke 16:1-2)

"this steward was reported to him as squandering his possessions. ... Give an account of your stewardship, for you can no longer be steward."

(Luke 16:23-24)

"And in Hades he lifted up his eyes, being in torment ... dip the tip of his finger in water and cool off my tongue; for I am in agony in this flame."

Luke 22:37 [Isaiah 53:12] wrong

[Georgia]

"gorgeous robe" (Luke 23:11)

Luke 23:30 [Hosea 10:8] correct

Luke 23:46 [Psalm 31:5] wrong

"Cleopas" (Luke 24:18) [Fr: not Cleo]

"the eleven" (Luke 24:33) ... leaven

["John the Baptist": Phaethon]

"Who are you?" (John 1:19)

...

"These things took place in Bethany behind the Jordan, where John was baptizing." (John 1:28)

...

"Nathanael" (John 1:45,46,47,48,49)

[Stewing]

"wedding in Cana of Galilee" (John 2:1) [... Cain, Kay]

"Now there were six stone waterpots set there for the Jewish custom of purification, containing twenty or thirty gallons each." (John 2:6)

[Pot weed cato, hin is 1.5 gallons; mikvah ... immolation, wine ... Pharaoh's cup?]

"Draw some out now, and take it to the headwaiter [8 steward]." (John 2:8)

John 2:17 [Psalms 69:9; according to Shoshannim, or possibly Lilies] wrong [... lotus]

"Nicodemus, a ruler of the Jews" (John 3:1) [Nicotine vice]

"born again" (John 3:3) [reincarnate]

[Numbers 21:8 "serpent...standard"]

"And as Moses lifted up the serpent in the wilderness, even so must the Son of Man be lifted up;" (John 3:14)

[Netanyahu]

" 'I know that Messiah is coming (He who is called Christ); when that One comes He will declare all things to us.' Jesus said to her, 'I who speak to you am He.' " (John 4:25-26)

[Bethesda lame CIA; LOTR "Watcher in the Water" kraken]

"by the sheep gate a pool, which is called in Hebrew Bethesda, having five porticoes. In these lay a multitude of those who were sick, blind, lame, and withered, [waiting for the moving of the waters;" (John 5:2-3)

[Heretic; above the Law, honesty]

"For not even the Father judges anyone, but He has given all judgment to the Son." (John 5:22)

John 6:31 [Exodus 16:4] false; metaphors misleading

John 6:45 [Isaiah 54:13, Jeremiah 31:34] false, false

[Alexander's TNT favorite]

(John 8:32)

"and you shall know the truth, and the truth shall make you free."

...

"the truth shall make you free":

Krystalle author/father/meteor/haute/Homer/Torah

marshal roulette/keyhole/lottery/theft

[Spit, stake, snake, log, word; clay, dust; eye-opener. Genesis 3]

"He spat on the ground, and made clay of the spittle, and applied the clay to his eyes." (John 9:6)

John 10:34 [Psalm 82:6] correct; yet then everyone is a son of God, hence a meaningless distinction, but a meaningful origin

[Kay's relativity]

"Caiaphas, who was high priest that year, said to them, "You know nothing at all, nor do you take into account that it is expedient for you that one man should die for the people, and that the whole nation should not perish." (John 11:49-50)

...

[Not a certainty that nation will perish; by Hebrew Law, this is a wrong reason to kill, bad high priest.

Now killing the innocent certainly will destroy the nation of Israel; the LORD will annihilate them.

By Roman Law Jesus is innocent, by Hebrew Law Jesus is a heretic, worthy of swift death by stoning.]

[Why anoint Jesus for death?]

" 'Why was this perfume not sold for three hundred denarii, and given to poor people?' Now he said this, not because he was concerned about the poor, but because he was a thief" (John 12:5-6)

John 12:38 [Isaiah 53:1] wrong

John 12:40 [Isaiah 6:10] correct; yet misquoted "CONVERTED".

[Cretins]

"He who has bathed needs only to wash his feet, but is completely clean" (John 13:10)

John 13:18 [Psalm 41:9] wrong; David metaphorically misapplied.

John 15:25 [Psalm 69:4] false; blasphemous.

[Female]

"that they may be one, just as We are one; I in them, and Thou in Me, that they may be perfected in unity" (John 17:22-23)

[Cluster Judas's betrayal in garden, садовой, D. SADOWAY, Khazarian Jew?; A.L Flis MIT course 18; Sadoway's Graduate student "Brian Neltner": Berliner Nat N, Lenin beta, Khazarian Jew, Rasputin; "eighteen", Jordan Nosanchuk, Khazarian Jew]
"there was a garden" (John 18:1)

[Sodaway]

"Donald Robert Sadoway":

LATERAL DOORWAY ["my door is always open"]

laboratory endows

analyst wardrobe/adorer/Debra

Boston Edward (88) adora

Toyoda borderlands/Wonderbra

Waterloo brand

Albert Aaron soddy

TREASON DRUGS/ROYAL

BETRAYAL ODORS

Beta sandalwood

bastard woodlander

letdown sorry

Lord Broadway/boatyards/databased/deodorant/tornadoes/downbeat/ratsbane/sanatory/sayonara

...

"ANTICHRIST VASSALS":

narcissists, Vaticanists, anarchists, archivists, Calvinists, Christians, charlatans, racialists, Stalinists

...

"Christ vassals": Issachar, Lhasa, sharia

[Smart]

"Pilate said to Him, 'What is truth?'" (John 18:38)

"Pilate answered, 'What I have written I have written.'" (John 19:22)

John 19:36 [Psalm 34:20] wrong

John 19:37 [Zechariah 12:10] wrong

(Zechariah 12:10) [subsequent]

"and they will mourn for Him":

iliofemoral rhythm

(Zechariah 12:11)

"Hadadrimmon in the plain of Megiddo":

Armageddon iodophthalein [X-ray dye]/definitional/immolation/manifolded/dandelion/Napoleon/Phaethon

...

mineral imagination/Maimonidean/Agamemnon/emanation

diadem nonoperational

dandelion dragon pothead

[Snow White]

"beheld two angels in white" (John 20:12)

[resurrection fishy]

"they were not able to haul it in because of the great number of fish" (John 21:6)

[End Tanakh reference check; later.]

[Breaking Bad]

"breaking bread from house to house" (Acts 2:46)

"they were uneducated and untrained men" (Acts 4:13)

["futile", "vain"; reminiscent of

The Borg's "resistance is futile"]

Acts 4:25-26 [Psalm 2:1-2] false

[Isaiah 7; ruin of Israel prophesy]

"stay away from these men and let them alone, for if this plan or action should be of men, it will be overthrown; but if it is of God you will not be able to overthrow them; or else you may even be found fighting against God." (Acts 5:38-39)

[Saul basket case]

"lowering him in a large basket" (Acts 9:25)

[False]

"solemnly to testify that this is the One who has been appointed by God as Judge of the living and the dead." (Acts 10:42)

[Universalisation; vs tribal nature]

"giving them the Holy Spirit, just as He also did to us; and He made no distinction between us and them, cleansing their hearts by faith." (Acts 15:8-9)

Name Density:

"Lydia, . . . , a seller of purple fabrics" (Acts 16:14)

"Apollonia" (Acts 17:1,11,13)

"Thessalonica" (Acts 17:1)

"Jason" (Acts 17:5,6,7,9)

"TO AN UNKNOWN GOD" (Acts 17:23)

"The Way" (Acts 19:9,23)

"Tyrannus" (Acts 9:23)

"Demetrius, a silversmith" (Acts 19:24,38)

"Artemis" (Acts 9:24,27,28,34,35,38)

"image which fell down from heaven" (Acts 19:35)

"Gaius" (Acts 19:29, 20:4)

"Alexander" (Acts 19:33,33)

"Pyrrhus" (Acts 20:4)

"Thessalonians" (Acts 20:4)

...

"Assos" (Acts 20:13,14)

"Mitylene" (Acts 20:14) [MIT]

"Chios" (Acts 20:15)

"Samos" (Acts 20:15)

"course" (Acts 20:24)

"shrink" (Acts 20:20,27) [for Paul]

[Baptism is heresy, only God pardons sins. Proselytizing is uncustomary, proselytizing heresy is abominable.]

"Arise and be baptized, and wash away your sins, calling on His name." (Acts 22:16)

[CIA]

"it is not the custom of the Romans to hand over any man before the accused meets his accusers face to face, and has an opportunity to make his defense against the charges." (Acts 25:16)

[Pharisee Saul should know spirits can be sent to deceive; see 1 Kings 22:22, Ahab and Jezebel.]

"Paul, you are out of your mind! Your great learning is driving you mad." (Acts 26:24)

[Innocent by Roman Law, heretical traitor by Mosaic Law.]

"Do not be afraid, Paul; you must stand before Caesar" (Acts 27:24)

[Snake, burning logs echos Jezebel]

"But when Paul had gathered a bundle of sticks and laid them on the fire, a viper came out because of the heat, and fastened on his hand." (Acts 28:3)

Paul's Arguments:

(Romans 2:12) Ignorance does not excuse, see Adam, however it can mitigate sentencing.

(Romans 2:13-15) See Deuteronomy 30:6 and 28.

(Romans 2:25) Matter of degree.

(Romans 2:26) No, yet righteous.

(Romans 2:27) Yes.

...

Circumcision is of the flesh, the LORD then circumcises the heart.

[See Deuteronomy 30:6]

...

Without accepting the covenant, hence facing the consequences of disobedience, one cannot reap the rewards of obedience.
[See Deuteronomy 28]

...
"Reason away God's covenant":
wrongness Actaeon

...
"[S]Paul of Tarsus of Cilicia":
calculus tipoff [Nathaniel]
Iscariot fallacious

...
Action and word vs thought.

"'Let us do evil that good may come'? Their condemnation is just." (Romans 3:8)

[zombies]
"present yourselves to God as those alive from the dead" (Romans 6:13)

[Definitional not actual; see Cain]
"for apart from the Law sin is dead." (Romans 7:8)

["Divorcing words from their meanings":
Christianising Mordred wrong]

...
(1 Corinthians 2:13)
"combining spiritual thoughts with spiritual words":
Christianisation wordsmith stillbirth/spotlight/BULLSHIT

[Intimacy is not evil, nor is sex, but fornication.]
"it is good for a man not to touch a woman" (1 Corinthians 7:1)

...
[Paul N is gay, like Catholic priests.]
"But I say to the unmarried and to widows that it is good for them if they remain even as I." (1 Corinthians 7:8)

...
[Good marriage has synergy.]
"his interests are divided ... secure undistracted devotion to the Lord." (1 Corinthians 7:34-35)

...
[Divorce permissible.]
"A wife is bound as long as her husband lives." (1 Corinthians 7:39)

...
VERSUS TORAH

...
"God said to them, 'Be fruitful and multiply.' " (Genesis 1:28)

...
[Keyword SUITABLE]
"Then the LORD God said, 'It is not good for the man to be alone; I will make him a helper suitable for him.' " (Genesis 2:18)

[FALSE; both important]
"Circumcision is nothing, and uncircumcision is nothing, but what matters is the keeping of the commandments of God." (Genesis 7:19)

[misguided guilt]
"eat anything that is set before you, without asking questions for conscience' sake." (1 Corinthians 10:27)

[cattle herder]
"Give no offense... please all men in all things"(1 Corinthians 10:32-33)

[WRONG; man is the head of family, Hebrew women are educated, also have rights.]
"man is the head of a woman" (1 Corinthians 11:3)

...
"Yet your desire shall be for your husband,
And he shall rule over you." (Genesis 3:16)

"Every man who has something on his head while praying or prophesying disgraces his head." (1 Corinthians 11:4)

...
"And for Aaron's sons ... you shall make caps for them, for glory and for beauty." (Exodus 28:40)

"Does not even nature itself teach you that if a man has long hair, it is a dishonor to him" (1 Corinthians 11:14)

...
"the vow of a Nazirite, to dedicate himself to the LORD" (Numbers 6:2)

[1 Corinthians 11:24-25] eucharist;
Notable that Paul's only other direct citation of Jesus is found in
[2 Corinthians 12:9].

"no one speaking by the Spirit of God says, 'Jesus is accursed' " (1 Corinthians 12:3)

...
vs TORAH

...
(Genesis 3:14)

"And the LORD God said to the serpent,":

Alessandro eighteen/dethroned/dehorned/potter/Detroit(253)

ALESSANDRO EIGHTEEN THROOP

Alessandro potter thigh dented

Dorothee antidepressant/degradations/detestation/disentangles/endoparasite/negotiatress/Thessalonian

Dorothee endoparasite(22) DDT/LSD/TNT

...
'Because you have done this,':
acid bathhouse/Beethoven/honeybee
Octavio husband/beheads/Sundays

...
'Cursed are you more than all cattle,':

[Richard at Jaffa in 1191]

COUNTERMEASURE (1191) octahedral/cathedral/charlotte/harlot/Dorthea/deathly/lottery/Rachael/yachter

OCTAHEDRAL EMASCULATORY

LOTTERY CHANCELLORATE/THERMONUCLEAR

Clytemnestra Leucorrhoea [vaginal discharge]/octahedral

Rachael adulterous

AMATERASU ELECTROCAUTERY [excision]

HARCOURT METATARSAL CLOUD

HERCULES AUTOCORRELATED/DEUTERONOMY/documentary

...
'And more than every beast of the field;':

foreordination detestable

dethronement deliberate

TRAVIS NONDEFAMATORY/NONREDEEMABLE

Bethesda deafferentation/reformational

ELEVATES (5444) DEAFFERENTATION [PHANTOM LIMB]/featherbrained/foreordination/Mediterranean/nonhereditary/

dethronement

...
'On your belly shall you go,':

logos honourable/Honolulu

ANGEL BOOHOO

...
'And dust shall you eat':

Ayatollah nudest/sunset

SELLOUT SUNDAY

analyst loathed

...
'All the days of your life;':

Dorothy Ieyasu

Ieyasu fellatory/foolhardy/deflator/deathly

fleurdelis loath/Alfy

LORD FLESH ALFY

alleluia theory

flesh fairytale/laudatory/floodlit

Lord faithful/hateful/hostile/loyalest/outyells/Alyosha

...
(Genesis 3:15)

'And you shall bruise him on the heel.':

demineralise absolute unholy

[Algebraic varieties A.G. Shapiro]

"varieties" (1 Corinthians 12:4,5,6)

[Divine authority usurped, prophets and miracles.]

"And God has appointed in the church, first apostles, second prophets, their teachers, then miracles," (1 Corinthians 12:28)

[Oliver Cromwell]

"and if I deliver my body to be burned" (1 Corinthians 13:3)

...

[P ... vs cupid]

"Pursue love, yet desire earnestly spiritual gifts, but especially that you may prophesy." (1 Corinthians 14:1)

...

[&c] "prophecy" (1 Corinthians 14:6)

[David] "harp" (1 Corinthians 14:7)

[algebraic dual ... dualist]

"But if anyone does not recognize this, he is not recognized." (1 Corinthians 14:38)

[Akira]

"There is one glory of the sun, and another glory of the moon" (1 Corinthians 15:41)

[Trump]

"at the last trumpet; for the trumpet will sound" (1 Corinthians 15:52)

[Alexander]

"Macedonia" (1 Corinthians 16:5)

[Spirit of Detroit statue in lotus;
by Marshall Fredericks,
commissioned August 2, 1955
acidic treatment to oxidize bronze.
"SOD" sodomized in Detroit "the D";
Michigan peninsular.]

...

(2 Corinthians 3:17)

"Now the Lord is the Spirit;":

periodontitis

Throop dentistry/Listerine

...

"and where the Spirit of the Lord is there is liberty.":

lordship worldbeater finisher

hydrosphere territorialise defensible/benefited/entitled

LIFELINE SHITHEAD DISOBEYER WHITEHORSE

Indefeasibility error heliosphere/lithosphere

...

VS

"Alexander self-immolation":

***DEMOTE (2111) MILLENARIAN

NATANIEL MEMORIAL/MISLEADER/Federals

Marianna Sodomite

lifeline (2022) monster Adam

freedom emanation

maxim (4404)

...

elated (2322) iliofemoral

iliofemoral mandates

Israel (2025) monofilament/amontillado

...

Deifies (802) [Friedrich]

Deifies annex aortal

mineral amontillados [A0]

meatloaf mineralised

...

defeat manorialism [slavery]/MILLENARIAN/Armenians/melanoma/Arianism/Iranians/Leninism/Marianne/Marxians/

millions/moronism/Romanism/Lillian/Marxism/Mormons/Riemann

Lillian (2000)

exonerate manifolds

Adamson eliminator/fellation/fellatrix/reinflame

[In Gladiator, Maximus on white horse, adopted by Marcus Aurelius, like Alexander and Aristotle.]

...

"Alexander Luka Flis self immolation":
defeat Maximus alkalise

[education]

"for the weapons of our warfare are not of the flesh, but divinely powerful" (2 Corinthians 10:4)

[Hates Torah]

"Christ redeemed us from the curse of the Law" (Galatians 3:13)

[universalising]

"There is neither Jew nor Greek, there is neither slave nor free man, there is neither male nor female; for you are all one in Christ Jesus." (Galatians 3:28)

[Confuting God Most High with 'Spirit', to justify emotional disobedience of Mosaic Law.
True that command from LORD supercedes, Commandment One.]

...
"But if you are led by the Spirit, you are not under the Law." (Galatians 5:18)

[Riemann sums, integrals ...]

"house of Rimmon" (2 Kings 5:18)]

...
"the summing up of all things in Christ" (Ephesians 1:10)

[Psychological warfare: confusion relabelled divine mystery.]

"you can understand my insight into the mystery of Christ" (Ephesians 3:4)

[Orientalism, Torah pioneered judges and women's rights.]

"But as the church is subject to Christ, so also the wives ought to be to their husbands in everything." (Ephesians 5:24)

[Richard Phillips Feynman ... Clementine Leninist of NY City]

"Indeed, true comrade ... together with Clement also" (Philippians 4:3)

[God endowed man with reason.]

"I say this in order that no one may delude you with persuasive argument." (Colossians 2:4)

[God made the world.]

"See to it that no one takes you captive through philosophy and empty deception, according to the tradition of men, according to the elementary principles of the world, rather than according to Christ." (Colossians 2:8)

[Elon Musk]

"If you have died with Christ to the elementary principles of the world" (Colossians 2:20)

...
"barbarian, Scythian" (Colossians 3:11)

...
[Eighteen]

"Wives, be subject to your husbands" (Colossians 3:18)

...
[Rinoa Heartily FF8; 23 Jordan]

"Whatever you do, do your work heartily" (Colossians 3:23)

...
[Bill Grant]

"Masters, grant to your slaves justice and fairness" (Colossians 4:1)

[p. 1007, James Bond license to kill;
scheme to make Lord into killer]

...
"For the Lord Himself will descend from heaven with a shout, with the voice of the archangel, and with the trumpet of God; and the dead in Christ shall rise first." (1 Thessalonians 4:6)

[Attempt to psychologically justify robbery through false prophesy]

...
"the day of the Lord will come just like a thief in the night." (1 Thessalonians 5:2)

...
"thief" (1 Thessalonians 5:4)

[Ephraim ... David,
See Psalm 60:7, 108:8]

...

"helmet" (1 Thessalonians 5:8)

[p. 1008 Ko]

"the man of lawlessness is revealed, the son of destruction ... displaying himself as being God." (1 Thessalonians 2:3-4)

[Topologize proximity ... Apple]

...

"Macedonia" (1 Timothy 1:3)

...

"Alexander" (1 Timothy 1:20)

...

"Adam ... Eve." (1 Timothy 2:13)

...

"office of overseer" (1 Timothy 3:1)

...

"branding iron" (1 Timothy 4:2)

[false, conniving]

"Do not sharply rebuke an older man, but rather appeal to him as a father, to the younger men as brothers" (1 Timothy 5:1)

[Literal retard Erica Standhart;

"living dead girl" by Rob Zombie of B Boston]

...

"But she who gives herself to wanton pleasure is dead even while she lives." (1 Timothy 5:6)

...

[Ko ... cow DD silicone Standhart]

"YOU SHALL NOT MUZZLE THE OX WHILE HE IS THRESHING" (1 Timothy 5:18)

...

[Nathaniel in TIMothy ... MIT;

MIT communist architecture, similar to FF7's Midgar, a children's game on Sony PlayStation; Star Trek "Seven", 7 of 9, DD Borg.

...

[Seven ... sneaking; NB of Boston]

"Therefore whoever kills Cain, vengeance will be taken on him sevenfold." (Genesis 4:15)

...

(Genesis 4:15)

"sign for Cain": signorina

...

Carl Friedrich Gauss

Erica (E, retard) vs Frieda (J, Euler)

b. 1777 d. 1855 at 77 years old.

"Prince of Mathematicians";

Electric (E) and Magnetic (B) fields;

Student Riemann ... Rimmon (K);

...

Gauss neighbor to Flis,

standard guitar tuning E/B,

NASB 1977 "New American Standard Bible",

Brighton dancing Joshua White, also Erica Standhart;

...

"Also seven priests shall carry seven trumpets of rams' horns before the ark; then on the seventh day you shall march around the city seven times, and the priests shall blow the trumpets." (Joshua 6:4)

...

["Shiloh" (Genesis 49:10)]

"behold, if the daughters of Shiloh come out to take part in the dances" (Judges 21:21)

...

"Cursed is he who gives a wife to Benjamin" (Judges 21:18)

...

[Limb ... Lamb ... Sodomized rape]

"he took a knife and laid hold off his concubine and cut her in twelve pieces, limb by limb, and sent her throughout the territory of Israel." (Judges 19:29)

...

[Ravenous; GOT "three eyed raven", Bran, brand, Branch ...

Bran crippled at youth by Jamie]

"Benjamin is a ravenous wolf" (Genesis 49:27)]

...

"The sins of some men are quite evident" (1 Timothy 5:24)

...

[FF7's Cloud Strife in SOLDIER,
"And the LORD said to Moses, 'Behold, I shall come to you in a thick cloud'"(Exodus 19:9)]

...
"No soldier in active service entangles himself in the affairs of everyday life, so that he may please the one who enlisted him as a soldier." (2 Timothy 2:4)

...
[Jae (J) and James (K)]
"And just as Jannes and Jambres opposed Moses" (2 Timothy 3:8)

...
[Erica ... GOT's "reek" of torture]
"ears" (2 Timothy 4:3,4)

...
[MIT course numbers, librarian N]
"I have finished the course" (2 Timothy 4:7)

...
"Alexander the coppersmith ... vigorously opposed our teaching" (2 Timothy 4:14-15)

...
["Sabrina" w. Audrey Hepburn,
cloud ... Claudian dynasty]
"Corinth ... Linus and Claudia" (2 Timothy 4:20-21)

...
[88th largest island, Cretins, Christians, Xtians]
"Crete" (Titus 1:5)

...
[TITUS ... Tit ... DD scheme]
"For the overseer must be above reproach as God's steward" (Titus 1:7)

...
" 'Cretans are always liars, evil beasts, lazy gluttons.' This testimony is true." (Titus 1:12-13)

...
[DD's ... Dunkin Donuts of Boston]
"both their mind and their conscience are defiled. They profess to know God, but by their deeds they deny Him, being detestable and disobedient, and worthless for any good deed." (Titus 1:15-16)

...
"strife" (Titus 3:9) [Cloud Strife FF7]

...
[Commissioned by Octavio 29 BCE to commemorate victory of Octavio over M. Antony and Cleopatra ...
victory, Nike herald, Elijah;
Nike sneakers Kay, ... Octavio's cain.
Nicolis, nicotine, Niccolo Poli ...
If Alexander consorts he's steward.]

...
"Nicolis" (Titus 3:12)

[Philemon ... Phil of "Hercules", Rinoa Heartily of FF8]
"sending my very heart" (Philemon 1:12)

[DD Boob scheme:
partner heroine Jae ... Jael,
Dibrova trident ... Deborah,
Euler Rd. of Brighton near Sal's,
"bottle of milk" (Judges 4:19)]

...
"For everyone who partakes only of milk is not accustomed to the word of righteousness, for he is a babe." (Hebrews 5:13)

[Child's intuition vs mistrained discernment ?]
"But solid food is for the mature, who because of practice have their senses trained to discern good and evil." (Hebrews 5:14)

[Priest of God Most High vs Yahweh; also Cohen were damned for embezzlement, hence Rabbis.

...
[Potholder, weed ... Shiloh]
"Then he would thrust it into the pan, or kettle, or caldron, or pot; all that the fork brought up the priest would take for himself. Thus they did in Shiloh to all the Israelites who came there." (1 Samuel 2:14)

...
"there will not be an old man in your house" (1 Samuel 2:31)

...
"an old man will not be in your house forever" (1 Samuel 2:32)

...

"all the increase of your house will die in the prime of life" (1 Samuel 2:33)

...

Alexander maternally Cohen from Marianna, who's father died young.]

...

"what further need was there for another priest to arise according to the order of Melchizedek, and not be designated according to the order of Aaron?" (Hebrews 7:11)

[Loathes Torah; word of LORD is perfect.]

"setting aside of a former commandment because of its weakness and uselessness (for the Law made nothing perfect)" (Hebrews 7:18-19)

[Nonsense]

"For a covenant is valid only when men are dead" (Hebrews 9:17)

[False]

"it is appointed for men to die once and after this comes judgment" (Hebrews 9:27)

[Bond]

"discipline ... yields the peaceful fruit of righteousness" (Hebrews 12:11)

[Prodigy P "Shook Ones Pt. 2; blue fire, toss dice]

"those things which cannot be shaken may remain" (Hebrews 12:27)

...

"for our God is a consuming fire." (Hebrews 12:29)

[James Bond; see discipline, yields]

"James, a bond-servant of God" (James 1:1)

"But if you have bitter jealousy and selfish ambition in your heart" (James 3:14)

...

[Chaos]

"there is disorder and every evil thing." (James 3:16)

"will consume your flesh like fire" (James 5:3)

...

"anointing him with oil in the name of the Lord" (James 5:14)

"Elijah" (James 5:17)

[metaphorical rebirth]

"born again" (1 Peter 1:23)

"manifold grace of God" (1 Peter 4:10)

[False]

"If you are reviled for the name of Christ, you are blessed" (1 Peter 4:14)

[Slandering prophet]

"having followed the way of Balaam, the son of Beor, who loved the wages of unrighteousness" (2 Peter 2:15)

[Baloney]

"Paul ... speaking in them of these things, in which are some things hard to understand, which the untaught and unstable distort" (2 Peter 3:15-16)

(1 John 2:18)

"antichrist is coming":

Christianising Oct

[Comics; X-Men]

"marvel" (1 John 3:13)

[Notable proximity]

"Gaius" (3 John 1)

...

"Demetrius" (3 John 12)

...

"shall speak face to face" (3 John 14)

[Notable mention; see Daniel 12:1]

"Michael the archangel" (Jude 9)

[Trump]

"a loud voice like the sound of a trumpet" (Revelation 1:10)

[Sardis (drama, Broadway), sardines, Sardinian (mobster)]

...

[NYC W44th St, p. 1043]

"Sardis" (Revelation 1:11)

...

[p. 1044]

"Jezebel" (Revelation 2:20)

[K nicotine]

"keys of death and of Hades" (Revelation 1:18)

...

"Nicolaitans" (Revelation 2:6, 15)

[On life support in Pasadena at Caltech]

"the tree of life, which is in the Paradise of God" (Revelation 2:7)

[Breaking Bad:

Mr. White with Skylar is Beta]

"white stone, and a new name" (Revelation 2:17)

[Teacher Richard Lamb CK CS possibly albino;

Richard the Lionhearted opponent of Saladin]

...

"Lion" (Revelation 5:5)

...

"Lamb" (Revelation 5:6, 12)

...

"riches" (Revelation 5:12)

[MIT Scheme 6.001 Lambda-calculus]

"Lamb" (Revelation 6:1)

...

"white horse" (Revelation 6:2)

[Repeal Revelation, analyst insane;

Revelation 8-9 (WORLD WAR III)

vs Isaiah (world peace);

1/3=.3333333333 Trinity]

...

"a third of the earth was burned up" (Revelation 8:7)

"a third of the sea became blood" (Revelation 8:8)

"a third of the creatures, which were in the sea and had life, died" (Revelation 8:9)

"a third of the ships were destroyed" (Revelation 8:9)

"a third of the waters became wormwood" (Revelation 8:11)

"a third of the sun and a third of the moon and a third of the stars were smitten" (Revelation 8:12)

...

"kill a third of mankind"

(Revelation 9:15)

"A third of mankind was killed" (Revelation 9:18)

...

"And I took the little book out of the angel's hand and ate it, and it was in my mouth sweet as honey; and when I had eaten it, my stomach was made bitter." (Revelation 10:10)

[Mortal Kombat ghouls, killing God]

"scorpions" (Revelation 9:10)

...

[9/11/2001 ... 001 becomes police;

Twin towers, pillars falling, radical attack on Minoru Yamasaki's art.

New One World Trade Center:

Cubic base, eight tall isosceles triangles ... HK triad; near its middle, a perfect octagon ... Octavio] (Revelation 9:11)

"Abaddon ... Apollyon":

Bond Lapland

[Confuting to evade blame:

dragon is N, Nemesis or Leviathan;
serpent is G, Jesus or Lilian;
devil is K, Killer or Death;
Satan is M, Adversary or Metatron]

...
"And the great dragon was thrown down, the serpent of old who is called the devil and Satan, who deceives the whole world" (Revelation 12:9)

[trader ... WTC]
"to buy or sell" (Revelation 13:17)

...
"the number of the beast ... is six hundred and sixty-six" (Revelation 13:18)

...
"Now the weight of gold which came in to Solomon in one year was 666 talents of gold" (1 Kings 10:14, also 2 Chronicles 9:13)

...
[Solomon means "peaceful", aka "Jedidiah" (2 Samuel 12:25).]

[Notable since LG is an idol]
"sea of glass" (Revelation 15:2)

[Seven ... bowls of weed]
"seven angels seven golden bowls full of the wrath of God" (Revelation 15:7)

...
"seven bowls" (Revelation 16:1)

...
"bowl" (Revelation 16:2, 3, 4, 8, 10, 12, 17)

...
[Armageddon or death of Odin;
End of the world;
666 or 616]
"Har-Magedon" (Revelation 16:16)

"great harlot" (Revelation 17:1)

...
[Gone with the Wind's Scarlett O'Hara, ... scarlet (red), scarab (and sun), Iscariot (blue)]
"a woman sitting on a scarlet beast" (Revelation 17:3)

...
"BABYLON THE GREAT" (Revelation 17:5)

...
"Nebuchadnezzar king of Babylon has devoured me and crushed me,
He has set me down like an empty vessel;
He has swallowed me like a monster" (Jeremiah 51:34)

...
"And let a beast's mind be given to him,
And let seven periods of time pass over him" (Daniel 4:16)

[Bait tattoo]
"And on His robe and on His thigh He has a name written, 'KING OF KINGS, AND LORD OF LORDS.'" (Revelation 19:16)

...
"KING OF KINGS AND LORD OF LORDS":
Floridian folksong [shaped like gun, see JNF permutations, gators]

...
"Circle with a nested loop":
Phaeton elicitor/wrestled/Lord
"Circle and loop":
Lord (333) cocaine

...
"The LORD will smite you with ... inflammation" (Deuteronomy 28:22)

...
"you shall flee seven ways before them, and you shall be an example of terror to all the kingdoms of the earth." (Deuteronomy 28:25)

"crystal" (Revelation 22:1)
"yielding its fruit" (Revelation 22:2)

[Stilgar of Dune]

"Let the one who does wrong, still do wrong; and let the one who is filthy, still be filthy; and let the one who is righteous, still practice righteousness; and let the one who is holy, still keep himself

holy." (Revelation 22:11)

...

[Done ... Dune, by Frank Herbert]

"Behold, I am coming quickly, and My reward is with Me, to render to every man according to what he has done.

I am the Alpha and the Omega, the first and the last, the beginning and the end." (Revelation 22:12-13)

...

[fatal in Dune]

"let the one who wishes take the water of life without cost." (Revelation 22:17)

Eve, eavesdropper

ode, Odo, Odey Meroueh, Odysseus (string bow, shoot through twelve axeheads)

Telemachus, Manchu

Shogun, hog

Stewing (mixing, pot), stupid, stoop, steward

Florida (alligator, gun ... wife J), Fluoride (F radical)

Beta, Bethesda (MD), beat (down)

David hexahedron (cop badge, Coptic or Egyptian, MIT coop, coup, Copley, copulate, Coco puff),

hexadecimal (base 666), hex (accursed)

Archimedes (death ray... death star)

Alpha-Simplex (triadic, Andy Lo)

naughty (forbidden), knots (DNA), NOT (logic)

James, Jae

Andromeda, android, Medea, Archimedes

machine, China, Hin

Grinch, Grinner

Yahweh, Yah, Job pronounced Yob, Japanese greeting Yo

Jesus, Jezebel

Ganja, gang

Barbed, Barbee, barber, barbaric, Arbor

Hippocratic, hypocrite

Pathogen, pathologic, pathos, path, pater, pattern

Metaphor, mater, mate

Sense, sanus, sane

Biologic [oo "rotated"], c.io

Grounder, rounder, ground zero

Index, identity, indus, induce

Om, womb

A0, AlphaZero, alphazone

Terran, tyrannosaur, tyre

Pharaoh [cobra hat, flail and crook], Egypt, gypsum [sets]

Mule, emulator, colt, colonel, kernel

Pet, petulant [Leviathan]

K-night, chivalrous, chevalier, cavalier

Alexander, De-fender of man

MAXIMS

Pressure makes a diamond.

Most people are deliberately dumbed down.

Research and education are collaborative enterprises, not brutalist survival.

Something feels wrong it is.

Enemies try to steal your heart.

Debase society with flawed values.

E.g. Hindu caste hierarchy ranks virtue: scholars, warriors, merchants, and cleaners.

Torah is scholarly education.

Yet cyclically, clearheadedness and humility elevate the soul.

Commerce funds research.

...

Why Chinese now dominate technical universities.

You are not your mistakes you are how you react to them.

Forget insults, remember kindnesses.

Delighting in war is evil.
War destroys, peace nurtures.

Trust in the Lord, for even your self efficacy flows from Him.

Passover is repayment for pharaoh killing the firstborn of Israel.

Blood runs thicker than ink.

Love and hated are on the same coin. Indifference is antithesis of love.

Conservative action and values.

Devote yourself to a subject to learn it.

The greatest pain is spiritual.

Idols trap souls.

Laughter is honest.

Virtue vs vice is God's commandments.

Attack philosophy not people.

Meta thinking and meta feeling.

The jaws of death lie under the wrong skirt.

Let the dust settle.

Not once did Samson harm innocents.

Can you remove conscience?
How intelligent and educated must one be to know right from wrong?
And how much intelligence and education does it take to forget?
The test of a man is morality.

Easy to do, hard to undo.

Prefer a sharp wit to a sharp sword.

Truelove conquers all.

Death is swift, cowardice lasting.

An enemy can be trusted a traitor cannot.

Cowardice betrays the heart.

Optimizing over uncertainty is polishing the Titanic.

If you do not rigorously know how well something can be known, you pursue it until you do. Naysayers are often wrong.

Easier to destroy than create, hard to destroy precisely.

Depth and breath seldom unite.

Teach a child to speak only mathematics.

Wisdom is dull.

Think before speaking.

Think long term.

Strong emotions lack discernment.

"The most powerful weapon":
FEAR unwholesome

The test of love is reasoned confirmation.

What is more insidious than miseducation? And from where comes knowledge of what is right?
Honeyed words consume souls.

Hate behavior not man, redeem your neighbor redeem yourself.

We see what we want to see.

Tendency of power corrupting character for lack of reproof.

Freewill is limited.

Timelessness is beyond innovation, like reinventing the wheel.

Confusion is healthy.
Yet a focus on grades makes people afraid. The solution is half structure and half play.

Blows are often unnoticed.

Higher loves than women, and higher motives than love.

Yolk a cow with eyes donut glazed, reduce man to mush.

Christianity feminizes man.

Compound interest.

Genius and pride do not coincide.

You are what you eat.

Learning is a double edged sword.
[David]
Lose your mind to ground it in the origin.
Nothing is more cruel than denying identity.
Discover something with no name attached.

Race religion and politics are like drugs.

Feelings are irrelevant what you do counts.

No anger for sheep.

Adults can feel and not do.

Existence measured by pain.

VERACITY PING?

Find me an honest criminal.
Enemies you can depend on.
Evil lurks in daylight.
True folly means well.
True patriots distrust government.

Alexander means defender of man, from James, with no gratitude.
Every possible way, something is constant.
Woman, without man [outside of].
Women are vessels.

Meditations

...
Alexander dinosaur, not a knight, not chivalrous. Defender of his own God, family, and country first.
...
Nothing evil about consorts. Reality is polygamy splinters families.
Alexander has honest love but does not crave sexuality or diversity, would rather avoid future headache, make ditzy wife happy.
Willing to consort if spiritually or politically necessary, *not at the cost of His soul*, as service to LORD is paramount before women.
Similar to Sarah, Jordan's behavior contributed to current plurality through her absence and conniving.
So did Alexander's deception by Michael.
Difference with Sarah is contract is not signed in blood, no oath given.
LORD said "Jordan", also said "choose three".
Bound by choice to honor old wives, possibly consort.
Defensive preference is to avoid, although Alexander knows Georgia and Virginia mean well.
Everyone means well, why the world is full of chaos.
Wait for further judgement from the LORD, keeping faith with Oakland.
...
Chivalry is a code empowering women to connive men.
Chivalry, cavalier

Great villains have redeeming characteristics, which they refuse to redeem.
E.g. Star Wars' Palpatine.

Remember the ARGO, ergo, ergot, therefore, implies.
Arg-o argument zero,
argument w. Medea.

[Arg-o nauts]
Argonauts:
Alexander relatives:
Schrodinger, Kelvin, Banach, Hilbert.

"Verified via exposition":
proof divinities
Aeneid vitrifies/positive/spoofers

[No banana]
"Schrodinger Kelvin Banach Hilbert":
earn occidentalising/valedictories/billionaires/brilliances/denicotinise/vinordinaire
earn denicotinise black

...
transcendence kohlrabi/gorilla/Virgil
brilliant (6001) convergences/codebreaker/Richardson/recondense/renascence
interbranch indiscoverable
BRILLIANCE KINDERGARTENS
birdcage elevation
denicotinise archangel
recondensing Alastair/arbiter/baseball/Hebraist
vindication researcher
VINORDINAIRE CANCELLERS
Richardson intelligence/belligerent/enthralling/leatherneck/achilleine/challenger/inelegance/liberating/
reteaching/rethinking/viceregent
ARGO chickenhearted/brainchildren/transcendence/electricians/TRIVALENCIES/tiebreaker

887

Srinivasa Ramanujan Aiyangar[a] FRS (22 December 1887 – 26 April 1920)

P. C. Mahalanobis posed a problem:
"Imagine that you are on a street with houses marked 1 through n."

Good Will Hunting.
Professor Gerald Lambeau (Stellan Skarsgård) explains to Sean Maguire (Robin Williams) the genius of Will

Hunting (Matt Damon) by comparing him to Ramanujan.

[Finish LOTR...Lot Characters,
not perfect but not trivial correspondence.
e.g. king of dead army M,
Theoden K, Sauron N, ring Georgia.]

...
"One ring to rule them all":
thermoregulation
Hanoi Elenore
Ariel torment
enthroned gorilla

"Why M betrayed L":
wreathed/Demetra/Albert/breath/Hebrew/hatred/helmet/herald/blame/death/rhyme/herb/lamb/meta/weed/Yah

...
Yah trembled/trebled
herald byte
byte whaler
herb medal
weed math
Meta herb

J descendant of Atilla the Hun.
M had a dog named Atilla.

Cain and Abel
Definition of barbarism
human behavioral pattern
1. Lack of knowledge
2. Emotion
3. Violent action.

Interestingly mammals are often ignorant and emotional yet do not exhibit human violence.
Humans having the capacity for abstraction yet misusing it to kill, are not animals sometimes more
righteous thus more worthy of salvation like in Noah's Arc?

AXIOMATIZING BEHAVIOR

Human social humor can be axiomatized into a first order formal logical system, i.e. prove something is
funny.

Similarly human behavior can be axiomatized to fundamentals.

Human female and male courtship behaviors can be condensed into algorithms.

Axiomatized human humor is based on violation of social standards, i.e. on bad behavior. Humans are
highly socially linked.

Human societal behavioral norms common to all cultures can be axiomatized.

These norms are all in the Torah.

How does the New Testament attempt to nullify axiomatic social norms from the Torah?

What features of the legal structure of the Torah are unusual?

To what extent is the US Constitution based on the Torah?

...
Constitution axiomatically fundamentally based on Torah with key exception of amendability.
By design US founders referenced Torah, citing God but not including because of Christian splintering.
God's law is timeless, complete, and extremely effective at generating success, demonstrated by "American
Exceptionalism".
Rather, Israel is God's chosen, partly scattered in the USA.

ChatGPT Ethics.

The fundamental principle in authorship is tracing originality.
Err toward acknowledgement, cheating does not pay.

Must understand to consent.

If ChatGPT contributes half the substance, it is half the author.

AXIOMATIZE US CONSTITUTION

as a minimal set of principles and meta-principles.

ChatGPT:

```
{  
Meta Principles [ideals]  
1. Popular Sovereignty - authority derives from consent.  
2. Limited Government - powers enumerated and limited.  
3. Separation of Powers - distinct branches.  
4. Checks and Balances - mutual oversight.
```

Principles

```
1. Rule of Law - supremacy of and equality under law.  
2. Individual Rights - protected fundamental rights.  
3. Federalism - division of sovereignty.  
4. Amendability - structured self change.  
}
```

0. Unstated meta principle

Tendency of power corrupting character for lack of reproof.

False Axioms:

1. Free will.

Free will is limited by God. Thus, some authority derives from God.

And if a degree of choice is given by God, choice should be honored, not manipulated.

Thus the mechanisms for its impedance should be well known, as recorded in the Bible.

2. Change.

God's law is timeless and complete.

[Standhart plagiarist assimilator]

ON SLAVERY

Overcoming imposed hardship provides a claim to glory and teaches humility and empathy, but it does not justify the imposition.

The pursuit of glory is a vain idol, the pursuit of substance a reward in itself. Reconquering mundane problems, reinventing the wheel of righteousness every generation is insanity. Lessons refine character, but the wise need less refinement, learning from others' lessons, not on their own skin.

Appraise the landscape of intellectual depth and aim high, better to fall short than not fully try, for surely the soul dies living a lie. Reason is cowardice's best disguise, the years of folly multiply, children know their hearts inside.

Race based slavery is a relic from Moses's time in Egypt; the Romans were more egalitarian. Hiding abuse behind colored statistics is abominable. Intelligence is multifaceted, perhaps Africans have a different genetic proclivity than Europeans. Ancient Sumerians were the first, they survive in every clock. However with abuse, even intellectual genius can be ground to mediocrity.

Men meet the bar set for them.

Lowering standards dilutes quality, and who wants to be indebted to charity? To uplift a people you educate the youth and remove obstacles. Focus on equality of opportunity not outcome. Socioeconomic success alone is survival not achievement. Race based prejudice and its corollary favoritism is absurd when you consider African Americans are on average ~30% genetically white. Any reduction in average IQ for this populace is thus likely grounded in behavior.

The thesis of Christianity is man is not defined by his worst actions.

Then is he not also not defined by his best? What then should history note, what man himself forgets?

Does this not lower the bar universally, debasing man God's creation, offering insult to divinity?

Judgement is the LORD'S.

Champions own their mistakes.

Man's worst often has a defining impact on character and life. The worst can evince the best and worst

in man; it can necessitate the best, but it is not necessary. Pressure can be simulated. Mercy undeserved invites disobedience, as lack of consequence invites the complacency of mediocrity. History esteems society by its brightest lights and its endurance, shadows of virtue and righteousness.

TANAKH FALSIFICATION

By secular reasoning, explicit inconsistency is exceptionally rare, and considering the people, context, and changes, most likely deliberate.
By religious reasoning, the LORD permitted tampering to be recorded yet corrected, leaving a fingerprint.

#1. Esau's wives [changed to favor Judah]

"And when Esau was forty years old he married Judith the daughter of Beeri the Hittite, and Basemath the daughter of Elon the Hittite, and they brought grief to Isaac and Rebekah." (Genesis 26:34-35)

"So Esau saw that the daughters of Canaan displeased his father Isaac; and Esau went to Ishmael, and married, besides the wives that he had, Mahalath the daughter of Ishmael, Abraham's son, the sister of Nebaioth." (Genesis 28:8-9)

"Esau took his wives from the daughters of Canaan; Adah the daughter of Elon the Hittite, and Oholibamah the daughter of Anah and the granddaughter of Zibeon the Hivite; also Basemath, Ishmael's daughter, the sister of Nebaioth."
(Genesis 36:2-3)

The first account is altered. Why?
Judith implies Judaism, these are times former. Why would a woman be named for Jacob's boy, and why would Esau marry her? To attempt to reestablish a lost claim in Judah.

Considering word permutations,
Basemath ... math.
"Gilgamesh": Ismael, sire of Arabia, ... algebra.
Oholibamah ... Obama, known for honesty.

#2. Solomon's Stables [40K vs 4K]

"And Solomon had 40,000 stalls of horses for his chariots, and 12,000 horsemen." (1 Kings 4:26)
"Now Solomon had 4,000 stalls for horses and chariots and 12,000 horsemen, and he stationed them in the chariot cities and with the king in Jerusalem." (2 Chronicles 9:25)

Chronicler understates both stalls and king, men do not share steeds.

#3. Judah not assigned kingship, but the king's staff, a marshall's rod.

"The scepter shall not depart from Judah,
Nor the ruler's staff from between his feet,
Until Shiloh comes" (Genesis 49:10)

[Drink is not for kings, nor milk for men grown. (Proverbs 31:4, Judges 4:19)]
"His eyes are dull from wine,
And his teeth white from milk." (Genesis 49:12)

[staff vs crown]
"May they be on the head of Joseph,
And on the crown of the head of the one distinguished among his brothers." (Genesis 49:26)

"Let it come to the head of Joseph,
And to the crown of the head of the one distinguished among his brothers," (Deuteronomy 33:16)

"Though Judah prevailed over his brothers and from him came the leader, yet the birthright belonged to Joseph," (1 Chronicles 5:2)

"Ephraim also is the helmet of My head;
Judah is My scepter." (Psalm 60:7, 108:8).

...
"Ephraim also is the helmet of My head":
Alasteir (3222) misemployed/polymath/sleepyhead
sleepyhead mesothelioma
Messiah haloperidol
Mithridates employee

...
"Judah is My scepter": miseducates, pasteurised, supremacist, Archimedes, eucharists, Christmas,
impeached, Demetrius, deputise, Jeremiah
physics majeure/remade
Messiah (180) decrypt/deputy/pyre

"And He put on righteousness like a breastplate,
And a helmet of salvation on His head" (Isaiah 59:17)

[Ephrathite, ... Ephraim]
"Now David was the son of the Ephrathite of Bethlehem in Judah, whose name was Jesse" (1 Samuel 17:12)

"Ephrathites of Bethlehem in Judah" (Ruth 1:2)

"David of Ephraim":
DIADEM (108) HARP [Psalm 108:8]
"David of Judah": VOID, jihad, Fuji, judo

...
[minimal phrasing, p. 600 NASB]
"David Ephraim": diadem harp vi
"David Judah": jihad

"Eliakim the son of Hilkiah" (Isaiah 22:20):
Mikael fishhook

[Set the Key, Egyptian god of chaos.
David of Ephraim kin to Pharaoh.
Sêth (Σήθ) Riemann sums, "Rimmon" (2 Kings 5:18).
Set the key of a harp.
Harpy Mikael plaguing Phineus in Jason and the Argonauts.]

...
"Then I will set the key of the house of David on his shoulder" (Isaiah 22:22)

...
[Phishing scam]
"key of the house of David":
fishhook defeated

David's hexahedron (cop badge, Coptic or Egyptian, MIT coop, coup, Copley, copulate, Coco puff),
hexadecimal (base 666), hex (accursed)

Egypt (House of Ptah ... n̄ar (bird), Holy Ghost), Egyptian eagle of Saladin ... Aladdin.

18 Years!

#1. "And the sons of Israel served Eglon the king of Moab eighteen years." (Judges 3:14)

...
Proximity to "Deborah, a prophetess, the wife of Lappidoth" (Judges 4:4),
"Jael the wife of Heber the Kenite" (Judges 4:17).

#2. "for eighteen years they afflicted all the sons of Israel who were beyond the Jordan" (Judges 10:8)

...
Proximity to "Jair the Gileadite" (Judges 10:3).

#3. "there was a woman who for eighteen years had had a sickness caused by a spirit" (Luke 13:11)

...
Also "eighteen" in Luke 13:4,16.

[Don Quixote]
(Numbers 24:3)

"The oracle of Balaam the son of Beor":
bachelors (1886) betatron/Abraham

[Jacob Israel ben Isaac]
"Alexander Oleg Daniv":
dandelion larvae

[M Pinewood]
(Genesis 30:37)
"exposing the white which was in the rods":
WATER PHOTSENSITISING/toxigenicities/denicotinises/osteogenetic/geneticist/idiogenetic
photosensitizing cheater
WATER GENETICS PINWOOD
whitewashes nephrotoxicities [alcoholic]/estrogenicities/indiscretions/christening/conditioner/
sheepherding

[mouth watering]
"and they mated when they came to drink." (Genesis 30:38)

[metaphorical patterns]
"So the flocks mated by the rods, and the flocks brought forth striped, speckled, and spotted." (Genesis
30:39)

[strong trained to follow white rod]
"Moreover, it came about whenever the stronger of the flock were mating, that Jacob would place the rods
in the sight of the flock in the gutters, so that they might mate by the rods" (Genesis 30:41)

Photosensitising is conditioned association, like mouth watering advertisement, or mental behavioral
trigger.

Maimonides [Saladin's physician]
Treatise on Poisons and Their Antidotes

...
"Moses ben Maimon Rambam":
ANAEROBIOSES [M ancient]
membranes boson [M Theory]
ribosomes banana/mamba
MARIANNA EMBOSOM
NEMESIS MAMA
RIEMANN BABA
Messiae baboon/bamboo/maomao/maroon/Aaron
Barbie Samson
earn Samson

...
"Alexander self immolation":
Maimonidean foretells
[not prophecy]
Yet prophets Isaiah, Haggai, Malachi not included in permutation.

"James fucked Jordan":
eureka Jason
Kaufman decodes/scored/dosed
Aaron deduces/seduced
Cane defrauds

"Jordan and James": Andromeda

...
Archimedean spiral, water pump. Euler's e^it, Euler or Cornu spiral.
Octopus seemingly alien.
Mitochondrial symbiote is universal genetic code exception.

...
James, Jae ... Cranbrook rainbow
Andromeda, android, Medea, Archimedes, Noah's Arc.
machine, China
Hin, Kor. Biblical vol, ... vola

...
E.g.1 Star Trek DS9
Jadzia spotted ... Israel,
Dax symbiote.
Marries Klingon Worf,
12450 Klinger St., "cling to LORD".

...
e.g.2 Mortal Kombat
Outworld vs Earth
Sub-Zero vs Scorpion.
Or evil Shao Khan and Shang Tsung.

e.g.3 GOT
ice cold "Night King": Hin Ting K
e.g.4 Star Wars
Emperor Palpatine vs Vader half machine,
Sith homeworld Korriban.
e.g.5 Dragonball-Z (loose)
Frieza vs fiery Saian Goku.

Biblical volume
"hin" (Exodus 29:40, Exodus 30:24; Numbers 15:5)
"kor" (1 Kings 4:22, 1 Kings 5:11)

"Used clothing": ungodliest, unholyest
"Then the Spirit of the LORD came upon him mightily, and he went down to Ashkelon and killed thirty of them and took their spoil, and gave the changes of clothes to those who told the riddle." (Judges 14:19)

Supranational. Yah upholds the West and all alphabetic languages.

No stewing.
"You shall not breed together two kinds of your cattle; you shall not sow your field with two kinds of seed, nor wear a garment upon you of two kinds of material mixed together." (Leviticus 19:19)

Biblical Voodoo
"So it came about when Moses held his hand up, that Israel prevailed, and when he let his hand down, Amalek prevailed." (Exodus 17:11)
"You should have struck five or six times, then you would have struck Aram until you would have destroyed it. But now you shall strike Aram only three times." (2 Kings 13:19)

Biblical Immolation; burning desire
"If there is a man who marries a woman and her mother, it is immorality; both he and they shall be burned with fire, that there may be no immorality in your midst." (Leviticus 20:14)
"Also the daughter of any priest, if she profanes herself by harlotry, she profanes her father; she shall be burned with fire." (Leviticus 21:9)

"And on this mountain He will swallow up the covering which is over all peoples,
Even the veil which is stretched over all nations." (Isaiah 25:7)
Deception is expected, not to be personalised; at least Christians believe in something.
Newton Leviathan N, Einstein Killer K, Jesus Snake G are not slouches.

Idols: unbreakable marriage, indivisible trinity, soul splitting.
Anti-divorce to tether me to abuse.

A point of logic and geography.

...
China is K's country, not K.
Not Christian, a banned subversive cult reserved for export.

Religions are Confucianism, Taoism, and Buddhism.
Government is Maoism lite not the great leap forward.
Capitol is Beijing not Hong Kong. Language Mandarin not Cantonese.

...
Neither has K always followed N, but for jealousy, which would lead to "revelational" World War III.

Mosaic law sets the foundation for capitalism. Nathaniel's hard communism is naturally antithetical, likewise Christian ideals of relative moralism and universalism. Span of life in David's time was 70 years, 80 with vigor.

...
"As for the days of our life, they contain seventy years,
Or if due to strength, eighty years,"
(Psalm 90:10)

[? unfinished.
Someone who would idealistically extinct dinosaurs would people.]

...
"Dinosaur extinction Chicxulub crater":
trinitrotoluene Icarus China
Cretaceous incident Harcourt/tribunal
chronicler contraindicates
...
recondensation arthritic

"Poisoning and child abuse":
cannabidiol shogun

8.02. Why not?

...
"Why would the LORD use MIT librarian notation":
trinitrotoluene Amontillado
Amontillado trinitrotoluene/Northwestern/worldbeater

"Alexander suicide":
deadline ICARUS

Not possible with a wife and profession.

...
(Isaiah 53:3)
"He was despised and forsaken of men,
A man of sorrows, and acquainted with grief;
And like one from whom men hide their face,
He was despised, and we did not esteem Him."

...
"He was despised, and we did not esteem Him":
astonishment sideswiped/Messiah
emanation disesteemed/sideswiped

"Greatest of all time":
Alastair mettle
Aristotle female/eagle
alligator test
gorilla fattest

"Hercules Mulan Aladdin Pocahontas Cinderella Snow White The Little Mermaid Beauty and the Beast":
ethylenediaminetetraacetic immunoelectrophoresis

subdebutantes/Nathanael
ETHYLENEDIAMINETETRAACETIC BLAMEWORTHINESS BLAMEWORTHINESS NATHANAEL/PHAETHON/ACTAEON

"Fedishin Karpinsky Credi Sobol Krasicky Jurek":
dishonourableness acidifiers
CEREBROSCLEROSIS UKRAINIAN

...
CHILD ABUSE DEPRESSIONARY
CANNABIDIOL PREDECESSORS
irreparable insidiousness
irreparableness dishonour
responsible archdeaconry/archdiocesan
foreordain accursedness
BRAINLESS CRANIOSCOPIES/parishioners
UKRAINIAN PRESCHOOL DESCRIBES
BELORUSSIAN CHAIRPERSON
Flis precociousness handbrake
recondense lordship Jurassic

"Immaculate Conception Ukrainian Catholic Grade School":
proletarianisation coeducational/academic

[fireworks]

...
"Alexander tosses bacteria sponge":
representation obsessed
celebration patronesses/assentor

(Isaiah 53:10)
"If He would render Himself as a guilt offering":
demineralisation fleurdelis hugh [3]
wrongheadedness firelighter/forfeiture/flameout

(Isaiah 53:12)
"Because He poured out Himself to death":
autohemotherapies bedclothes/scheduled/selected [A.O. Daniv]
father (7885) automobile desuetude/custodee/dopesheet
father Themistocles beheaded
Themistocles Dorothee behead
Flis Prometheus beheaded
Flis chemoautotroph Buddha

"full moon Passover":
supernova fool
Samson pullover

["immolation is a trap":
option martialism]

LORD:
"Hodor uses time wisely":
DEMOTE SERIOUSLY/ULYSSES/OILER
DEMOLISH TOWERS

"Alexander death by immolation" (8858):
demotion inalterable
dethronement maxilla/lambda

LORD:
"polygamy splinters families":
mineralise lamppost/loyalist
earn (2522) plasmoptysis/simplifies
immolate painlessly [demineralise]

"Alexander self immolation":
demote (2111) millenarian
Lord emanation falsifies/alleluia/lifeless/maxillae

"Alexander Luka Flis self immolation":
DEMOTE Lousianians
DEMOTION Marseillaise
DEMINERALISE Faustino
DEMINERALISATION samuel

"Alexander Luka Daniv Flis self immolation":
assure demotion (1181) millennial
assure emanation manifolded
elevation lordliness Kaufman
...
iliofemoral Kaufman invalidates
Lord emanation alkalinised
...
DANDELION AFFIRMATIVENESS MAXILLA

"Alexander Luka Flis self excision":
recondenses alleluia/alfalfa
acidifies unforsaken
deifies carefulness/cleanliness/unforsaken/alleluia/assurance
lifeline Cinderella/lordliness
assure lidocaine
Delila nefariousness

"Alexander Luka Daniv Flis self excision":
ASSURE (3888) dandelion/cleveland

Crowfoot
"Isapo-Muxika Istowun-eh'pata
Akhap-say-pi":
Hippopotamus Pakistani awakens/Hanukas

[Eminem]
"Marianna Munchausen's":
Messiah unman
Riemann ashcans/manchus
marijuana amuses
Icarus unshame

CK Friends:

[Odysseus]
"Odey Meroueh":
Homer Ode

"Telemachus Yuyin Chen":
Manchu Chinese

[Colin Clarke]
"Jules Henri Poincare":
earn Colin sphere

"Flirting vs Deceiving": devirginising, infidelities, fertilising, interceding

[Consorts are a burden.
Very common after divorce.]

...
"Polygamy splinters families":
ILLEGALISE MATRIMONY
PERMISSION PLAYMATES
ALLIGATOR sliminess/NEMESIS/yippees
immortalising apple/Alfy
Allister (2282) misemploying/misapplying
angstrom ellipses/epilepsy/Messiae
lifeline pragmatism
lifeline psalmist orgasm[No thanks]
atone simplifies
mineralise lamppost/loyalist/optimal
immolate painlessly
meatloaf misspelling/grisliness
IMPALEMENT GORILLA
ALLISTER FLIS POMPEIAN

Canaan vs Israel.

Adoni-bezek Judges 1:7.
K cutting off thumbs and toes, metaphorical record of traps.

...
Alexander has scars on both left and right thumbs. Left thumb is from grade school attempting to open a glue bottle. Slightly deeper and the thumb would be paralyzed.
Right thumb is from bicycle slide at MIT, torn ligament. If not surgically reattached, lose use of thumb.

"Alexander left and right thumb scars":
authenticate marshalled/hexagram
Archimedes strangulate
Archimedes Albert annular
Nathanael burglarised

Fundamental correspondence between religion and physics.
[Take that feminists. 4/13/25]

Three families of elementary particles corresponding to three holes in curled up Calabi-Yau geometrical shapes.

LORD:
"Polygamy splinters families."

"How many holes? Four is excess, choose three."

[Publishing multidimensional unification of gravity and E&M.]

...
"Einstein restrains Kaluza":
renaissant neutralizes

...
"Einstein restrains Kaluza from publishing":

interrelationship marginalizing

[TREFOIL KNOT]

"Correct Calabi Yau shape":

baccalaureate physic/Chris/Spiro

calcosphaerite capybara

[crystallise ratpig or beaver]

ACCURATE HYPERBOLA

TRI HYPERBOLAES/hypercubes/parabolas/sepulchre [tomb]

Three bicapsular/parabolas/cubical

THREE PARABOLAS

SHOELACE BACCARAT

[9 spatial dims; closest to 9 wins]

SEPULCHRE ACROBAT

[snake, Adobe acrobat symbol]

BIRTHPLACE CAESAR

[Adobe homes, El Paso]

accelerator physic

research catabolic

...

alphabetise Curacao/cacao

alpha aristocracy/autocracies/accuracies/acrobatics/cretaceous/racecourse

laureateship carboy [beer]

laureate pariah/physic/scarab

laureate physic cobra [?!]

Alastair hypercube [Rubik]

hypercube acrostical [permutation]

SHAPIRO BETRAYAL [IHES symbol; Haute, Utah]

[Triad]

"Trefoil knot": Ko orient

Same universal covering of complements in R^3 of

(Trefoil knot in R^3) \times Disc,

(Disc with three disc holes) \times $[0,1]$.

"Eleven dimensional M theory":

Mohamed reinvention

"Ramanujan Theta Function":

caftan Metatron/Ruthenium/Marianne

Meta annunciator

Marianna cotenant

...

authenticator, antineutron, antimatter

...

emanation Arjuna

Manchurian enfant

refutation manhunt

theft marijuana

Actaeon antihuman

The Riemann Hypothesis

[1/2]

"Then the king said to her, 'What is troubling you, Queen Esther? And what is your request? Even to half of the kingdom it will be given to you.' " (Esther 5:3)

...

"Even to half of the kingdom it will be given to you.":

knowledgeability (1444) helmeting (222) footnote

...

(Esther 2:5)

"Mordecai Jair Shimei Kish Benjamite":

Archimedes (3733) tribesman

SKETCH.
Applying omniscience to first verify.
Probability distribution of permutational word splittings gives clues for constructive proof.
Adam's apple demonstrated historically, constructively in physics with Calabi Yau, extends to mathematics.

[4/18/25]
"Maximal Proof of Riemann Hypothesis":
mineralisation (887) mesomorph [compact]/prophesy
mineralise promotion payoff
expiation horsemanship royal/Alfy/fool
Alpha Messiah premonition/promotion
...
Mephistophelian Aaron
explanation homeomorphisms fair
approximation ammonolysis/formalise/formalism
approximation formalise money
RESONANT (2922) HOMEOMORPHISM AXIAL
syntonies axial preaffirm
prime harmonisation employs
entropy harmonise maximal
RATIONAL (3393) HOMEOMORPHISM AFFINE
THEOREM ISOMORPHISM PIANO [WHAT KEY?!!]

"Key to Riemann Hypothesis":
transposition hem [pause]
Eratosthenes nympho [sieve, 333]
metaphor Einstein/keystone/syntonies
resonant epitomise
syntonies hemiatrophy/Ephraim
syntony hemisphere/temporise
hemisphere notation
ORIENT (2262) SYMPHONIES/SYMPHONY
OMNIPOTENT REHASHES/essayer/Kessiah/kaiser

...
ESTHER PIANO MONTHS [12]
astonishment Ko
Smithson (1121) Phaeton eyrie/reeky
...
Messiah thiopentone [truth serum]
Messiae pointer/potter/thinker/theory/throne/throop/trophy

"Riemann Hypothesis":
hemiatrophies [hemi 1/2]
HYPHENATION SEMI
...
THEOREM SPANISH [peninsular]/SINAPIS [gaps]/Issiah/PINYIN [primes are alphabet of numbers]
theory (443) misshapen
PRIME SYNTONIES/synthase/tensions/thinness/Hessian/intones/isolate
SYNTONIES EPHRAIM [1/2 tribe]
RESONANT SEMI
PRIME ISOHYET NASH
[Line of equal rainfall]
hyphen assertion
SEMI IT SPANNER

...
ESTHER MINION/NYMPHO/PIANO
entropy seisinam
[writ of execution commanding sheriff to give recovered ownership]
pinyin thermoses/maestro
Thermo sisyphian
Nemesis Hanoi/piano/Torah
...
Messiae trophy
Messiah Phenytoin [for epilepsy]
HaShem insertion/seniority

pointer (313) Messiah/myiasis [fly maggot]/HaShem
enthroned Issiah

"The Riemann Hypothesis":

thermohypesthesia [... theorem]
hemihypesthesia [... hemi 1/2]
hypertensinase [... hyphen or line]

...

THEOREM SISYPHEAN

[Corinth founder, murders brother Salmoneus]/pithiness/shintyan [baggy trousers, error]
THEORY (1116) INSEMINATES

[Insects have six legs, sperm have 1/2 chromosomes]
prime synthetase/athetesis [beetle]

SYNTONIES HEMIPTERA

RESONANT SEMITE/SMITH/SEMI

SEMI HYPHENATION/penetration
ISOHYET HEMIPTERAN [half wing]
hyphen estimation
hyphenate isotherm

...

ESTHER HYPHENATION

entropy heathenism [K, chaos]
Einstein metaphors/maestro [1/2]
antithesis phoneme [alphabet]
Pinyin (888) metatheses [permute sounds]
Thermo hypesthesia/hyphenates
Nemesis Phaeton

...

Messiae Phenytoin/Hyperion/potter/throne
Messiah retention/enthroned/penitent/thirteen
HaShem hypertension
pointer Messiae/Messiah [Branch]
enthroned metaphysis [bone gap]

"zeta nontrivial zeros":

REAL ORIENTATION [pointer, arrow, branch]
ION ALTERNATIVES [1/2]
elevator Zionist
avianise Lotto
Israel nervation [branching]
resonant variolite [spotted matrix volcanic rock]/levator/Voltaire/violet

"Riemann zeta nontrivial zeros":

SEMI REAL ORIENTATION [1/2]
elevator insemination/emanation
Israel reorientation
resonant mineralization/intermezzo [inserted music]/mezzanine [halfway between floors 0 and 1]

[885, 887]

"William Thomson Baron Kelvin" (8758):
mineralisation (100) hollow
annihilation worm
BOSTON (2007) MILLENARIAN
immolation Brownsville [demotes]
killer abomination

[Josef Alexander]

"Erwin Rudolf Josef Alexander Schrödinger":
fleurdelis recondensing

"David Hilbert": triad devil/evil

"Alexander related to David Hilbert":

revelation (1666) extraditable

"Thomson Schrodinger Hilbert":
enthroned christ blood/lord

[INCOMPLETE]

"particle of time":
felicitor, imperfect, meteoric, compare, miracle, optimal, trefoil, atomic, primal, limit, timer

...
IMPERFECT IOTA
meteor italic
COMPARE LEFT/TILT
MIRACLE TIPTOE
TREFOIL IMPACT

..
TOE amplifier/empirical/miracle
potter Alfie

"nature of time":
attermine (limit), orientate, terminate, fermion, matter, meteor, minute, orient, fermi, meter, unite,
atom, earn

...
ORIENTATE [arrow]
ORIENT TAU
FERMION TAU
matter fine
meteor anti
MINUTE AFTER
fermi notate
meter unit
unite Fermat
ATOM TRIUNE
earn timeout

"interstellar portals":
transport Allister/literal/realest/realise
potter (1119) Alastair/Allister
real trainspotter

"Alcubierre Drive":
Uriel cabdriver

"Intergalactic travel is possible":
contractibilities passage

"Faster than light travel":
interstellar/restraighten
elevating astral/tartar
EARTH SHATTERING
lifesaver Hagar